

Proceedings from FONETIK 2024
Stockholm, June 3–5, 2024

PERILUS XXVIII, June 2024

Edited by

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ISSN 0282-6690

ISBN 978-91-89107-40-3 (printed version)

ISBN 978-91-89107-41-0 (web version)

Printed by Publit, Stockholm 2024

Distributor: Department of Linguistics, Stockholm University

Previous Swedish Phonetic Conferences

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VI	1992	Chalmers and Göteborg University
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XXIV	2016	KTH Stockholm
—	2017	(Interspeech 2017 in Stockholm)
XXX	2018	University of Gothenburg
XXXI	2019	Stockholm University
—	2020	Cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic
XXXII	2021	Lund University
XXXIII	2022	KTH Stockholm
—	2023	Cancelled
XXXIV	2024	Stockholm University

Preface

This volume contains the contributions to FONETIK 2024, *the XXXIVth Swedish Phonetics Conference*, organized by the Department of Linguistics at Stockholm University, June 3–5 2024. The papers have not been peer-reviewed, and they appear in the order in which they were planned to be given at the conference.

Only a limited number of copies of this volume have been printed. For access to electronic versions of the contributions, please see <http://www.fonetik.se>.

We would like to thank all authors for their contributions. We would also like to thank Fonetikstiftelsen for financial support.

Stockholm in May 2024

On behalf of the organisers,

Mattias Heldner

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Participants

Ambika Kirkland	KTH
Anita McAllister	Karolinska Institutet
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Anna Jespersen	University of Copenhagen
Anna Persson	Stockholm University
Anne-Marie Öster	KTH
Annika Høeg	Stockholm University
Axel Ekström	KTH
Björn Granström	KTH
Björn Hammarberg	Stockholm University
Björn Lindblom	Stockholm University
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Christine Ericsson Nordgren	Stockholm University
Christopher Cox	Aarhus University
Daniel Friedrichs	University of Zurich
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Exploring the implications of discrete categories along an acoustic correlate

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Abstract

The present paper provides empirical evidence that the change in intensity during the production of the Spanish alveolar tap in a variety of Mexican Spanish is best characterized by two distributions instead of one, replicating a recent finding from another variety of Spanish. The finding of multiple ‘categories’ along an acoustic gradient is discussed in the context of the implications for phonetic theory and analyzing acoustic measurements. We outline future steps and questions that we believe will be important to address, starting with the nature of statistical vs. phonetic categories, as well as incorporating knowledge of acoustics-to-articulatory mapping into the discussion of phonetic variability.

Introduction

Speech production research that has investigated several varieties of Spanish has demonstrated that there is substantial acoustic variation in the production of the alveolar tap (Amengual, 2016; Bradley & Willis, 2012; Henriksen, 2015; Kim & Repiso-Puigdeliura, 2020; Willis & Bradley, 2008). Two example tokens outlining this variability are depicted in Figure 1. Recent modelling of the intensity difference (IntDiff) between the minimum during the tap and the maximum of the surrounding vowels by Perry et al.

(2024) showed that an assumption of two latent pronunciation variants of the tap, coded into the model as two distinct distributions, was required in order to adequately model the data. The first goal of the present study is to analyze a corpus comprised of spontaneous speech from a variety of Mexican Spanish to investigate whether this finding replicates in a new set of data from another dialect. Our second goal is to explore what having discrete categories along acoustic correlates could mean for phonetic theory, especially when this variation is generally thought of as gradient.

Figure 1. Spectrograms and waveforms of taps with intensity curves overlaid. The top panel shows a tap produced as a stop, while the bottom panel shows a highly reduced variant produced as an approximant.

It is generally accepted that the phonetic variation we observe in speech production can be thought of as falling along a continuum from carefully enunciated speech on one end to highly ‘reduced’ speech on the other (Tucker & Mukai, 2023). There have been several proposals which attempt to explain this variation not as noise, but instead as part of the signal that can help us understand the cognitive mechanisms of speech production (e.g., Aylett & Turk, 2004; Bell et al., 2009; Jaeger, 2010). One such proposal is H&H Theory, put forth by Lindblom (1990), which states that phonetic variation results partially from obedience to the principle of economy of effort while producing speech, leading to more phonetic reduction in situations where the signal will be easier to discriminate.

If we assume that the phonetic variability present in speech can inform cognitive models of speech production, then the physical properties of the acoustic signal need to be properly accounted for when modelling this variation. That is to say that models with acoustic correlates as the dependent variable need to, at minimum, be compatible with the patterns we observe when measuring speech. We also need to consider the fact that any cognitive pressures shaping speech production are doing so through changes in articulation, which are then responsible for the acoustic signal. Most studies which analyze acoustic correlates of reduction implicitly or explicitly treat this variation as gradient within phonemic categories, and generally do not provide evidence that the statistical models are descriptively adequate. In contrast with gradient within-category phonetic variability, some analyses do show both gradient and categorical variation. Examples of this include the voicing implementation of obstruents in English (Davidson, 2016), schwa deletion in French (Bürki et al., 2011), and, central

to the present paper, alveolar tap variation in Spanish (Perry et al., 2024).

The first goal of the present study is to attempt to replicate a finding from Perry and colleagues (hereafter P24), namely, that analyzing the IntDiff of Spanish alveolar taps using a finite mixture model with two distributions leads to a better fit to the data than using a single distribution. To identify whether the bimodal nature of IntDiff reported in P24 can be sidestepped by employing a different proxy of consonant reduction, we also look at another acoustic measurement: the maximum velocity of the intensity curve leaving the tap.

Materials and methods

The data analyzed in the present paper is spontaneous speech data from first-language speakers of Spanish from Querétaro, México (N=13). Their speech was recorded using a head-mounted microphone in a sound-attenuated booth during a phone conversation with a friend or relative, which lasted approximately 15 minutes. The speech of the participants was orthographically transcribed and subsequently aligned using the Montreal Forced Aligner (McAuliffe et al., 2017). For additional details regarding the creation and preparation of the corpus, the reader is directed to Hernandez et al. (2023).

To model the acoustic variability of alveolar taps in our corpus, we extracted acoustic measurements and information about the tap and surrounding words and segments with a script in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2022) as in P24. This gave us our intensity measures as well as the quality of the surrounding vowels, the identity of the word containing the tap, as well as the average speech rate of the utterance in syllables per second. We also measured the maximum slope of the intensity curve leaving the tap, which has been used as a measure of lenition in previous studies of other consonants (e.g., Simonet et al., 2012).

Statistical analysis

To model the variation in IntDiff, we fit a series of generalized Bayesian hierarchical models using package *brms* (Bürkner, 2017) in *R* (R Core Team, 2021). All models predicted IntDiff using an additive combination of the following variables: log unigram frequency as calculated from the OpenSubtitles corpus (Lison & Tiedemann, 2016), log local speech rate (syllables/s), whether the preceding and following vowels bore lexical stress, and the vowel quality of the preceding and following vowels. All models had a varying intercept for speaker.

The first model had a single skew-normal distribution as the likelihood function. Following P24, we then moved to fitting finite mixture models comprised of two skew-normal distributions. In order to aid model identification, this model was fit using informative priors for the intercepts for the means of the two distributions, which were based on the posteriors of the models fit in P24, but with wider scale parameters. All population-level effects were centred at zero to provide regularization, with the priors' scale parameters informed by the largest relevant effects reported in P24. Finally, we fit a model with three skew-normal distributions, again with the intercepts being informed by P24, this time in the form of the descriptive statistics reported for the qualitative categories coded visually using a spectrogram. As one would expect due to the increased complexity, this last model had computational issues.

Results

The first goal of the present paper was to replicate the finding of P24. Specifically, we wanted to know if the predictive performance of our statistical model was improved when we modelled IntDiff of Spanish taps using more than one distribution. This corresponds to the

assumption that there are two latent categories of the tap, which were referred to as 'reduced' and 'unreduced' by P24.

This finding is replicated with our present data. In Table 1, we report the model comparisons using the leave-one-out information criterion (LOOIC; Vehtari et al., 2017), which show that the model with two skew-normal distributions outperforms the model with a single distribution, and that the estimated improvement is more than four times the standard error of the difference. This improvement from one skew-normal distribution to two was a less certain improvement compared to the one reported in P24, where the improvement in LOOIC was more than 8 times the standard error of the difference.

Table 1. The results of the model comparison via LOOIC. The second column shows the difference in the expected log predictive density (ELPD) compared to the best model. The third column shows the standard error (SE) of the difference; a measure of uncertainty regarding the comparison. The models with likelihoods comprised of two and three skew-normal distributions have similar estimated out-of-sample predictive accuracy, and they both outperform the model with only a single distribution.

Model	Difference in ELPD	SE of difference
2-dist	0	0
3-dist	-1.8	7.1
1-dist	-41.8	9.8

In Figure 2 below, we include a visualization of the maximum velocity of the intensity slope coming out of the tap, as well as a visualization of IntDiff. The distribution for the maximum velocity of the intensity slope is clearly bimodal, indicating that the issue of a single distribution being inadequate for modelling the data is not an issue with IntDiff specifically, and it at least

extends to one other acoustic correlate used to measure stop reduction.

Another difference between the present findings and those from P24 are the visual nature of the posterior predictive checks. While the skew-normal likelihood was clearly inappropriate for modelling IntDiff in P24, this may not have been as clear for the current data. Posterior checks presented in Figure 3 show only a small visual improvement when shifting from generalized linear models to finite mixture models.

Figure 2. The estimated density distribution of the maximum velocity of the intensity slope leading out of the tap for the present data (A) and the estimated density distributions of IntDiff for the present dataset and the hand-corrected data from P24 (B).

Discussion

The finding of two latent pronunciation variants improving our modelling of the IntDiff of Spanish taps, which has now been found for two different varieties of the language (Mexican and Iberian), raises questions regarding acoustic measurement as well as what this finding means for phonetic theories. In the present discussion, we do not offer any definitive explanation or account of this, but instead sketch out what we believe to be important considerations that deserve to be empirically evaluated

moving forward. However, before we turn to this more general discussion, we discuss the differences between the findings presented here and those from P24.

The first notable difference is the distribution of IntDiff itself. P24 presented a clear bimodal distribution of IntDiff (Figure 2B). In contrast, the deviation of the present distribution from a skew-normal distribution was not as obvious and may not have raised concern for all speech researchers (Figure 3A). Potential reasons for this difference are numerous. Cross-dialectal differences cannot be ruled out, but conclusions regarding potential differences are hampered by differences in the recording equipment and elicitation method, which could feasibly be responsible for some of the observed differences. The data analyzed in the present paper are from phone conversations between two people, while those analyzed by P24 took place in a face-to-face setting in groups of three. Any future work looking to make comparisons across dialects would be strengthened by keeping recording and elicitation methods consistent.

We turn now to how we might integrate these findings concerning the production of the Spanish tap into the body of research investigating the cognitive factors at play during speech production. The first avenue that we believe should be investigated is bringing articulatory data to bear on this issue. As acknowledged in P24, it is possible that the latent categories we observe in our acoustic correlates are, in fact, not present in articulation. It is also possible that the nature of the acoustics is related to the movement and/or timing of multiple articulators.

Figure 3. Depicted in this figure are the posterior predictive checks comparing the observed IntDiff values in black to ten datasets simulated from the model. Panel A corresponds to the model with a likelihood comprised of a single skew-normal distribution, panel B to the model with two distributions, and panel C to the model with three distributions.

Research that has attempted to map articulation to acoustics and vice-versa has shown the relationship is complex, and often employs mixture models or other models with multiple discrete states to handle the mapping (Ananthakrishnan & Engwall, 2011). It is possible that these flexible models are needed because the complex coordination and movement of the vocal tract creates statistical grouping effects in acoustic correlates that simple regression cannot account for.

If, after examining the articulation, it is still clear that there are multiple discrete pronunciation variants of the Spanish tap, we can explore the ramifications for theories of speech production and sound systems in general. As these variants would not be phonemic in nature, we would most readily refer to them as allophones in free variation. However, as discussed by Pierrehumbert (2002), it is desirable for several reasons to keep the total number of allophones to a minimum when outlining a probabilistic model of phonology that integrates lexical effects. This issue of multiple variants may extend to stop consonants more generally, as they are often reduced in both spontaneous and read speech (e.g., Barry & Andreeva, 2001; Warner & Tucker, 2011). It will have to be determined whether reduced variants

have their own representation in the speech production system, or if general patterns of articulatory undershoot and/or coarticulation can be solely responsible for patterns of reduction that are both gradient and categorical.

Overall, the findings of the present study and those of P24 have raised several questions regarding patterns of variability in the production of the Spanish tap and how to account for them in a cognitive model of speech production. Even if these more complex mixture models are only relevant in accounting for the complex mapping between articulation and acoustics, they need to be integrated into phonetic analyses so that we can better capture the wide range of acoustic variability present in the speech signal when using statistical models to understand potential cognitive effects on speech production.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded partially by a grant from the US National Science Foundation: BCS-1022313.

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When aspiration meets voicing: Native Danish speakers' production of Spanish initial stop voicing

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Abstract

The present study examines how native speakers of a language with a short-lag vs long-lag aspiration contrast (Danish) for initial stop consonants realize the voicing contrast (prevoiced vs short-lag) in their foreign language (L2), Spanish. We report and compare the voice onset time (VOT) of Danish and of Spanish initial stops as produced by 23 native (L1) Danish speakers who are learning Spanish as an L2 in high school. Both beginning and intermediate learners produced Spanish voiceless stops with significantly shorter VOTs than their Danish counterparts, but they never prevoiced, producing Spanish voiced stops with VOTs that did not differ from their L1 short-lag stops. These results fit in with previous studies which have shown that both experienced and inexperienced learners adjust, but do not reach, the VOT of L2 stops in the positive (aspirated) range. Our participants thus exhibit sensitivity to aspiration differences, but are apparently insensitive to prevoicing.

Introduction

As illustrated schematically in Figure 1, languages with a binary phonological voicing contrast for initial stop consonants typically implement this contrast using either aspiration (short-lag vs long-lag) or voicing (prevoicing vs short-lag).

The second language (L2) learning scenarios that arise from the difference between “aspiration” languages and “voicing” languages have been studied

Figure 1: Typical implementation of the binary phonological voicing contrast through presence vs absence of voicing (left) or presence vs absence of aspiration (right).

mostly with respect to how adult L1 speakers of a voicing language with [p, t, k] produce and perceive the long-lag stops [p^h, t^h, k^h] of an aspiration language. These studies typically report compromise values for long-lag stops, i.e., values that are intermediate between the L1 short-lag and the L2 long-lag stops (e.g., Flege & Eefting, 1987). Even the highly experienced L1 Spanish speakers in the Garibaldi & Bohn (2017) study did not produce Danish long-lag stops with target values with but with compromise values.

A smaller number of studies has examined the reverse scenario, i.e., how adult speakers of an aspiration language produce and perceive the short-lag stops of a voicing language. These studies reveal the same pattern as the one mentioned above: An approximation of the target language VOT with compromise values, without actually reaching these values, both for relatively inexperienced and for experienced L2 learners. (e.g., Flege 1987, Major 1990).

To the best of our knowledge, no study has yet examined how L1 speakers of an aspiration language with short-lag [p, t, k] produce and perceive the prevoiced stops [b, d, g] of a voicing

language. Addressing this lacuna presents one of the motivations for the present study, which is based on Ahle (2023), and which asks the following questions:

☐ How do L1 speakers of an aspiration language produce the stops of a voicing language?

☐ Do learners show a sensitivity towards the L2 way of implementing the voicing contrast by either producing reduced aspiration intervals for [p, t, k] and/or prevoicing for [b, d, g]?

☐ Is the L2 production of the voicing contrast affected by the length of Spanish language instruction?

Characteristics of the two languages

Both the Spanish (SP) and the Danish (DK) way using VOT for implementing the phonological voicing contrast for stops in initial position has been studied extensively. Even though these studies may differ widely in how they elicited tokens (e.g., following stressed or unstressed vowel, carrier phrase or not, etc.) the overall picture is clear:

SP has a contrast between initially prevoiced stops (range: ca. -90 ms to -60 ms VOT) and unaspirated stops (range: ca. 14 ms to 30 ms VOT), with increasing VOT values from anterior to posterior places of articulation.

DK has a contrast between initially unaspirated stops (range: ca. 6 ms to 35 ms VOT) and aspirated stops (range: ca. 30 ms to 140 ms). DK is remarkable in two respects: Unlike other languages with an unaspirated vs aspirated voicing contrast (e.g., English, see Dmitrieva et al. 2015), DK stops in initial stressed position are never optionally prevoiced. Also, whereas VOT increases in many (most?) languages as the place of articulation moves from anterior to posterior (Lisker & Abramson, 1964; Cho & Ladefoged, 1999), DK aspirated coronal stops typically have a longer VOT than velar stops (e.g., Fischer-Jørgensen 1954, Mortensen & Tøndering 2013, but see Puggaard

2023), and they are also heavily affricated, which is why they are transcribed here as [ts] following Schachtenhaufen (2022).

Methods

Participants

Two groups of adolescent L1 Danish speakers (age range: 16-19 years) participated. They were learning Spanish as a foreign language in high school in Aarhus, Denmark. Group 1g consisted of 13 students who had taken Spanish classes for 9 months with lessons of two times 90 minutes per week at the time of the study, and group 3g consisted of 11 students who had taken Spanish classes for more than two years with lessons of three times 90 minutes per week at the time of the study. The teachers for both groups were L1 Danish speakers, and the languages of instruction were both Danish and Spanish, with increased use of Spanish in the advanced 3g classes.

Materials and Procedure

Participants read Spanish and Danish disyllabic real words embedded in Spanish and Danish carrier sentences. The initial segment of the word was [b, d, g, p, t, k] for the Spanish tokens and [p, t, k, p^h, ts, k^h] for the Danish tokens. Because VOT is affected by stress (Lisker & Abramson, 1967) and by the following vowel (Port & Rotunno, 1979; Mortensen & Tøndering 2013), both the Spanish and Danish words had initial stress, they occurred in initial position in the carrier sentences, and the following vowel was either [i, a] or [u], which Danish and Spanish share.

Tokens were elicited by presenting individual power point slides for each word. Half of the participants read a randomized Spanish list first, and the other half, a randomized Danish list. Recordings were conducted individually in a quiet environment using Zoom H2n digital recorder. Each participant

recorded 72 tokens, resulting in (23 participants x 72 tokens) = 1656 tokens. A total of 189 tokens were not used for further analysis (because of technical problems, noise, or failure of participants to follow instructions). In addition, three prevoiced tokens, all from one participant's total of 72 tokens, were considered outliers and not included in the analysis. This resulted in a total of 1464 tokens for analysis.

VOT was measured using *praat* (Boersma & Weenink, 2022) following standard procedures, i.e., by measuring the interval between the onset of the release burst and the onset of periodicity in waveform displays.

Results

VOT in Danish initial stops

We first compared the mean VOT values produced by 1g and 3g for Danish stops using t-tests for each place of articulation. Table 1 shows the mean VOT values for the DK unaspirated stops. The two groups did not differ significantly ($p > .3$) with respect to any of the VOT values.

Table 1. Mean VOT values (in ms) as produced for Danish unaspirated initial stops by two groups of Danish high school students. SD in parentheses.

	p	t	k
1g	20.5 (8.6)	22.4 (10.5)	31.0 (11.8)
3g	20.5 (7.6)	24.9 (10.1)	32.2 (9.0)

The values for the aspirated stops are shown in Table 2. The mean VOT values for [ts] and [k^h] did not differ significantly between the two groups. However, the VOT values for [p^h] produced by 1g were significantly shorter than those produced by 3g ($p = .0289$).

Table 2. Mean VOT values (in ms) as produced for Danish aspirated initial stops by two groups of Danish high school students. SD in parentheses.

	p ^h	ts	k ^h
1g	64.8 (17.8)	107.1 (26.1)	88.9 (19.0)
3g	72.0 (19.8)	102.9 (26.1)	94.3 (24.0)

VOT in Spanish initial stops

Table 3 shows the mean VOT values produced by 1g and 3g for target Spanish prevoiced stops, and Table 4 the VOT values produced by 1g and 3g for target Spanish unaspirated stops. Separate t-tests for each place of articulation revealed that the differences between the two groups were nonsignificant ($p > .4$).

Table 3. Mean VOT values (in ms) as produced for target Spanish prevoiced initial stops by two groups of Danish high school students. SD in parentheses.

	b	d	g
1g	20.0 (7.6)	25.5 (8.5)	29.6 (9.1)
3g	20.0 (7.2)	26.7 (8.7)	30.7 (9.6)

Table 4. Mean VOT values (in ms) as produced for target Spanish unaspirated initial stops by two groups of Danish high school students. SD in parentheses.

	p	t	k
1g	48.6 (21.9)	63.8 (40.1)	60.8 (22.3)
3g	57.6 (24.2)	61.6 (27.2)	67.1 (67.1)

Comparison of Danish and Spanish stop productions

This section compares the production of phonologically voiced and voiceless stops separately for each group and place of articulation. We used paired t-tests to establish whether the participants

produced differences between SP and DK cognates. The figures below are box plots in which the vertical line within each box represents the median, the lower and upper lines of the box the lower and the upper quartile, respectively, and the whiskers extending from the boxes represent the range.

Phonologically voiced stops

Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate how the participants from 1g and from 3g produced the phonologically voiced stops in their L1, DK, and in their L2, SP. The figures show that the participants produced the SP target prevoiced stops as unaspirated stops. The paired t-tests revealed that the VOT values for the DK unaspirated and the target SP voiced stops did not differ significantly ($p > .4$) for 1g and for 3g for any of the places of articulation, except for the coronal stops produced by 1g, whose target SP voiced stops had significantly longer mean VOTs (25.4 ms) than their DK unaspirated stops (22.4 ms), $t(262) = 2.826$, $p = .00634$. These results indicate that both L1 DK groups produced stops which in the L2 have lead VOT as unaspirated stops whose VOT values were more or less the same as those of the L1 unaspirated stops.

Figure 2. VOT values for DK unaspirated and SP target voiced stops as produced by 1g.

Figure 3. VOT values for DK unaspirated and SP target voiced stops as produced by 3g.

Phonologically voiceless stops

Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate how the participants from 1g and from 3g produced the phonologically voiceless stops in their L1, DK, and in their L2, SP. The figures show that both groups produced the SP target unaspirated stops as aspirated stops, but the figures also suggest that both groups produced these stops with reduced VOT values vis-à-vis their native DK values. This impression is confirmed by paired t-tests, which, for both groups and for all three places of articulation, revealed highly significant differences ($p < .001$) between the VOT values produced for SP and DK words.

Figure 4. VOT values for DK aspirated and SP target unaspirated stops as produced by 1g.

Figure 5. VOT values for DK aspirated and SP target unaspirated stops as produced by 3g.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present study examined how speakers of a language which uses aspiration to differentiate voicing in initial stops produce a voicing contrast in a language which uses voicing to differentiate initial stops. Two groups of L1 Danish speakers differing in Spanish language experience produced word-initial stops in stressed syllables for all three places of articulation in their L1, Danish, and in their L2, Spanish.

We found that both groups produced target unaspirated Spanish stops as aspirated stops with long-lag VOT values. However, these values were consistently and significantly shorter than the VOT values for the L1 DK aspirated stops, suggesting that the DK learners had developed a sensitivity towards the reduced VOT values for SP voiceless stops. Several earlier studies have likewise reported that even minimal exposure to a language which differentiates stops using voicing (prevoiced vs unaspirated) may result in the production of “compromise” VOT values by L1 speakers of an aspiration language, i.e., VOT values that are consistently intermediate between the values produced by native speakers of the languages (e.g., Flege & Hammond 1982, Flege & Eefting 1987).

No such sensitivity to the L2 values was found for Spanish prevoiced stops. We found that both groups produced target prevoiced Spanish stops as

unaspirated stops whose VOT values did not differ from the L1 unaspirated stops.

There are two aspects about the present study that are remarkable: First, that the two-year difference in Spanish-language experience in high school classes between groups 1g and 3g had no effect on the production of VOT values for syllable-initial Spanish stops. Both groups produced compromise VOT values for Spanish unaspirated stops, and both groups did appear insensitive to Spanish prevoicing, producing initial short-lag stops instead of target prevoiced stops.

It would be interesting to see in further studies how much Spanish-language experience (both in terms of quality and quantity) is needed for learners whose L1 has an aspiration contrast to show some sensitivity to prevoicing in the L2 so that they will produce prevoiced stops. It would also be interesting to investigate whether this amount of experience would be different for L1 speakers of an aspiration language which does not have optional prevoicing (e.g., Danish) as opposed to an aspiration language with optional prevoicing (e.g., English).

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Measuring the informativity of F3 for rounded and unrounded high-front vowels in Central Swedish

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Abstract

The Swedish vowel space is densely populated, especially in the high-front part of the space. One hypothesis holds that third formant information (F3) helps distinguish rounded and unrounded high-front vowels. The present study uses a simple model of speech perception to investigate the predicted consequences of including F3 for the perception of the high-front vowels. Ideal observer models were trained on vowel production data under different assumptions about the cue space (F1-F2 vs. F1-F2-F3) and evaluated on how well they predict the category intended by the talker. Results indicate that F3-inclusion facilitates recognition accuracy.

Introduction

The Central Swedish vowel space is densely crowded in the first two formants (F1-F2). It contains a total of 21 vowel categories that differ in quantity—assumed to be primarily cued by vowel duration—and quality—assumed to be primarily cued by formants. Category overlap in F1-F2 space is particularly pronounced among the high-front vowels, highlighted in Figure 1 (Persson, 2024). This has prompted research on what additional acoustic cues might allow listeners to distinguish between these vowels. One long-standing hypothesis holds that the third formant (F3) correlates with lip-rounding, allowing listeners to distinguish rounded and unrounded vowels, such as [i:]-[y:] (e.g., Fant, Henningsson & Stålhammar, 1969; Fujimura, 1967; Kuronen, 2000;

for a review see e.g., Rosner & Pickering, 1994).

Figure 1. Summary of vowel productions from the *SwehVd* database described in more detail below. High-front vowels that constitute the focus of the present study are highlighted. Adapted for the present purpose from Persson (2024). Ellipses show 95% probability mass of bivariate Gaussians fit to the data.

This question has been approached in a number of ways. One approach has been to qualitatively compare the realization of F3 in rounded and unrounded vowels, typically on a small number of recordings. For example, Kuronen (2000) compared the realization of [i:] and [y:] by four talkers, and found that the two vowels tended to differ in their F3 (see also Fant et al., 1969). Another approach has been to measure the effects of F3 on listeners' perception. For example, Fujimura (1967) exposed Swedish listeners to synthesized [i:]-[y:]-[u:]

continua, while varying F3. Based on listeners' responses, Fujimura argued that F3 affected listeners' perception. This particular approach has, however, been criticized for confounding multiple cues (e.g., Rosner & Pickering, 1994): while F1 and F4 were kept constant across the synthesized tokens, F2 and F3 covaried inversely. This makes it impossible to conclude that F3 was the cause for changes in listeners' perception.

A third approach—the one we pursue here—is to use computational models of speech perception to assess the *predicted* perceptual consequences of F3-inclusion. For example, Johnson & Sjerps (2021) compared the performance of support vector machines in categorizing US English vowels, either with only as F1 and F2 as input, or while also including F3. This yielded improved recognition accuracy when F3 was included. Another recent study has applied a similar approach to the recognition of Central Swedish vowels. In Persson & Jaeger (2023), we compared fifteen different normalization accounts for the perception of Central Swedish vowels. Critically, we did so under different assumptions about what cues Swedish listeners rely on in categorizing vowels: just F1 and F2 or also additional cues. The results indicated that the inclusion of F3 resulted in equivalent or improvements in recognition accuracy for all fifteen normalization accounts, compared to models based on F1 and F2 alone. This result held across all 21 vowels of Central Swedish.

Here, we follow-up on this work but focus specifically on the high-front vowels—i.e., the vowels for which F3 has been hypothesized to be particularly important. Following Persson & Jaeger (2023), we use a general model of speech perception based on Bayesian inference, ideal observers (e.g., Nearey & Hogan, 1986; for review, see Xie, Jaeger & Kurumada, 2023). We investigate to what extent a model trained on F1-F2-F3

predicts higher recognition accuracy for the high-front vowels, than a model trained on F1-F2. If F3 indeed carries information about high-front vowels, we would expect the model that includes F3 to achieve higher recognition accuracy relative to a model based on only F1 and F2.

Materials and methods

Materials

The materials are a subset of the *SwehVd* database of Central Swedish *h-VOWEL-d* words, recorded in 2020-2024 at Stockholm University (described in Persson & Jaeger, 2023). *SwehVd* contains recordings and annotations of 44 (24 female) talkers of Central Swedish, born and raised in the Greater Stockholm area, of 18-44 years of age at the time of recording (mean age = 30, SD = 6.82).

All talkers were recorded reading 10 repetitions of all 21 Central Swedish vowels. The database contains F1-F2-F3 measurements for each talker at five different time-points of the vowel (at 20, 35, 50, 65 and 80% into the vowel), as well as vowel duration and mean f_0 across the entire vowel segment.

For the present study, we focus on the cluster of high-front vowels [i:], [i], [y:], [y], [e:], and [ø:] (see Figure 1). We included all productions of these vowels from all talkers in the database, excluding outliers and mis-pronounced vowels (using the same criteria as described in Persson, 2024).

To obtain a reliable estimate of the formant values at the steady state of the vowel, we obtained the geometric mean across the three mid-points of the vowel (at 35, 50 and 65% into the vowel).

To adjust for inter-talker variability in formant realization, as caused by differences in talkers' vocal tract physiology, formants were normalized using Nearey's uniform scaling account (Nearey, 1978). Uniform scaling was used because it has been found to

provide equally good of better fits against human perception than more complex normalization accounts (Barreda, 2021; Persson, Barreda, & Jaeger, 2024).

Bayesian ideal observers

Ideal observers have been found to provide a good fit against human speech perception (e.g., Norris & McQueen, 2008; Kleinschmidt & Jaeger, 2015; Kronrod, Coppess & Feldman, 2016). Ideal observers describe optimal use of available information, based on previous experience. For categorization, ideal observers describe the posterior probability of a given category as dependent on both the prior probability of the category in the current context, $p(\text{category})$, and the likelihood of the acoustic input under the hypothesis that it pertains to the category, $p(\text{cues}|\text{category})$:

$$p(\text{category}|\text{cues}) = \frac{p(\text{cues}|\mu, \Sigma) \times p(\text{category})}{\sum_c p(\text{cues}|\mu_c, \Sigma_c) \times p(\text{category}_c)} \quad (1)$$

Here, we follow the implementation of ideal observers adopted in Persson & Jaeger (2023), including the simplifying assumptions of e.g., uniform priors and multivariate Gaussian category representations. For the 6 vowels included here, $p(\text{category}) = .167$. The cue likelihood, $p(\text{cues}|\text{category})$, is assumed to be a multivariate Gaussian distribution, defined by the category mean (μ) and the variance-covariance matrix (Σ).

Five-fold cross-validation

To avoid over-fitting to the sample, a five-fold cross-validation approach was adopted to obtain 5 separate estimates of model predictions for each combination of cues: F1-F2 or F1-F2-F3. Following Persson & Jaeger (2023), the data was split by talker and category into five separate folds. For each fold, an ideal observer was fit on four of the folds, and subsequently tested on the fifth held-out fold (using the R package MVBELIEFUPDATR, Jaeger, 2024). This

resulted in 2 (cue spaces) * 5 (folds) = 10 ideal observer models.

Results and discussion

Recognition accuracy depending on F3-inclusion

Averaging over the six high-front vowels, F3 improves recognition accuracy of the ideal observer from 55% to 69%. This change was statistically significant, as confirmed by a logistic regression predicting accurate (1) vs. inaccurate (0) recognition as a function of the phonetic space (F1-F2-F3 vs. F1-F2; $\hat{\beta} = .129$, $p < .0001$). This result suggest that F3 carries helpful information for the categorization of high-front vowels.

To further assess how the inclusion of F3 affects the recognition of individual vowels, Figure 2 summarizes the recognition accuracy for all six high-front vowels.

Figure 2. Vowel-specific recognition accuracy of ideal observer in F1-F2 and F1-F2-F3 space. Point ranges indicate the average mean accuracy and average 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals across the five folds. Chance level is indicated by gray line.

Two general observations can be made from Figure 2. First, and perhaps unsurprisingly, some vowels have lower recognition accuracy than others, at least under the simplifying assumption of uniform category priors. Presumably, this is

Figure 3. Confusion matrices for ideal observers trained in F1-F2 space (**Panel A**) and F1-F2-F3 space (**Panel B**). Columns show the intended vowel; rows show the recognized vowel. Probabilities sum to 1 in each column, indicating the distribution of responses for each intended vowel (averaged across the five folds). The difference matrix (**Panel C**) illustrates the differences between the Panels A and B. More **purple** indicates an increase in posterior probability for the former (F1-F3) over the latter (F1-F2) model, more **red** indicates an advantage for the latter over the former.

a consequence of their location in the acoustic-phonetic space relative to neighboring vowels. The more overlap, the lower the accuracy by which vowels are predicted to be recognized. For instance, as suggested by Figure 1, [i:] has many close competitors and partly overlaps all other categories considered, and subsequently has the lowest predicted recognition accuracy. This highlights that the recognition of vowels is dependent on their relative rather than absolute position in the phonetic space (e.g., Peterson & Barney, 1952; Kuhl, 1991; Polka & Bohn, 2003).

Second, the overall improvement in recognition accuracy when including F3 seems to be driven by a subset of the vowels. In particular, the rounded long and short [y:] and [y] seem to benefit the most from the inclusion of F3, while the predicted recognition accuracy of [i:] numerically *decreased* in the F1-F2-F3 model. This was confirmed by fitting separate logistic regression models for each vowel. This revealed significant improvements for [y:], [y], and [ɯ:] (all $ps < .0001$). For [i:], [I] and [e:], recognition accuracy was statistically indistinguishable between the F1-F2 and F1-F2-F3 models (all $ps > .10$).

To better understand *how* the inclusions of F3 improved recognition accuracy, we investigated changes in category confusability.

Category confusability

Figure 3 summarizes the category-to-category confusability for the F1-F2 and F1-F2-F3 model.

Panel A of Figure 3 confirms that the low recognition accuracy of [i:], [I], and [y:] in F1-F2 space is primarily due to confusions with their neighboring categories. Panels B and C show that inclusion of F3 decreases category confusability for most vowels. The increase is particularly noticeable for the rounded long and short [y:] and [y], for which F3 seems to carry helpful information.

Figure 3 further suggests that the numerical decrease in the recognition accuracy of [i:] in the F1-F2-F3 model is primarily driven by the increased probability of confusing [i:] with [y:]: when F3 is included, there is a 21% increase in ideal observer responses for [y:] for when the intended category is [i:] (Figure 3, Panel C). One possible explanation for this is that F3 does *not* add helpful information about this particular contrast, and that additional measurement noise associated

with F3 causes the increased [i:]-[y:] confusability.

As discussed in Persson (2024), the centralization of [i:] and [y:] in the *SwehVd* database might suggest an ongoing merger of the two categories in Central Swedish. This merger might be caused by a relaxation of lip-rounding in the long [y:], or indications of talkers producing the two vowels as damped versions. Either of these two explanations might possibly account for the predicted confusability of the two vowels, and the lack of informativity carried by F3 for the contrast.

Conclusions

We assessed the informativity of F3 for high-front vowel distinctions in Central Swedish using ideal observer models of speech perception. This has allowed us to assess whether—and how—the inclusion of F3 affects the recognition accuracy that can be achieved for the high-front vowels. To ultimately establish the importance of F3-inclusion, however, it will be necessary to assess how well the types of models we evaluated here predict listeners' *actual* vowel perception.

Ideal observers offer a comparatively simple computational model that enables researchers to estimate the consequences of different perceptual systems. The use of these models has become substantially easier with the development of freely available R libraries like the one we used here (MVBELIEFUPDATR), which provides functions for fitting, plotting, and evaluating ideal observers and exemplar models.

Acknowledgements

We thank audiences at the *LMU Institute for Phonetics and Speech Processing* in October 2023, at *FiNo 2024*, and at Department of Swedish language and multilingualism at Stockholm University for feedback on earlier presentations of this work. We are particularly grateful to

Maryann Tan for collaboration in preparation of the *SwehVd* database.

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The Descriptive Approach to Segmental Articulations (DASA): new definitions on acceleration landmarks

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Acoustic segment transitions correspond to the deceleration and acceleration of primary active articulators (Svensson Lundmark 2023). Specifically, for any speech posture of an active articulator we find a deceleration peak at the start of the speech posture and an acceleration peak at the end of the posture, seemingly dividing the slow movements of speech postures from the fast intervals of the movements to and from the postures (Svensson Lundmark and Erickson 2024). However, only the speech postures of the consonantal articulators align directly with the segment transitions (deceleration peaks with segment onset and acceleration peaks with segment offset); the mandible and tongue body movements do not.

In the Descriptive Approach to Segmental Articulations, DASA, the deceleration and acceleration peaks of articulatory movements can be used to describe the coordination of the different articulators in the construction of syllables and speech segments (Svensson Lundmark and Erickson 2024). This talk will report on previous EMA findings on Swedish speakers, while also redefine the DASA approach slightly: segment onset at constriction closure align to the jerk of the deceleration phase, and segment offset at the release with the acceleration peak (Svensson Lundmark 2024).

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Mapping the effect of body position: Voice quality differences in connected speech

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Abstract

This work investigates the effect of body position on voice quality based on cepstral peak prominence (CPP) and spectrum balance (SB) metrics layered on a mapped speech range profile (SRP) across a sound pressure level (SPL) and fundamental frequency (f_0) plane. Eight participants were tested in an upright position, supine position at 0° and an inverted position at -10°. Findings show varied and small changes in voice quality in connected speech between positions and that effects may occur at specific SPL and f_0 ranges among some participants.

Introduction

Body position has a marked impact on speech physiology due to changes in gravitational influence. Previous findings in respiratory kinematics indicate that the respiratory system is susceptible to changes in body position (Hoit, 1995). In an upright position the abdominal muscles are activated to counter the downward pull of the diaphragm and remain active during speech. In a supine position the abdominal muscles are inactive since the abdomen is held in place by gravitational load. This increases the mobility of the abdomen in a supine position, causing a difference in respiratory kinematics compared to an upright position. Additional electromyographic (EMG) findings in quiet breathing research by De Troyer (1983) showed that the upper abdomen was activated among

some participants while placed in an inverted position at -45°, also suggesting a difference in respiratory kinematics between a supine and an inverted position.

The effect of body position on voice quality is less known. An abductive effect on the vocal folds at high lung volumes found in an upright position (Iwarsson et al., 1998) suggests that the voice source is affected by gravity due to tracheal pull. Tracheal pull entails that the lungs are pulled downwards in an upright position, causing a lengthening of the tracheal tube and widening of the glottis. Since tracheal pull occurs when the lungs are pulled in a downwards direction, the abductive effect on the vocal folds is likely to disappear in a supine or inverted position. Furthermore, in a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) study by Traser et al. (2021) the larynx was found to be more cranially displaced during phonation among classically trained singers placed in a supine position, suggesting a loss of tracheal pull.

Speech data is typically procured from participants positioned upright, however, considering that current MRI technology predominantly requires participants to be placed in a supine position, it is possible that results may not be comparable between studies. Ternström and Pabon (2022) presented voice maps as a tool for comparative analysis of the individual voice. Based on synchronously obtained voice- and electroglottographic (EGG) signals mapped across a sound pressure level (SPL) and fundamental frequency (f_0) plane, voice maps can be generated and compared within

the FonaDyn software (Ternström et al., 2018). Each map cell is one semitone wide and one decibel high and contains its own metric averages based on phonatory cycles observed at the corresponding SPL and f_0 . The comparative function of voice maps, proposed as a way for assessing voice disorders before and after treatment, may also be of benefit for analysing voice quality differences between body positions by mapping a speech range profile (SRP).

As part of a master's thesis project by the first author, which aims to investigate the effects of body position on voice quality and respiratory kinematics using a mapped SRP, the present work highlights cepstral peak prominence (CPP) and spectrum balance (SB) findings between an upright position, a supine position at 0° and an inverted position at -10°.

Material and methods

Participants

Eight participants in total were tested. Three men, one non-binary person and four women within the age range of 24 to 35 years. All participants reported no pre-existing health risks that posed a problem with being tested in an inverted position. No compensation was offered.

Environment and equipment

The sessions were held at the Phonetics laboratory at Stockholm University.

A MAXXUS Gravity Pro inversion table modified with an angle chart was used to ensure that the supine and inverted position was comparable between participants. A head-mounted Sennheiser HSP2 microphone was used to record the voice signal and SPL was calibrated with a Galaxy Audio CM C200 calibrator. The EGG signal was acquired using a Glottal Enterprises EG2-PCX2 electroglottograph with two dual-channel electrodes. Additionally, respiratory inductance plethysmography (RIP) was used to record respiratory kinematics

through two transducer bands connected to a RespTrack 2.4 processor (Heldner et al., 2019). The RIP signals were traced in a MORDAX DATA oscilloscope during testing. Calibration and usage of the RespTrack system is described in Heldner et al. (2019) and similar application of acquiring and analysing RIP signals across the same body positions used in the present work is described in Engström (2023). All signals were recorded with the FonaDyn software connected through an Expert Sleepers ES-9 audio interface. EGG and microphone signals were acquired at a 44100 Hz sampling frequency and RIP signals were acquired at a 100 Hz sampling frequency. The speech material consisted of three standard texts in Swedish that were modified to exclude any instances of voiced fricatives since these speech sounds affect the SB metric.

Experimental procedure

Each participant was recorded at separate occasions with one experimenter present (the first author). The participant signed a consent form and provided information about age, gender and past vocal training experience by answering a voluntary information questionnaire. Rib cage circumference, abdominal circumference and height was measured to obtain a body type estimate. Information about height was also necessary for adjustments of the inversion table. The participant was equipped with the microphone, electrodes and transducer bands. One transducer band was placed at axillary height and the other with the umbilicus as reference. To prevent the transducer bands from slipping between positions, the participant's upper garment was taped down onto the trousers. The microphone was SPL calibrated by following *Scenario A* inside the FonaDyn environment and placed at a 30 cm distance from the participant's mouth. The participant was instructed through the calibration process of the transducer bands (See Heldner et al., 2019) and had

an initial vocal warm-up by familiarizing themselves with the speech material.

The body positions were always tested in the same order: The upright position, the supine position at 0° and lastly the inverted position at -10°. The electrode placement indicator on the electroglottograph was used to ensure that the electrodes were at level with the larynx in each position by having the participant phonate [a:]. The recording sequence of each position consisted of calibration of the transducer bands and phonation of an initial [a:] followed by reading aloud the three texts.

Data processing and analysis

A Praat script (Version 6.4.04; Boersma & Weenink, 2024) was used to extract the speech segments from each body position and mapped together with the EGG signal in the FonaDyn software. The voice threshold was set at ≥ 0.9 to exclude overly aperiodic EGG cycles and de-noise was set at 0.02 to filter out interfering EGG noise. Mapping the EGG and voice signal resulted in three csv files containing smoothed SRP maps for each participant: An upright map, a supine map and an inverted map. The maps were filtered to obtain representative values, similarly to Patel and Ternström (2021). In the present work, the cycle threshold for comparative analysis of the SRP maps was set at the median of the total number of cycles per cell. This means that the 50% of the most visited map cells were used for analysis. The lowest median value was used across each comparison. The three comparisons consisted of the upright and supine comparison (U_S), the upright and inverted comparison (U_I) and the supine and inverted comparison (S_I). The comparison of the CPP and SB metrics between positions was obtained by creating a difference map calculated by the formula:

$$\Delta MAP = MAP2 - MAP1 \quad (1)$$

The SB map layer available in FonaDyn measures the difference in acoustic energy above 2000 Hz and below 1500 Hz, corresponding to increased vocal effort when SB is less negative. The CPP map layer indicate less periodicity in the acoustic signal when CPP is decreased, corresponding to increased breathiness.

Only the participants that show a marked change in ΔCPP and ΔSB distributions between positions are included in the results in the present work. Participants that are excluded show ΔCPP and ΔSB distributions that are close to zero between positions.

Results

Figures 1-4 visualize the data distribution of each comparison for selected participants.

Figure 1. ΔCPP distribution of participants P1, P7, P8 in comparisons U_S, U_I, S_I.

Figure 2. ΔCPP distribution of participants P3 and P6 in comparisons U_S, U_I and S_I.

As seen in Figure 1, the ΔCPP distribution in comparisons U_S and U_I show predominantly small positive changes for participants P1, P7 and P8. CPP increased in the supine and the inverted position compared to the upright position. The S_I comparison show a less systematic pattern. The ΔCPP distribution of P1 and P7 is closer to zero,

which indicates less change than P8 where there is a positive change.

In Figure 2, the Δ CPP distribution of participants P3 and P6 in the U_S and U_I comparison show that there is an overall CPP decrease in the supine and inverted positions compared to the upright position. The Δ CPP distribution is centred around zero in the S_I comparison for P3, whereas the Δ CPP distribution of P6 show a positive change from S to I. Participants P3 and P6 also shared similarities in Δ SB distribution, as seen in Figure 3. The U_S comparison show a negative change in the Δ SB distribution for both participants. This indicates that there was less energy at high frequencies in the supine position compared to the upright position.

Among the eight participants, only P8 show a positive change in Δ SB distribution across all comparisons, as seen in Figure 4. This points to more energy at high frequencies in the supine and inverted position compared to the upright

position, as well as in the inverted position compared to the supine position.

Figure 3. Δ SB distribution of participants P3 and P6 in comparisons U_S, U_I and S_I.

Figure 4. Δ SB distribution of participant P8 in comparisons U_S, U_I and S_I.

Figure 5. Filtered SRP maps visualizing similar pattern of Δ CPP in the U_S comparison (top row) and U_I comparison (bottom row) for participants P2, P3, P6 and P5.

Figure 6. Filtered SRP maps visualizing similar pattern of ΔSB in the U_S comparison (top row) and U_I comparison (bottom row) for participants P1, P2, P4 and P3.

Despite less change in ΔCPP and ΔSB distribution between positions, other participants share similar patterns when visualized as filtered SRP difference maps. Figure 5 show overall a pattern of a negative change in ΔCPP at low SPL ranges and a positive change at high SPL ranges for participants P2, P3, P6 and P5 across U_S and U_I comparisons. As seen in Figure 6, there are overall negative changes in ΔSB at the lowest and highest f_0 ranges as well as a positive change in middle f_0 ranges for participants P1, P2, P4, and P3 across U_S and U_I comparisons.

Discussion

This investigation has shown that body position has influence on voice quality among some participants. However, among the participants that showed the most change in ΔCPP and ΔSB distributions included in the results, the changes were not necessarily similar. P3 and P6 showed an increase in breathiness and P8 showed less breathiness across the CPP and SB metrics in the supine and inverted position compared to the upright position. However, shared systematic patterns across SPL and f_0 ranges

were also found among participants P1, P2, P4 and P5 when considering the visual output of the filtered SRP difference maps.

Iwarsson et al. (1998) found an abductive effect on the vocal folds at a high lung volume, however, reading and conversational speech is restricted to the middle lung volume range (Hixon et al., 1973). The present results therefore suggest that the effects of gravity on voice quality also occur at habitual lung volume ranges in speech, reflected as small and varied changes in CPP and SB metrics. However, other unexplored factors may influence these results, such as a potential increase in subglottal pressure caused by the abdominal contents pressing on the chest cavity in a supine and an inverted position.

Additionally, the advantage of using a filtered mapped SRP has been shown in the fact that the similarities observed among the participants when visualized in difference maps across an SPL and f_0 plane would have gone unnoticed if only value distributions had been considered. This indicates that voice mapping could benefit voice quality analyses in speech

and phonation as well as being informative of where effects occur based on SPL and f_0 ranges.

Conclusions

This work has shown that differences in voice quality based on changes in body position can be observed among some participants, possibly indicating that the loss of tracheal pull in a supine and an inverted position may have a small impact on speech compared to an upright position. In addition, that future voice quality investigations may benefit from the usage of voice maps for analyses.

Acknowledgements

We thank all participants for their time and effort.

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Gravity and anti-gravity behaviour in speech production

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Abstract

Even though most speech is produced while standing up or sitting down, we are perfectly capable of speaking while lying down or hanging head-down. The ease with which we accomplish this task obscures the complexity of mechanisms necessary to adapt to the changing effects of gravity in each of these conditions. In the planned future project *The effects of gravity on speech production*, we aim to investigate adjustments to breathing, phonation and articulation when speech is produced across three body positions using a mixture of established instrumental techniques. In this paper, we motivate the project proposal.

Introduction

Humans are capable of producing speech in a wide range of physical conditions—at rest and while jogging, in sound-treated echo-free rooms, reverberant cathedrals, and in noisy nightclubs. We can also speak when standing up, lying down, and, even though as adults we have regrettably few excuses to do so, when hanging upside-down. While speaking in different orientations feels almost effortless, from the point of view of motor control the varying effects of gravity on Earth present a complex problem which involves adjustments to all three major components of speech production, i.e. breathing, phonation and articulation, mediated via proprioceptive feedback.

Effects of gravitation on breathing and phonation

One of the primary functions of the breathing apparatus in speech is generating an egressive air-stream, which is in turn used for the build-up of the pressure below the larynx (i.e. subglottal pressure, P_s) for setting the vocal folds in motion. It has been shown (Konno & Mead, 1967) that the breathing apparatus can be adequately modelled using two degrees of freedom – one for expansion of the rib cage and one for the abdomen. Despite the simplicity of this model, previous research (Hixon, 1973) reported a great interspeaker variation in terms of the relative contributions of the two components, which additionally depend on both lung volume and speech task (McFarland & Smith, 1992).

Gravitational effects on speech breathing are primarily due to the displacement of the abdominal content (Hoit, 1995), which in the upright position is pulled caudally (footward) and exerts an inhalatory force. To prevent the abdominal wall from becoming distended by the resulting hydrostatic pressures, the abdominal muscles are often activated. Additionally, the lungs pull the larynx downwards, particularly when the diaphragm is contracted. This tends to result in lowering of the larynx combined with a reduction of glottal adduction (and thus breathier voice quality) at high lung volumes (Iwarsson & Sundberg, 1998; Iwarsson et al., 1998).

By contrast, in the supine position (lying face upwards) gravity displaces the abdominal content cranially (headward), exerting an exhalatory force and reducing the functional residual capacity of the lungs (Ibañez & Raurich, 1982). This extra load, which is likely to result in undesirably high P_s , is countered by a two-fold compensatory strategy. First, there is a reduced or ceased contraction of the abdominal muscles (De Troyer, 1983). Second, the range of motion of the diaphragm is increased, pushing against the abdominal content and enlarging the chest cavity (Takazakura et al., 2004). Combined, this strategy leads to a predominant contribution of the abdomen to the total lung volume change (Hixon et al., 1976; Sundberg et al., 1991), in contrast to a mixed contribution of the abdomen and the rib cage when standing up.

Since in the supine position the caudal pull on the larynx is reduced or absent, the vertical larynx position is increased (Traser et al., 2014). However, the effect of body position on phonation is not well understood. In a small study of two professional singers performing a series of vocal tasks, Sundberg et al. (1991) found that the participants were able to maintain largely unchanged levels of P_s in the upright and the supine positions. However, it is not known to what extent P_s levels and voice source characteristics are sensitive to changes in body position in untrained participants. Indeed, Traser et al. (2021) demonstrated that professional singers can maintain a mixed strategy involving the diaphragm and the rib cage in both the supine and upright positions, suggesting that they might evolve more complex compensatory strategies.

Little is known about breathing kinematics in the reclined position. De Troyer (1983) collected muscle activity data in participants breathing quietly while tilted head-down at a 45° angle. His results showed increased activity of

the abdominal muscles compared to the supine position. A possible explanation is that similar to the upright position, abdominal muscles are activated to counteract the hydrostatic pressure exerted by the abdominal content being pulled caudally (in the upright position) or cranially (in the reclined position).

Effects of gravitation on articulation

As we know from snoring, gravitation pulls articulatory structures backward in the supine position, which results in a narrowing of the throat (Engström, 2023; Stone et al., 2007; Vorperian et al., 2015). With no compensation, we would therefore expect a more retracted tongue position and reduced lip protrusion in the supine position. In contrast to this prediction, previous studies report mixed, and sometimes contradictory results. For example, Tiede et al. (2000) report x-ray microbeam measurements for two participants, comparing upright and supine positions, noting slightly anterior tongue position in one speaker when supine, while the opposite was found for the other speaker, who had a somewhat more posterior tongue position when supine. Similarly, Kitamura et al. (2005) present MRI data from three speakers of Japanese, which show overall retraction of the tongue root in the supine position, but the magnitude of the difference appeared to vary considerably between participants. One speaker showed virtually no difference between upright and supine positions, one showed consistent tongue root retraction when supine, and one showed retraction in some vowel contexts, and no difference in others.

Stone et al. (2007) propose that such mixed articulatory results may be due to individual differences in the degree of compensation for gravitational forces in different positions, where the primary goal of the compensation is to keep the airway open. In their ultrasound study of 13 speakers, Stone et al. (2007) identify three broad strategies in response to

being in a supine position: 1) no compensation, which produces differences consistent with gravitational effects, e.g. retracted tongue root; 2) sufficient compensation, such that little difference is observed between upright and supine position; 3) overcompensation, which produces ‘anti-gravity postures’, such as relative tongue anteriority in supine position. In general, sufficient compensation appeared to be the most common strategy, consistent with Vorperian et al. (2015). This, however, varied depending on the segment, as also seen in Kitamura et al. (2005).

Interestingly, some systematic group-level differences emerge when comparing two studies by Traser et al. (2013) and Traser et al. (2014). Both were MRI studies of articulatory differences in singing phonation, but Traser et al. (2013) studied classically trained singers, while Traser et al. (2014) studied untrained participants. The professional singers showed minimal-to-no-differences between upright and supine positions, as far as supralaryngeal articulators are concerned, suggesting the presence of compensation. In contrast, the untrained singers showed some differences in tongue position consistent with variable or insufficient compensation. As far as the specific nature of articulatory compensation is concerned, both Traser et al. (2013) and Traser et al. (2014) found that the jaw position may be adjusted to counter the gravitational pull on the tongue in the supine position. More specifically, the jaw was more protruded in the supine position. The combination of this effect with stable supralaryngeal articulation in Traser et al. (2013) is consistent with a pattern of jaw-tongue coordination, in which jaw manipulation is used to adjust the position of the tongue (Johnson et al., 1993).

Overall, previous articulatory research suggests that speakers tend to compensate for the effects of gravity on speech. Similarly, recent results on

astronauts returning from space missions indicate that the gravitational pull on articulatory structures is compensated by anti-gravity behaviour on Earth (Shamei et al., 2023). However, we also know that speakers achieve compensation in a variety of ways, and the nature of this variation is only partially understood. The picture is even less complete when it comes to speech produced in the reclined position (see Figure 1), which to our knowledge, has not been systematically studied using articulatory methods.

Purpose and aims

The first purpose of the present project is thus to investigate the strategies speakers employ under these conditions to produce comprehensible speech.

The observation that we can speak when our speech organs are perturbed in some way, for instance when holding an object between our teeth, is not new. Indeed, studies exploring adaptations of speech production to mechanical constraints have been instrumental in understanding some of the basic principles of speech motor control. However, so far, they have been predominantly restricted to articulatory phenomena. This limitation obscures the synergistic nature of speech production, which involves precise coordination of many anatomical structures. Since gravity is known to perturb breathing, phonation, and articulation, the second purpose of the project is to help overcome the fragmentation of the research field by contributing to a more holistic account of speech production, encompassing all its major components.

In short, we propose to draw on the known effects of gravity on speech production and investigate adaptive patterns across the whole speech production pipeline as body position is changed from upright to supine to reclined. Specifically, the project aims to address the following research questions:

1. What respiratory, phonatory and articulatory strategies are employed by speakers to compensate for the effects of gravity in the upright, supine, and reclined positions?
2. To what extent do these strategies vary across participants?
3. Does manipulating body position result in changes to speech output, such as vowel and voice quality differences?
4. Does vocal training (e.g. in classically trained singers) result in more consistent compensatory patterns?

Method

Human participants will be recorded using established methods for studying speech production: audio recordings, miniature accelerometers attached to speakers' necks, intraoral pressure sensors, electroglottography, ultrasound tongue imaging and respiratory inductance plethysmography.

The speech recorded in the project will consist of isolated syllables, read text and small samples of casual spontaneous speech and will contain no sensitive information. Should data of such character be inadvertently collected, they will be removed from the database in line with the recommendations of The Swedish Ethical Review Authority. None of the tasks involves an increased risk of vocal fatigue. Video recordings will be collected for the purpose of lip and jaw tracking and will only capture a small fragment of the participants' faces containing the lips and the jaw in profile.

The research plan involves collecting speech samples from participants placed in the supine and reclined positions using an inversion table (see Figure 1). Inversion tables are used in spinal traction, a home-based decompression therapy to relieve back pain, muscle spasms, compressed spinal disks and sciatica pain. Due to increased blood pressure in the inverted position, the

method is not recommended for individuals with:

- Diseases of the eyes, (glaucoma, conjunctivitis, high myopia of -6 diopters or more)
- Cardiovascular problems
- Respiratory illness
- Otitis
- Balance problems
- Spinal injuries
- Osteoporosis
- Hypertension
- Thrombosis
- Circulatory disorders
- Pregnancy

In the project, we will only record healthy individuals and we will screen for any of the above exclusion criteria. We will also screen for gastroesophageal reflux disease, which while not an exclusion criterion in itself, might be exacerbated in the reclined position. The inversion table will only be operated by trained research personnel. The gradient and the duration of the speaking tasks will be adjusted in order to avoid participant fatigue in the reclined position. Participants will also be allowed to take breaks (as well as to terminate the experiment) at any point. Due to the physical intervention involved, as well as the processing of health data in the screening process, we will apply for a permit from The Swedish Ethical Review Authority before the research starts. The remaining data collection methods carry no significant risks for the participants. Similarly, the research is not associated with any long-term risks.

Overall, with proper screening, we assess the risks for participants to be low and to be fully justified by the research goals. Gravity offers a unique opportunity to study compensatory strategies which affect the whole speech production mechanism, a holistic perspective which is routinely overlooked in existing literature.

Figure 1. First author in reclined position on an inversion table.

Discussion

By providing a more comprehensive account of physiological constraints in speech, the project will contribute to overcoming the fragmentation of the research field, which overwhelmingly focuses on individual components of speech production and loses track of its coordinative nature. In addition to its theoretical contributions, the project will develop protocols for collecting speech data encompassing breathing, phonation and articulation. It will also inform vocal pedagogy, for instance with respect to optimal strategies when vocal performances involve body position other than upright. The project will be carried out over three years by an international group of researchers with expertise in the different aspects of speech production and instrumental techniques.

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A phonetician's reading of Darwin's notes on the vocal

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Abstract

Sexual dimorphism has played a key role in research on vocal attractiveness. This paper looks at Darwin's *The Descent of Man and Selection in Relation to Sex* (1871[2021]) with the following questions in mind: 1) What role does the vocal have according to Darwin?; 2) What reasons are provided for any tendencies identified by Darwin?; and 3) Have these (in humans) been supported by research conducted since? Darwin consistently acknowledges the role of the voice in sexual selection. Specific details are discussed in the paper, which further compares these with more recent research on vocal attractiveness and suggests further avenues of research from a phonetician's perspective.

Introduction

The field of vocal attractiveness (VA) has established the role of several vocal traits which contribute to the listener's percept of the speaker's physical, and in some cases romantic, attractiveness (Weiss, Trouvain, Barkat-Defradas, & Ohala, 2021). Because much of this research, either explicitly or implicitly, focuses on sexual attractiveness, it is perhaps not surprising that much of the research on VA has been conducted in the fields of evolutionary biology and psychology, and only considerably more recently also in linguistics. Sexual selection (Darwin, 1859) thus necessarily recurs in the literature focusing on VA.

In this paper, the following questions are asked: 1) What role does the vocal have according to Darwin?; 2) What reasons are provided for any tendencies identified by Darwin?; and 3) Have these been supported by research

conducted since? Because Darwin's notes on the vocal may seem rather "scattered" throughout (some of) his works, one of the primary goals of this paper is to provide a more practical overview of Darwin's notes on the vocal (RQ1-2). However, discussing RQ3 facilitates a second primary goal of this paper, namely to outline areas in the field of VA which remain somewhat of a terra incognita and which should be explored in future research on VA. This discussion is written from a linguistic perspective as well, which has been less represented in the highly interdisciplinary area of VA. This paper therefore ultimately also attempts to bring linguistics and biology and psychology closer together in a mutual endeavour.

Sexual selection and natural selection

According to Darwin (1871[2021]), "sexual selection [...] depends on the advantage which certain individuals have over others of the same sex and species solely in respect of reproduction". When contrasted with natural selection, "[s]exual selection acts in a less rigorous manner [...]. [Natural selection] produces its effects by the life or death at all ages of the more or less successful individuals" (1871[2021]).

If we take f_0 as an example to illustrate the two types of mechanisms, we could paint the following picture. Firstly, lower f_0 is strongly indicative of a larger body size (Ohala, 2010) and also correlates with strength (Puts, Apicella, & Cárdenas, 2012) and the individual's survival chances. An individual can lower one's f_0 on purpose in order to (attempt to) exert and/or signal dominance. A lower f_0 may also increase one's

chances to propagate the species. For instance, if f_0 correlates with more physical size and strength and prowess, and if these are desired characteristics, then f_0 would also signal to the listener which vocalisers/speakers are more desirable to mate with and/or more likely to overpower a mate.

Method

Two books were chosen for the analysis: *On the Origin of Species* (1859) and *The Descent of Man and Selection in Relation to Sex* (1871). The two works have been chosen of Darwin's several works as these have been the most influential in terms of the theories of natural selection and sexual selection. However, due to limited space and because the former provides few comments on the vocal, only the latter is discussed here.

Results

The Descent of Man and Selection in Relation to Sex is rife with comments on the vocal and (in humans) the linguistic, with the table of contents giving them a more prominent place by their explicit mention, as in “musical instruments of the males” in the chapter on secondary sexual characters of insects; “vocal organs” in the chapter on secondary sexual characters of fishes, amphibians, and reptiles, and those of birds (but not mammals). The chapter on the secondary sexual characters of humans (“man”) also explicitly mentions “differences in mental powers, and voice”. Overall, Darwin's commentaries on the vocal (and the linguistic) fall within the following types: speech impediments and communication disorders, racial aspects of the vocal, evolutionary and historical development of language(s), aesthetic aspects of the vocal, the vocal in fights and combats, and finally the vocal as a “charm” (i.e. a VA trait). As we will see, sex enters in the discussion of most of these and some of the discussion is coloured by racial and gender stereotypes in places.

“Arrests of development”

Darwin mentions the possibility of cleft palate being inherited to provide an example of “[v]arious monstrosities”. He does not link this directly to speech. An explicit comment on speech is connected to the cognitive faculties, with some “arrests of growth” affecting the development of the brain in ways which can result in the inability to “acquire the power of speech”. The most explicit comment concerns “some hemiplegic patients and others”, who, “at the commencement of inflammatory softening of the brain, unconsciously imitate every word which is uttered, whether in their own or in a foreign language, and every gesture or action which is performed near them”.

Evolutionary and historical development of language(s)

Darwin makes several observations on the development of the linguistic faculty. A whole chapter is dedicated to “Mental faculty”, which contains a section on “Language”, but discussions of the linguistic faculty appear in various places. In particular, Darwin suggests that the development of the linguistic faculty went hand in hand with the development of overall mental capacities. Indeed, to him the discovery of fire is “probably the greatest ever made [...] excepting language”.

Darwin speculates that vocalisations were used before language evolved, which were emphasised particularly through sexual selection (during the “season of courtship”), and language developed from these. However, Darwin acknowledges the use of non-linguistic vocalisations as an important part of human communication today: “Our cries of pain, fear, surprise, anger, together with their appropriate actions, and the murmur of a mother to her beloved child are more expressive than any words.” While some of Darwin's notes on the linguistic faculty seem shrouded in a mist of admiration for humankind (or “man”), he is at

the same time well aware of the fact that human beings are also very physical beings: “Although the intellectual powers and social habits of man are of paramount importance to him, we must not underrate the importance of his bodily structure”; and “Man still bears in his bodily frame the indelible stamp of his lowly origin”.

Darwin also explicitly discusses “difference(s) in the mental powers of the two sexes” in humans. More specifically, “[w]oman seems to differ from man in mental disposition, chiefly in her greater tenderness and less selfishness”. Darwin further notes that the intellectual powers are higher in men than women, because “[i]f two lists were made of the most eminent men and women in poetry, painting, sculpture, music (inclusive both of composition and performance), history, science, and philosophy, with half-a-dozen names under each subject, the two lists would not bear comparison [...] the average of mental power in man must be above that of woman. [...] Thus, man has ultimately become superior to woman.” These represent some of the (from today’s point of view) most glaring gender stereotypes in the work.

Racial aspects of the vocal

It is not only gender stereotypes which can be seen in some of Darwin’s work in places. One commentary reflects racially stereotypical aspects of communication: “the light-hearted, talkative negroes” are contrasted with “taciturn, even morose, aborigines of S. America”. Darwin also claims that “the voice and the form of the larynx differ in the different races of mankind; but with the Tartars, Chinese, etc., the voice of the male is said not to differ so much from that of the female, as in most other races.”

Aesthetic aspects of the vocal

Numerous notes can be found on aesthetic aspects of the vocal, especially regarding “instrumental music” as opposed to speech, although Darwin makes

subjective comments on the aesthetic of the vocal in speech as well.

Many of these notes are explicitly linked to sexual selection (e.g. “The sweet strains poured forth by many male birds during the season of love, are certainly admired by the females.”). The groups of animals for which Darwin makes such observations include (many) birds, crickets, fish, frogs, grasshoppers, and humans. In one of the four chapters on birds, an entire section is dedicated to “instrumental music”.

What seems to motivate Darwin’s decisions behind which vocalisations are “instrumental music” is 1) whether the vocaliser can give “a complete and correct octave of musical notes” (as in the case of the gibbon); 2) whether the sounds are perceived as smooth or symmetrical, and/or 3) pleasing to humans. On the one hand, Darwin points out that a range of species derive pleasure from “instrumental music” in some way, which suggests more universal tendencies. On the other hand, the role of culture is also explicitly acknowledged: “but such high tastes [i.e. human preferences for art] are acquired through culture, and depend on complex associations for landscapes and refined music”.

The aesthetic is also explicitly linked to the sexual in several places: “The true song, however, of most birds and various strange cries are chiefly uttered during the breeding-season, and serve as a charm, or merely as a call-note, to the other sex.”

The vocal (and acoustic) as a charm

Many males are discussed in using their voices and other sounds to appeal to the female during the “breeding-season” or as part of “courtship”. Darwin mentions beetles, birds, cicadas, crickets, crustaceans, fishes, frogs, gibbons, grasshoppers, humans (“man”), monkeys, seals, snakes, spiders, and tortoises. The voice and body sounds are therefore very explicitly and consistently identified as a secondary sexual trait of most species

discussed by Darwin. In the case of the cicada, as is the case for other species, Darwin notes that it is only the male that utilises the voice, and accompanies this with a misogynist quote from the poet Xenarchus: “Happy the Cicadas live, since they all have voiceless wives.”

Darwin attributes this to the fact that “the male of almost all animals [has] stronger passions than the females. Hence, it is the males that fight together and sedulously display their charms before the females”. While Darwin also identifies the male as more active than the female, he also comments on the fact that the female could be seen as active in exerting a choice. He also makes an interesting comment on the fact that she does not necessarily choose “the male which is the most attractive to her, but the one which is the least distasteful”. It is somewhat curious that, when it comes to deer, while the stag is claimed not to use the voice to “charm”, “[t]he voice of the female, on the other hand, quickly brings to her one or more stags”. Although this note implies that the *female* voice is utilised in sexual selection, Darwin nevertheless concludes that the stag does not use the voice for sexual selection purposes, even though the implication is, at the same time, that they must pay attention as *listeners* at least. At one point, Darwin admits that not only males but also females might compete with other males and females, respectively, and that not only males but also females might utilise the vocal as a “charm”: “[w]omen are generally thought to possess sweeter voices than men, and as far as this serves any guide, we may infer that they first acquired musical powers in order to attract the other sex. [...] But if so, this must have occurred long ago, before our ancestors had become sufficiently human to treat and value their women merely as useful slaves.” Darwin frames this within a contemporary parallel with “utterly barbarous tribes[, where] the women have more power in

choosing, rejecting, and tempting their lovers, or afterwards changing their husbands.” Thus, although the focus of VA traits is repeatedly on the male as a producer and the female as the perceiver, Darwin nevertheless speculates (and in some places strongly implies) that female voices, too, can serve as a “charm”.

AGEING. A slightly different aspect linked to female vocalisations is touched upon with respect to ageing, with an example of ageing hens. A female within the same species can adopt the “male” characteristics, including the voice, especially as she ages. Although this is not discussed as female “charms” being lost, this is ultimately what this relates to.

SYMMETRY. In his notes on the aesthetic, symmetry is discussed as a result of sexual selection. However, this does not seem to apply to the male sea-elephant’s nose and its “gurgling” sounds.

HUMANS (MALES, BUT ALSO FEMALES). A considerable amount of space is dedicated to the vocal in sexual selection particularly with respect to birds and (less so) humans. For humans, the male voice is described as having a “more powerful tone” than the female voice. This “great difference between the adult sexes” lies “in the power of [male] voices”, which is due to male vocal folds being larger than female ones. According to Darwin, the reason is “the long-continued use of the vocal organs by the male under the excitement of love, rage and jealousy”. Finally, with respect to humans, Darwin clearly identifies language as a complex and a more evolved form of expressing and communicating love and desire: “before acquiring the power of expressing their mutual love in articulate language, [they] endeavoured to charm each other with musical notes and rhythm”; and “[h]e [i.e. ‘man’, i.e. the human] differs also from the lower animals in the power of expressing his desires by words, which thus become a guide to the aid required and bestowed.”

VOCAL VS NON-VOCAL TRAITS. Although the vocal is, across the different species discussed by Darwin, positioned as less important than other secondary sexual characteristics, Darwin explicitly comments on one scenario in which this may not be the case: “if bright colours were dangerous to the species, other means would be employed to charm the females; and melody of voice offers one such means.” However, even though the vocal is framed as less important than non-vocal traits in the work, Darwin consistently positions it as widely relevant and important in the evolution of many species: “[f]rom the curiously diversified means for producing various sounds, we gain a high idea of the importance of this means of courtship.”; and “To suppose that the females do not appreciate the beauty of the males, is to admit that their splendid decorations, all their pomp and display, are useless; and this is incredible.”

INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS OF THE VOCAL. While few, some notes also comment on the interactive elements of the vocal of sexual selection, and how different phases of an encounter affect vocalisations. For instance, the male crickets and grasshoppers are described to stridulate in “louder notes” when attracting females to their burrow, and then utilising “a more subdued tone, whilst the successful musician caresses with his antennae the mate he has won”. A more complex example is also provided for the eared seal, in which we find a combination of the use of the vocal both to attract and then subdue and dominate in the process of sexual selection, with the female first being lured with low-intensity vocalisations, and then intimidated and held captive in the male seal’s harem.

The role of the vocal in fights

As already mentions, Darwin links “instrumental music” also to competitiveness within the same sex of a species. The first scenario falling within this

category is one in which a male or a group of males, for instance, intend to intimidate each other (e.g. baboons, birds, cicadas, gibbons, and monkeys).

Discussion and conclusion

RQ1: What role does the vocal have?

The vocal is consistently acknowledged by Darwin in his *Descent of Man*, particularly with respect to sexual selection. This is commented on fairly systematically for a wider range of species. Although more focus is given to birds and humans, this is nevertheless the case for other sexual characteristics as well. Darwin mainly mentions volume and power with respect to different sexes with respect to humans. Darwin’s comments on humans differ from those on other animals also in that humans express their desires through language, i.e. not solely or primarily through vocalisations, although vocalisations are still seen as very important.

RQ2: What reasons are provided?

VA is indeed one aspect of the vocal discussed most consistently across numerous species covered by Darwin. For humans at least, some of the assumptions put forward reflect gendered (and racial) deterministic and essentialist ideologies. At the same time, these are not adhered to consistently throughout the work, and both culture and biology are seen as important and interrelated.

RQ3: Have these been supported since?

Limiting the (considerably succinct) answer to this question solely to the human vocal, research has repeatedly shown that lower-pitched voices are associated not only with larger body size but also with higher percepts of dominance and aggression, and this is the case across different cultures (Puts, Apicella, & Cárdenas, 2012). However, while Darwin associates this deterministically with the two sexes, recent research provides us with more nuanced approaches to gender

and power and includes evaluations of both male but also female voices with respect to perceived dominance (e.g. Krahé, & Papakonstantinou, 2019; Pisanski, & Rendall, 2011; Tusing, & Dillard, 2006).

One note focuses on the symmetrical being aesthetically pleasing. Much research has been conducted which engages with the idea that “smooth” voices are evaluated as more attractive and good, which translates into periodic, harmonically rich voices. Discussions are ongoing regarding the role of symmetry vis-à-vis typicality in terms of exposure frequency and averageness (Pisanski & Feinberg, 2018).

Considering racial differences in the vocal, most sociophonetic work would struggle relating its findings to Darwin’s assumptions. Firstly, it has been acknowledged that both ethnicity and race (similarly to gender and sex) are discursively constructed. Secondly, Darwin does not specify *how exactly* strictly *vocal* (rather than communicative) characteristics of different races are supposed to vary. Different physiology of the larynx is mentioned, but not commented on. 21-century research has targeted racial differences in the vocal tract as a whole (e.g. Hao, 2002).

Areas to pursue

A sociophonetician would propose that future research on VA considers the role of gender and age identity, and gender and age norms of specific speech communities. Secondly, vocal traits of *romantic* attractiveness seem to be much less understood. Furthermore, the focus in VA research has been predominantly on heterosexual speakers/listeners. I also suggest that a plethora of interesting information lies in public discourses about “sexy voices” (and variably labelled un/attractive voices) as well as in media representations. Phonetic research has established much nuance in specific phonatory and other vocal aspects of speech production, which could be

approached in a more nuanced manner in future work as well. Finally, the phonatory typology of specific languages used in VA studies should be acknowledged, as it is not known to what extent these may constrain the availability of specific vocal traits as VA cues, especially in interactional settings.

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Does purring “ronron” in the family? A longitudinal and intra-family study of purring in a female cheetah as a cub and as an adult and purring in her father as an adult and brother as a cub

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Abstract

In 2009 the author initiated his “zoonetics” activities by recording purring in the male cheetah Caine as well as in the domestic cat Misha and presented the results at the Fonetik Meeting in 2010 at Lund University. Subsequent studies of cheetah purring then followed, including a study of purring in Caine’s daughter Jade and son Parker in 2013, Jade at the time 7 months old. In May 2019 the author recorded Jade again (now 7 years old) and was then able to study whether any changes in her purring had occurred and, specifically, whether Jade as an adult had kept her cub characteristics or was now more similar to her father, who was 7 years old when he was recorded. To the best of my knowledge this study presents the first longitudinal study of purring in a cheetah.

Introduction

In 2010 Eklund, Peters and Duthie (2010) compared purring in the cheetah and the domestic cat, based on recordings made of the male cheetah Caine in South Africa and the domestic cat Misha (recorded in Sweden).

In 2013 Caine’s daughter Jade (pronounced [ˈdʒeɪdɪ]), then 7 months old, was recorded alongside her brother Parker (11 months old) and a few other cheetahs and the analyses were presented in Eklund and Peters (2013).

In May 2019 the author had the opportunity to record Jade, now 7 years old, again which made it possible to

study longitudinal development in Jade’s purring and also see whether she, now being the same age as her father Caine was in the 2010 study, more resembled her father or whether she has retained the characteristics of her purring as a cub.

To the best of this author’s knowledge the present study provides the first longitudinal study of purring in a cheetah.

The cheetah

The cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus*) is probably best known for being the fastest land animal in the world with an estimated top speed of circa 112 km/h (Sunquist & Sunquist, 2002:23).

A widespread misconception is that the cheetah “is not a cat”, it is a full-fledged felid, most closely related to the puma (*Puma concolor*) and the jaguarundi (*P. yaguarondi*) (O’Brien & Johnson, 2007:70).

The cheetah is of roughly the same size as the leopard (*Panthera pardus*) – with which it is often confused but is of a lighter and more slender build, has a smaller head and smaller teeth. The cheetah is distinguished by dark tear-marks in the facial fur running down its eyes, towards the muzzle.

Purring

The term ‘purring’ has been used liberally in the mammal vocalization literature, and an exhaustive review is given in Peters (2002). Using a definition of purring that *continuous*

sound production must alternate between pulmonic egressive and ingressive airstream (and usually go on for minutes), Peters (2002) reached the conclusion that only “purring cats” (Felidae) and two species of genets (Viverridae *sensu stricto*), *Genetta tigrina*, and likely also *G. genetta*, had been documented to purr. For further discussion see Eklund, Peters and Duthie (2010).

Data collection and processing

Data were collected at the Dell Cheetah Centre, in Parys, South Africa, on 12 May 2019. Jade, at the time around 7 years old, was recorded in her enclosure by the author and Estelle Kemp. Jade, who was not at all an approachable “people cheetah” – normally only Estelle Kemp was able to approach Jade – was exceptionally friendly and even (to everyone’s great surprise) approached the author in a friendly manner and allowed herself to be petted by the authors, which also made it possible to obtain high-quality data.

Film captures of the data collection are shown in Plates 1 and 2.

Equipment

The equipment used was a handheld Canon HG-10 HD camcorder. A wide-angle lens was also used to enable filming closer to the cheetah while still capturing the entire scene.

Sound was recorded with an external professional high-fidelity Audiotechnica AT813 cardoid-pattern, condenser mono microphone (the same used to record Caine in 2009). The position of the microphone varied, partly due to Jade moving (albeit slightly), but was mostly directed towards the muzzle

of the cheetahs, where the sound emanates (see e.g., Eklund, Peters & Duthie, 2010).

Data post-processing

Audio tracks were excerpted from the films with TMPGENC 4.0 Xpress. Working audio format was 44.1 kHz, 16 bit, mono.

Analysis tools

The sound files were analyzed with Cool Edit 2000 and cycles per phase were counted manually from the waveform. Statistics were calculated with SPSS 12.0.1.

Analyses

Identification of egressive and ingressive phases

For most of the data, egressive and ingressive phases were identified according to the method described in Eklund, Peters and Duthie (2010), i.e. with the author keeping his hand on the side of the chest of the cheetah to monitor breathing, while uttering the words “in” and “out” in synchronization with the cheetah’s breathing and purring.

Egressive and ingressive phases were identified by the first author by a combination of visual inspection of the waveform and sound characteristics, based on the very distinctive sound quality and amplitude differences between egressive and ingressive purring.

It proved very easy to identify both ingressive and egressive phases from both a waveform and sound quality perspective; a sample is shown on Plate 3. Note the “two-stroke” characteristics of both egressive and ingressive phases.

Plates 1 and 2. Video captures from the recording session. Estelle Kemp (left) and Robert Eklund (right) taking turns in holding the microphone and the camera, respectively. Note the author’s hand on Jade’s back to make sure the identifications of egressive/ingressive phases were correct. The recording session took place in Jade’s enclosure.

Plate 3. **Waveform example** showing egressive and ingressive phases (Cool Edit 2000 screenshot). Note the “two-stroke” characteristics of both phases which is much clearer in the ingressive phases, thus making identification much more straightforward for ingressive phases than for egressive phases.

Table 1. **Summary results.** For all four cheetahs results are given for duration, cycles per phase and fundamental frequency. Egressive and ingressive phases are given both separately and combined. Caine and Parker also 2013 data.

	Caine (M)		Parker (M)		Jade (F) 2013		Jade (F) 2019	
Age	7 years		11 months		7 months		7 years	
Weight (kilos)	> 70		25		18–20		~42	
Phonation type	Ingr	Egr	Ingr	Egr	Ingr	Egr	Ingr	Egr
No. phases analysed	38	38	21	21	24	25	25	22
Mean duration (ms)	2174	2438	1003	970	685	590	1816	1428
Mean duration egr+ingr (ms)	2306		986		637		1634	
Standard deviation	385.5	534.5	413.6	406.6	376.1	243.3	130.5	298.5
Maximal duration	3300	3640	1700	1710	2100	2100	1972	1790
Minimal duration	1280	1200	100	280	300	160	1816	1428
Δt test (paired-samples, two-tailed)	$p = 0.014$		$p = 0.074$		$p = 0.168$		$p < 0.001$	
Δ Wilcoxon (two related samples)	$p = 0.018$		$p = 0.068$		$p = 0.094$		$p < 0.001$	
Mean no. cycles/phase	49.3	49.1	20.3	21.5	19.3	18.4	35.0	30.1
Mean no. cycles/phase egr+ingr	49.2		20.9		18.9		32.8	
Standard deviation	10.5	12.1	6.7	9.1	11.8	7.4	2.6	5.7
Maximal no. phases/cycle	69	77	35	38	67	34	38	43
Minimal no. cycles/phase	24	23	7	3	10	8	29	18
Δt test (paired-samples, two-tailed)	$p = 0.921$		$p = 0.562$		$p = 0.576$		$p = 0.004$	
Δ Wilcoxon (two related samples)	$p = 0.959$		$p = 0.456$		$p = 0.471$		$p = 0.009$	
Mean fundamental frequency (Hz)	22.6	20.1	19.6	22.7	28.3	30.8	19.3	21.0
Mean frequency egr+ingr (Hz)	21.3		21.1		29.6		20.1	
Standard deviation	2.25	2.25	2.38	1.58	4.45	7.26	0.36	1.85
Highest fundamental frequency	25.7	21.9	23.4	25.7	37.5	49.0	20.1	24.8
Lowest fundamental frequency	18.7	11.2	16.4	20.0	22.5	24.1	18.4	17.8
Δt test (paired-samples, two-tailed)	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$		$p = 0.072$		$p < 0.001$	
Δ Wilcoxon (two related samples)	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$		$p = 0.113$		$p = 0.001$	

Table 2. **Duration values** for egressive and ingressive phases combined (i.e. entire purring phases); *t* test for independent samples, two-tailed, equal variances assumed. Jade 2013/Jade 2019 are considered independent.

	Jade 2013	Jade 2019	Caine	Parker
Jade 2013		$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$
Jade 2019	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$
Caine	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$
Parker	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	

Table 3. **Cycles per phase** for egressive and ingressive phases combined (i.e. entire purring phases); *t* test for independent samples, two-tailed, equal variances assumed. Jade 2013/Jade 2019 are considered independent.

	Jade 2013	Jade 2019	Caine	Parker
Jade 2013		$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$
Jade 2019	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$
Caine	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$		$p < 0.001$
Parker	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	

Table 4. **Hz values** for egressive and ingressive phases combined (i.e. entire purring phases); *t* test for independent samples, two-tailed, equal variances assumed. Jade 2013/Jade 2019 are considered independent.

	Jade 2013	Jade 2019	Caine	Parker
Jade 2013		$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$	$p < 0.001$
Jade 2019	$p < 0.001$		$p = 0.099$	$p = 0.060$
Caine	$p < 0.001$	$p = 0.099$		$p = 0.002$
Parker	$p < 0.001$	$p = 0.060$	$p = 0.002$	

Results

Summary results are shown in Table 1.

Amplitude

Previous studies, of both cheetahs (e.g. Eklund & Peters, 2013; Eklund, Peters & Duthie; 2010) and domestic cats (e.g. Eklund, Peters & Duthie; 2010; Peters, 1981; Moelk, 1944) have reported both egressive and ingressive phases being louder which suggest a substantial individual variation at play. In the present study, however, ingressive phases were clearly and consistently louder than egressive phases.

Although no absolute amplitude figures can be given here since no sound level meter was used during the recording, a marked relative amplitude difference was observed in that

ingressive phases on average were 6–8 dB louder than egressive phases. This difference is clearly seen in Plate 3.

Phase durations

Comparing phase durations produced when Jade was 7 months old and when she was 7 years old the first obvious difference observed is that the duration for both egressive and ingressive phases had increased with a factor of around 2.5. However, phase durations were still not as long as they were in Caine, who was a considerably larger and heavier cheetah.

Cycles per phase

The number of cycles per phase in Jade’s purring had increased with around 1.7 since Jade was 7 months old but, as was the case for durations, the number of

cycles per phase was still much lower than for Caine number of cycles per phase was still much lower than for Caine.

Fundamental frequency

Comparing 2013 data and 2019 data Jade's fundamental frequency had decreased from 29.6 Hz to 20.1 Hz, the latter being even lower her than Caine's 21.3 Hz. The observed difference between the 2013 and 2019 recordings amount to 6 semitones (i.e. noticeable to a human ear) what is of interest here is perhaps not primarily human perception but rather the physiological changes have taken place in a cheetah growing into adulthood, and that may affect purring production.

Intra-family comparisons

In addition to individual characteristics shown in Tables 2–4, a number of one-way ANOVAs were also performed on the data sets.

For **duration** values ANOVAs were all significant at $p < 0.001$.

As for **cycles per phase** all ANOVAs were also significant $p < 0.001$ with the sole exception of Jade 2013 vs Parker where a Tukey post hoc test returned $p = 0.760$.

ANOVAS for **frequency** were significant at $p < 0.001$ for all pairs except for Tukey post hoc tests for Jade 2019 and Caine ($p = 0.994$), Jade 2019 and Parker ($p = 0.588$) and Caine/Parker ($p = 0.462$).

In short, the ANOVAs mainly confirm the general impression of the pair-wise t tests shown in Tables 2–4.

Conclusions

An immediate to be drawn is that almost all comparisons made are highly significant. Given the data set of only three individuals (whereof one at two ages) and three test parameters this is clearly not enough data to allow far-reaching conclusion but given that all the cheetahs are closely related and that

so much difference are observed within the same family this strongly suggests that purring is a varied phenomenon, both physiologically and acoustically.

The only non-significant results all show up in the frequency domain, which perhaps is not surprising given the consistently low frequency, even across species (see Eklund, Peters & Duthie, 2010), at which purring occurs.

From the main perspective of the present paper, whether or not Jade's purring had changed between 7 months and 7 years old, the most interesting changes occurred in the frequency domain in that Jade had, in fact, become more like her father, and indeed in 2019 even purred at a lower frequency than her (very big) father. But again, it must be remembered that her brother Parker also purred at a very low frequency when he was a cub, and that even comparatively very small domestic cats, too, exhibit purring at very low frequencies (Schötz & Eklund, 2011). This, of course, means that purring frequency per se it not a reliable indicator of size and/or weight.

Summing up, purring seems to changes with age.

Notes

This paper was originally planned for the 2020 Fonetik meeting, for the tenth anniversary of the domestic can/cheetah purring paper. Covid (and other reasons) made this not happen until now and thus the paper now appears a few years late – although it's still intended as an “anniversary” publication.

A YouTube clip of the Jade 2019 recording is found here:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ACxi8vbwYKw&ab_channel=DrJubatus

A YouTube clip of the Caine 2009 recording is found here:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZFvULxbN3NM&ab_channel=DrJubatus

Finally, “ronronner” is French for purring (of course!).

Acknowledgements

My warmest thanks to and deepest respect for **Estelle, Pieter** and **Charl Kemp** for their devoted work to try to prevent that the cheetah becomes yet another TEXT

Thanks to **Åsa Wengelin** for some last-minute statistics advice and soundboarding. You're a rock!

Thanks to **Per Näsman** for valuable advice on statistics. Always appreciated!

The author would like to thank **myself** for making all old data files available.

A personal thanks is extended to **Jade** (she has sadly passed; the life expectancy of cheetahs is around ten years), who was *not* an approachable cat and the author was even a little wary of entering the enclosure and would not have done it without Estelle Kemp being there, the only person Jade accepted. To everyone's big surprise Jade suddenly stood up from her position on Estelle's lap and went straight for the author and started to rub herself against the author, friendly purring (which can be seen and heard on the YouTube clip). Needless to say, the author regards this as one of the pinnacle and most moving events in his career or even life! *Thanks, Jade!*

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The production and perception of phrase prominence in pre-schoolers from Stockholm and Scania

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Abstract

The use of phrase-level prosodic prominence (PLP) relations for the encoding of information structure (IS) is mastered fairly late in children's language development according to previous research (e.g., MacWhinney & Bates, 1978; de Ruiter, 2010). However, few studies have investigated children's production of PLP in relation to how they perceive and comprehend PLP in the context of IS encoding and decoding (Chen, 2010); earlier studies involving perception have made use of offline paradigms (e.g., Wells et al., 2004), while more recent studies using online methods such as eye tracking have usually not been complemented by production data (e.g., Ito, 2014). In addition, previous production work has indicated that language-specific intonational-phonological properties of PLP might play a role, too (e.g., Romøren & Chen, 2015, 2021; Prieto & Esteve-Gibert, 2018). In this study we explore the production and perception of PLP as used to mark contrastive focus in 3–5-year-old children speaking either Scanian or Stockholm Swedish, two dialects which differ crucially in the way PLP is realized phonetically. While both dialects exhibit a lexical accent contrast, PLP is realized more subtle in the Scanian variety: instead of adding a prominence H(igh)-tone, PLP is encoded through phonetic adjustments of the H(igh)L(ow) accent patterns determined by the lexical accent. Our production experiment involves eliciting adjective-noun phrases displaying different PLP relations (e.g., 'a red BOAT' vs. 'a RED boat'), using an interactive video/card game. Production data are analysed acoustically and auditorily. In our visual-word eye-tracking experiment we use the same pictures of coloured objects to investigate whether children make use of PLP relations in the audio stimuli for reference resolution. Preliminary results suggest that 5-year-olds from Stockholm display a perception behaviour like adults; in 3–4-year-olds, this pattern is emerging. For Scanian children (3–5 years), we cannot observe any sensitivity for PLP yet.

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Assessing Children's Pronunciation of Nordic Languages

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Abstract

We report on a number of corpora of Nordic languages spoken by children that we collected during the Teflon project. We focused on two speaker groups: non-native children learning a Nordic language (L2) and L1 children with speech sound disorder (SSD).

This abstract is a summary of the paper recently presented in Olstad et al. (2024). There, we report on the experience collecting a number of corpora aimed at creating automatic pronunciation assessment for children speaking selected Nordic languages. The goal was to develop a game to assist pronunciation training for two target groups: foreign children learning a second language (L2) and native children with speech sound disorder (SSD).

Although corpora suitable for research on child speech recognition exist for several languages (Eskenazi et al., 1997; Khaldoun et al. 1997; Pradhan and Ward, 2021; Cucchiarini and Smits, 2008; Yu et al., 2021) those do not include recordings of L2 learners or children with SSD. L2 corpora are much rarer (Zhang et al., 2021; Vidal et al., 2019; Sudhakar et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2020) and only contain limited recordings of children. Finally, there are to the authors' knowledge no corpora that address non-standard or L2 pronunciation of Nordic languages for child speakers.

The Teflon project collected three corpora with L2 recordings of foreign children learning Norwegian, Finnish and Swedish, and two corpora with native Swedish children with SSD. We also describe some preliminary results in developing automatic pronunciation assessment in this particular domain. The full details can be found in Olstad et al. (2024).

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Analysis of text-reading speech produced by Japanese primary school children (age 6-12): Focus on Topic-Comment structure

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Abstract

This paper presents a cross-sectional analysis of text (story)-reading speech produced by Japanese primary school children adopting the CIAIR Children's Voice Speech Corpus, comprising 253 children across six grades. A high percentage of pause insertion after the topic marker *wa* indicates that the Topic-Comment structure is well-comprehended and phonetically marked by Japanese primary school children. The peak relation of fundamental frequency (F0) between the domain of Topic (T) and Comment (C) shows the T>C pattern as dominant with a gradually increasing pitch range difference. The opposite pattern T<C also increases, indicating the upcoming of the focal prosody, which is typically associated with storytelling style.

Introduction

Age-dependent characteristics of speech are essential for efficient speech communication. This paper presents a cross-sectional analysis of text (story) reading speech produced by Japanese primary school children (age 6-12) focusing on the manifestation of the Topic-Comment structure.

Prosodic correlates of information structure have received much attention in past decades. Kügler & Calhoun (2020) present an overview and typology of prosodic correlates for information structure defined as focus, givenness, and topicality across languages. The role played by prosody is most evident in languages like English

and other Germanic languages lacking grammatical markers to indicate information structure. Conversely, there are languages with rich morphosyntactic means of expressing information structure, which often leads to little or no contribution of prosody. It is unclear where Japanese fits in the typology as it is not included in Kügler & Calhoun's overview.

Topic-Comment structure in Japanese

The Topic-Comment structure is one of the key concepts with which information structure in Standard Japanese can be encoded (Büring 2007). Japanese has a word order subject-object-predicate, but the sentence structure is dominated by a Topic-Comment relationship. The Topic indicates what is being talked about (often old information), followed by the speaker's comment, i.e., substantially new information. A topic particle *wa* usually follows the Topic.

Other Japanese information structure concepts include the particles *wa* versus *ga*, where some researchers consider *ga* a focus particle (cf. discussion by Heycock 2008). Others consider the key concepts of information structure in Japanese as focus, givenness, and topic/topicality (Féry & Ishihara 2016, Tomioka 2016).

Japanese intonation has been well studied with syntactic structure and focus manifestation (Pierrehumbert & Beckman 1988, Kubozono 1993, Ishihara 2011). However, such studies are experimental with systematically varied

components. The corpus used for the present study consists of short sentences with simple syntactic structure, with no clearly identified focus.

Therefore, this study adopts a Topic-Comment structure as a reference. Two types of prosodic correlates of Topic-Comment structure in Japanese have been reported. The first is a regular pause insertion after the topic marker *wa* (Sugito 1986). The second is intonation in terms of the F0 peak relation between the domain of Topic and Comment. Unless the Topic is contrastive, the F0 tends to be higher in the Comment domain, which carries new information (Nakanishi 2007, Nakagawa 2016).

Method

Speech corpus

The study utilized parts of Children Voice Speech Corpus (CIAIRVCV) [24] as a primary material. The corpus contains read-out speech of words in isolation and a story, “The Little Match Girl” by H. C. Andersen in Japanese. The recordings are without annotation and are clipped for each word or sentence(s). The participants are 253 Japanese-speaking Children from the Tokyo district. Table 1 displays the specifications of the children.

Table 1. Specification of speakers.

Grade	Age	Girl	Boy	Total
1	6-7	16	15	31
2	7-8	18	20	38
3	8-9	18	20	38
4	9-10	24	30	54
5	10-11	25	23	48
6	11-12	23	21	44
Total		124	129	253

Sentences

The story consists of 32 sentences, of which 19 have a topic-comment structure. For analysis, two successive short sentences with a topic-comment

structure were selected. The Topic ends with a topic particle *wa*, and the rest belongs to the Comment. In (1), the Topic is ‘the girl’ and the subject is ‘stomach’; in (2), ‘the small hands’ is both the Topic and the subject.

(1)
 [Syoojyo-wa] [onaka-ga herimasita.]
 Girl-TOP stomach-NOM empty
 ‘As for the girl, her stomach became empty.’

(The girl became hungry.)’

(2)
 [Tiisana te wa] [imanimo kogoosodesita.]
 Small hands-TOP about to freeze
 ‘As for her small hands, they are about to freeze.’

Analysis parameters

The data was analyzed using the following parameters: total reading time and pitch range in semitone for the two successive sentences, pauses, and intonation, which were captured as F0 peak relation in the domain of Topic vs. Comment. All the measurements were done manually using PRAAT, and the obtained data was processed using SPSS for statistical analysis and graphs. SUGI Speech Analyzer produced Figure 5.

Results

Reading time

The boxplot in Figure 1 displays the distribution of the total time taken to read two successive sentences for each grade (age). It includes pauses and repetitions. The boxplot shows decreasing medians and standard deviation with increasing ages. A one-way ANOVA revealed significant differences in reading time across the six groups $F(5, 247)=48.9, p<.001$. Post-hoc comparisons indicated a significant difference between grades 1 and 2 ($p < .001$) as well as between grades 3 and 4 ($p < .001$). It is characterized that text reading fluency develops in two steps and becomes more stable after grade 4 (9-10 years).

Figure 1. Reading time by grade. Vertical bars denote inter-speaker variability (SD).

Pitch range

The pitch range (F0 max–F0 min for the entire utterance) distribution is shown in Figure 2 for each grade. The boxplot shows the increasing median and standard deviation from grade 1 to grade 3, and after grade 4, both become more stable, just like the reading time. A one-way ANOVA revealed significant differences in pitch range across the six groups $F(5, 247)=5.4, p<.001$. Post-hoc comparisons indicated a significant difference between grade 1 and other grades ($p < .05$). It is concluded that the pitch range measured in semitone does not vary across grades except for grade 1.

Figure 2. Pitch range. Vertical bars denote inter-speaker variability (SD).

Pauses

The total number of pauses, including inter- and intra-sentential pauses for the two successive sentences, is shown in Figure 3 for each grade (age). Inter-speaker variability (SD) becomes stable from grade 3.

Figure 3. Number of pauses. Vertical bars denote inter-speaker variability (SD).

The location and frequency of pauses are shown graphically for linguistic categories in Figure 4. Pause frequency is calculated in percentages by dividing the number of pauses by their potential numbers.

Figure 4. Pause location and frequency in %.

Figure 4 indicates that the location and frequency of pauses become stable from grade 4 (9-10 years). In the text, punctuation marks appear only for the sentences, and all the speakers (100%) inserted a pause after the first sentence. Around 70% of the topic marker *wa* is followed by a pause, while the particle *ga*, considered a focus marker by some researchers, is seldom accompanied by a pause. Another pause is found after the word *imanimo*, ‘almost,’ with a stable but less significant occurrence.

Intonation

F0 peak relation

The analysis shows three main intonation patterns based on the F0 peak relation in Topic (T) and Comment (C). Figure 5 illustrates the three patterns termed Level T=C, Downstep T>C, and Upstep T<C.

Figure 5. Typical F0 patterns for Level (T=C), Downstep (T>C), and Upstep (T<C). The speakers are all boys at 9 years old.

F0 peak values in the domains of Topic and Comment and the difference between the two F0 peaks are measured in semitones. F0 peak values for Topic (y-axis) and Comment (x-axis) are plotted with a reference line ($y=x$) to examine the difference in pitch range. Tokens below the reference line indicate the intonation pattern T>C, while tokens above the reference line indicate opposite T<C. Figure 6 shows the F0 peak plot for grades 1 and 4 for comparison.

Figure 6. Distribution of F0 peaks with a reference line. Grade 1 (above) and Grade 2 (below).

F0 peak range

Tables 2 and 3 compare the pitch range, SD, and the number of speakers for the two patterns (T>C and T<C). The mean pitch range is greater in the T<C pattern, indicating that the upstep patterns tend to show focal intonation. For this pattern, the speaker variability (SD) is more variable. The pitch range for the T>C (downstep) pattern is narrower than that of the T<C (upstep) pattern, with more minor standard deviations.

Table 2. F0 peak range for T>C patterns in semitone.

Grade	Mean (ST)	SD	N	%
1	1.22	0.90	51	80
2	1.35	0.79	60	79
3	1.54	1.00	60	78
4	1.49	1.06	77	70
5	1.66	1.06	68	69
6	1.31	0.80	58	70

Table 3. F0 peak range for T<C patterns in semitone.

Grade	Mean (ST)	SD	N	%
1	1.08	0.71	13	20
2	1.83	1.99	16	21
3	1.94	3.05	17	22
4	1.89	1.85	33	30
5	1.62	1.65	30	31
6	1.99	2.23	25	30

Development of intonation patterns

The results of the developmental change in the intonation patterns are shown graphically in Figure 7. Since most tokens have the T>C pattern with considerable variation in pitch range, the pitch range difference below 0.7 semitones is classified as T=C in this graph to show the changes more clearly. The Mixed pattern indicates that the two sentences have a different pattern, one T>C, the other T<C. The graph shows that the level pattern is gradually reduced while other patterns increase gradually.

Figure 7. Development of intonation during the primary school ages.

Discussion

Previous studies have reported that word-level lexical prosodic properties, such as lexical pitch accent in Japanese, are typically acquired before primary school ages (Shirose 2004, Fikkert et al. 2020 for an overview). The present study confirms the claim. All the children analyzed in this study demonstrated in their pitch accent patterns that they are native speakers of Tokyo Standard Japanese.

Several previous studies suggest what follows as the next stage of prosodic development: they include prosodic phrasing, intonation, and focus manifestation (Schwanenflugel et al., 2004; Wells et al., 2004; Frazier et al., 2006, Chen 2011, Chen et al., 2020, Romøren, & Chen 2022). The main developments found in the present study are along these lines.

The results of pause insertion in the present study agree with those reported by Sugito (1986), who analyzed Japanese broadcastings. Sugito found that the topic particle *wa* is usually followed by a pause regardless of punctuation, while pause insertion was rare after the particle *ga*, which some researchers consider a focus marker.

Unlike stable pause insertion, the intonation patterns show more variations and constant developments. The present study also reveals the upcoming focal intonation around grade 4 (9-10 years) in the Comment domain.

The difference in speaking style has a strong influence on the intonation patterns. The T<C (upstep) pattern indicates focal intonation, particularly those with an extensive pitch range. They are found in speech, where children try to read the text in a storytelling style. When the text is read more like a smooth narration, intonation becomes T>C (downstep) instead.

Godde et al. (2021) compared read-aloud material in French for two age groups: children (9–12 years) and adolescents (13–17 years). The results reveal many differences between the two groups, including differences in pausing and prosodic boundaries. The prosodic patterns of Japanese children in reading text are likely to develop further. It should also be noted that reading prosody differs from spontaneous speech (cf, Godde et al. 2020). Therefore, the upcoming focal intonation may be earlier in spontaneous speech in Japanese, which does not require reading competence.

Conclusion

The Topic-Comment structure in Japanese is well comprehended by primary school children and marked phonetically by inserting a pause in between. The intonational pattern captured as F0 peak relation between Topic and Comment changes throughout the primary school ages. The most significant changes occur between grades 3 (8-9 years) and 4 (9-10 years) regarding reading time, pause insertion, and focal intonation. The focal intonation is associated with the storytelling style.

Acknowledgment

We gratefully acknowledge using the “CIAIR Children Voice Speech Corpus (CIAIR-VCV)” provided by the Speech Resources Consortium at the National Institute of Informatics, Japan, which was crucial to completing this paper. Chen 2011.

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Enhancing AAC Devices with Generative AI for Natural and Expressive Speech Synthesis

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Abstract

Introduction: The advancement of generative AI in speech synthesis holds transformative potential for Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) devices, aiming to enhance the speed and naturalness of speech for users. This project focuses on developing and integrating generative AI to create expressive, conversational speech synthesis, ultimately improving the social inclusion of individuals relying on AAC devices.

Objectives: The primary objective is to leverage generative AI to develop an AAC system that provides contextually appropriate and naturally sounding speech. Specific goals include:

- Enhancing speech prediction accuracy using contextual data from Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR).
- Implementing style-adaptive Text-to-Speech (TTS) that interpolates between reading and conversational styles.
- Evaluating the system's effectiveness in reducing the communication effort for AAC users.

Current Work: We have developed a research prototype named ConnecTone, which serves as a modular platform for rapid integration and testing of language generation and speech technology. ConnecTone incorporates:

- **Contextual Generative Text Prediction:** Using conversational context from ASR inputs, ConnecTone predicts desired speech and provides multiple speech options generated by a Large Language Model (LLM).
- **Style-Adaptive TTS:** This component supports interpolation between reading and spontaneous conversational styles, allowing users to adjust prosodic features such as speech rate and pitch.

Planned Work: The upcoming phases of the project will involve:

- **User Studies:** Conducting extensive user studies with AAC device users to gather feedback and refine the system.
- **Enhanced Context Integration and Prosodic Control:** Implement object detection and user control of prosody via gaze and facial expressions.
- **Integration and Testing:** Integrating ASR components for better contextual understanding and implementing user-specific customization features.

Expected Outcomes: The project aims to deliver an AAC system that significantly reduces the communication time and effort for users. By generating more natural and contextually appropriate speech, we anticipate that users will experience enhanced social interactions and greater inclusion in daily activities.

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The role of F0 and Vowel Formant Dispersion in cis-gender female-male flirting interactions

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Abstract

This study explores variation in the fundamental frequency (F0) and Vowel Formant Dispersion (VFD) in cis-gender, heterosexual men (n=4) and women (n=4) within flirting interactions (compared to non-flirting interactions) on the American reality show ‘Married at First Sight’. Results show that women of this study produce a rise in mean F0 while in flirting interactions and men project larger vocal tract sizes (lower VFD). Our findings suggest that women may perform greater degrees of stereotypical hyper-femininity via F0 variation when aiming to appear more attractive to a desired male partner – at least for the speakers of the current dataset. As for the men, two speakers exhibit lower F0 when in the flirting context (possibly signalling notions of hyper-masculinity) where the other two raise F0 (possibly accommodating to their romantic partner). VFD shows similarly diverse results, with all men possibly using it to signal hyper-masculinity and only two women hyper-femininity. These results suggest that speakers of this study combine features associated with stereotypically hyper-gendered speech production with aspects of vocal accommodation to their partner in their flirting strategies.

Introduction

This study investigates the role of F0 and Vowel Formant Dispersion (VFD) in heterosexual flirting interactions. In this we argue that speakers may engage in flirting acts by drawing from and performing sociocultural expectations of hegemonic masculinity/femininity as a

way of signalling interest and sexual desire. Furthermore, we suggest that when such flirting strategies are not employed, speakers may instead rely on acts of accommodation (Lawson & Giles 1973) to signal interest in their romantic partner.

Speakers may perform more stereotypical gender presentations out of a desire to have their identities endorsed by the listener (Milani 2017), a desire which is perhaps most patent in a flirting interaction. Therefore, a cis-gender heterosexual individual may be likely to perform hegemonic and stereotypical gender presentations when aiming to flirt. This may be accomplished through an individual’s voice (in addition to other semiotic practices), as a way to indicate desire.

Studies have shown that women with a high F0 are initially considered more attractive by heterosexual male listeners (Buckert, et al. 2010; Puts, et al. 2011). Inverse findings have been shown in regard to male vocal attractiveness, wherein those with lower F0 productions are perceived as more attractive by heterosexual female listeners (Riding, Lonsdale, & Brown 2006; Xu, et al. 2013).

However, vocal attractiveness is only one aspect of human attraction. In more long-term relationships, the importance of vocal signalling of femininity decreases, suggesting that hyper-feminine gender presentation is less important than other factors (Puts et al. 2013). Furthermore, in studies where male subjects were in direct contact with their desired partner, these show that the importance of F0 decreases when deciding the level of attractiveness (Anolli &

Ciceri, 2002; Ranganath, Jurafsky, & McFarland 2013). This suggests that vocal productions of hegemonic gender and hyper-feminisation or masculinity are most important at the early stages of a relationship. We therefore might expect women to perform some form of hyper-femininity when flirting, raising their F0, while men may conform to notions of hegemonic masculinity by producing lower F0 as one of the many semiotic resources for signalling desire. This is particularly true for the current dataset as all speakers are on a reality dating show whose main objective is to find love. Love may nevertheless come in diverse forms, and in order to create a desired connection with their partner, speakers may employ different communicative strategies in order to best form and nurture the desired connection.

VFD is less studied within the literature on vocal attractiveness than F0 is, where VFD acts as a correlate of a speaker's projected body size (Babel, McGuire, & King 2014; Xu et al. 2013). VFD may therefore indicate fitness of a mate and is rife with potential to signal willingness to engage in a 'mating context' (e.g., Puts, et al. 2011) through the act of flirting.

Our research questions therefore explore whether male and female speakers employ aspects of F0 variation and VFD as a strategy to signal desire in flirting interactions, and to what extent these are employed in comparable ways within and across individuals. Furthermore, we explore if and how these flirting strategies are used differently by male and female speakers. In doing so, we present a study of vocal attractiveness in speech production with a focus on the relationship between two vocal attractiveness traits.

Methodology

Data for the present study comes from eight contestants on the American reality television show *Married at First Sight*, Season 9 (2019). In the show, a number

of singles are chosen and matched by a group of experts. These singles proceed to get married on the show, prior to having met each other or having any previous knowledge of their match. Their aim is then to attempt to fall in love and build a lasting relationship over the course of eight weeks.

The speech data comes from four male and four female contestants. Our corpus is derived from 'talking head' segments where the contestant is alone speaking to a camera (non-flirting context), and romantic situations with their matched partner (flirting context). The non-flirting context used in this study occurs before they have met their match where the flirting context contains data collected from so-called "date nights".

Speakers

All speakers of the study are heterosexual cis-gender singles of different races (though no paired couples are mixed-race), and ages (27-35 years old at the time of filming). Speakers are grouped with their corresponding partner (§2.3, Table 1; wherein C# refers to the couple numbering, and M/F corresponds to the male and female contestant of that couple). C1 and C2 are Black individuals, and C3 and C4 are White individuals. C3-4 further differed by showing more overtly sexualised flirting than C1-2. While the context of being more 'overtly sexualised' may be rather subjective, it is clear from the interactions that C1-2 were more practical in their attempts to get to know their partner, whereas C3-4 had very strong sexual overtones and engaged in more openly sexual conversational topics.

F0 and Vowel Formant Dispersion

All vowels in the recordings were manually identified and segmented in Praat (Boersma & Weenink 2021). In total, we analysed 19 minutes of speech with an average of 55 seconds for each speaker in their 'talking head' segment, and an average of 1m 50s for each couple

during their flirting interactions. Each speaker had between 275 and 464 vowel tokens with an average of 406 tokens per speaker (Table 1). In total, 3250 vowels were analysed across all eight speakers, with 1361 tokens in the non-flirting context (average 170) and 1889 tokens in the flirting context (average 236).

Formant measures were extracted at the temporal midpoint of each vowel. F0 was set with a minimum pitch parameter of 50Hz, and a maximum of 600Hz for both males and females. This was done as instances of periodic creak and falsetto occurred in both the female and the male data. The results presented here are based on raw F0 values for two reasons. Firstly, these do not differ from the results available for the ST normalisation. Secondly, this is also in line with some other studies in the area of vocal attractiveness (Farley & Lafayette 2013; Fracaro, et al. 2011). VFD analysis was conducted via F1, F2, F3, and F4 values which were also extracted at the temporal midpoint of each vowel token. Vowel normalisation was not conducted as VFD analysis relies on raw Hz values. The flirting and the non-flirting contexts are segmentally comparable.

Speaker	Flirt	Non-flirt	Total
C1:F	327	137	464
C1:M	324	137	461
C2:F	119	213	332
C2:M	289	187	476
C3:F	131	144	275
C3:M	156	192	348
C4:F	258	176	434
C4:M	285	175	460

Table 1: Number of tokens per speaker.

Analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted via Linear Mixed Effects Models in R (R Core Team 2021), using the lme4 (Bates, et al. 2014), the lmerTest (Kuznetsova 2015), and the effects packages (Fox, et al 2017). The initial models for

analysis included predictors for Sex (female or male), context (flirt or non-flirt), vowel (18 levels), and couple (C1, C2, C3, C4) with a sex*context interaction and F0 or VFD as a dependent variable. Individual models were then contrasted through backward stepwise ANOVA tests by taking out an independent variable one at a time.

Due to the size of the dataset, race was not included within the statistical modelling as a discussion of potential implications of differences in race is out-with the scope of the present paper. Impressionistically, within our dataset, there are no obvious overall trends regarding flirting strategies and race *per se*, and F0/VFD variation – though the male speakers do show race-specific patterns briefly discussed below, which we attribute to the difference in approaches to flirting strategies being more or less overtly sexualised as opposed to differences in race *per se*.

Results

The mixed effects analysis reveals that across all speakers, a higher F0 is realised in the flirting context in contrast to the non-flirting one ($\chi^2(4) = 22.96, p < 0.001$), as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: F0 (Hz) by speaking context for the model: F0 ~ Context * Sex + Vowel + Couple + (1|Speaker).

Overall, female speakers have higher maximum and mean F0 values in the flirting context than in the non-flirting context. Their F0 minimum is lower in the flirting context. This means that they also display a larger F0 range in the flirting context. In contrast, male speakers have lower maximum F0 values and a smaller range in the flirting context. All

of these differences are nonetheless rather small in magnitude, and the interaction between sex and context is not significant ($\chi^2(1) = 2.14, p = 0.14$). Fig. 2 shows the overall F0 change for all speakers across the two contexts by sex.

Figure 2: Comparable F0 change for all speakers by context.

While there is an overall rise in average F0 for the male speakers in the flirting context compared to the non-flirting context, as shown in Table 2 there appears to be an interesting disconnect not represented within the statistical models. Two speakers (C1:M and C2:M) follow the same patterns as the female speakers with a rise in F0 within the flirting context. The other two speakers (C3:M and C4:M) lower their F0 in the flirting context, which falls in line with previous research on male vocal attractiveness (Riding, Lonsdale, & Brown 2006; Xu, et al. 2013). Interestingly, this difference correlates with speaker race with the Black male speakers raising their F0 in flirting interactions, while the White male speakers lower their F0. Though this finding correlates with differences in race, we do not suggest that it is in fact motivated by racial differences; instead, it seems more likely that this finding is an artefact of the overall tone of the conversation given that C3-4 are more overtly sexual in contrast to C1-2.

Speaker	Flirt	Non-Flirt
C1:F	230	218
C2:F	285	191
C3:F	241	238
C4:F	211	217
C1:M	149	133
C2:M	177	117
C3:M	126	154
C4:M	163	173

Table 2: Mean F0 for each speaker by context. All values represented in Hz.

The females also offer interesting individual-specific variation. C1:F and C3:F show little visual change across the two conditions. C4:F has a higher mean in the non-flirting situation, but a larger range in the flirting situation. Finally, C2:F has a larger range and higher mean F0 value in the flirting context.

Looking at the individual couples provides an interesting insight as well. Couples 1, 3, and 4 show extremely low-magnitude change across the two conditions. However, both the female and the male speakers show a comparable magnitude of change by context, both increasing their F0 in the flirting context. C2 stands out: both speakers shift, but they do so in the same direction, and more so than the other couples (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Comparable F0 change by context in Couple 2.

In terms of VFD, higher maximum VFD values correspond to smaller vocal tract size where lower VFD values indicate more expansive usage of the vowel space. The mixed effects analysis shows that across all speakers, VFD is lower in the flirting context ($\chi^2(1) = 8.79, p < 0.01$), which means that speakers generally project a larger size of the vocal tract when flirting, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 VFD (Hz) by speaking context for the model: $VFD \sim Context * Sex + Vowel + Couple + (1|Speaker)$.

This effect is nevertheless driven primarily by the male speakers. Overall, females project a smaller vocal tract size (higher VFD) than males in general, although including the variable of sex does not improve the model fit ($\chi^2(1) = 1.02, p > 0.3$). The male speakers show larger and more consistent differences across the conditions, and both groups also display higher VFD range values in the flirting context.

As shown in Table 3, here too we find couple-specific patterns. The male speakers all consistently lower their VFD in the flirting context. Surprisingly, two females show the same tendency (C1:F and C3:F), albeit with a very small magnitude of the effect. On the other hand, and as expected, C2:F and C4:F project a *smaller* vocal tract in the flirting context (i.e. higher VFD). Thus, the male speakers are consistent in that they all lower their VFD in the flirting context, and they also do so with a larger magnitude of the effect than is the case for the female speakers (irrespective of the directionality of the effect in these female speakers).

Speaker	Flirt	Non-Flirt
C1:F	1100	1119
C2:F	1153	1114
C3:F	1207	1219
C4:F	1164	1160
C1:M	1209	1220
C2:M	1161	1190
C3:M	1113	1170
C4:M	1157	1197

Table 3: VFD for each speaker by speaking context. All values represented in Hz.

Discussion

Despite the limitations on the size of our dataset, the results presented here provide interesting insights into flirting strategies that may be employed by speakers. The speakers of the current study have a vested interest in making things work with their romantic partner. While in everyday interactions, individuals may flirt casually, and decide if they would like to continue seeing the person (with the option of leaving the relationship as they see fit before any commitment to the new partner is solidified), the individuals in the present study are quite literally “Married at First Sight”, creating an incentive for any romantic (i.e., flirtatious) interactions to succeed.

Our results may indicate two potential flirting strategies, neither of which is mutually exclusive within an interaction. The first is that individuals may employ speech acts of hegemonic/hyper-masculinity or femininity as a way to signal willingness to engage in romantic interactions. In such interaction we find that speakers are engaging in hyper-gendered productions, which corresponds to features which are interpreted as more attractive to the opposite sex (e.g. Anolli & Ciceri, 2002; Ranganath, Jurafsky, & McFarland 2013). Overall, for the speakers of the present study, productions of hyper-femininity more consistently rely on F0 where productions of hyper-masculinity more consistently rely on VFD. Our results show that three

of the four female speakers raise their F0 in flirting interactions, which is one potential method to exhibit more stereotypically hyper-feminine productions. Two male speakers also lower F0 in the flirting interaction. The overall results for F0 fall in line with research suggesting greater degrees of attractiveness for females with higher F0 and males with lower F0 productions. Furthermore, all male speakers project a lower VFD value within the flirting context, which meshes well with the expectation that larger vocal tract size will be projected in such situations.

The two male speakers who do not lower their F0 are perhaps engaging with what we suggest is the second potential flirting strategy - accommodation. This would make sense as a potential flirting tactic given that accommodation is one known method employed in attempts to gain approval between interlocutors (e.g. Giles & Powesland 1975). We suggest that the two male speakers who do not lower their F0 are converging their speech to their romantic partner as a way of quickly accommodating to their new spouse as well as the newlywed situation they now find themselves in. This accommodation is most evident in C2, who shows the greatest change between flirting and non-flirting contexts. While two females raise their VFD values and project a smaller-sized vocal tract, the other two female speakers nevertheless do the opposite. In doing so, the female speakers with lower VFD values may be accommodating to their partner in ways they do not for F0, albeit to a lesser extent.

Our results suggest that both strategies are used by both genders to some extent. In this, speakers do not restrict themselves to one flirting strategy, with some speakers employing a combination of the two strategies within the same interaction using different vocal cues in their attempts to create a bond with their romantic partner. Of these two romance

strategies, accommodation tends to emerge more frequently as a possible tactic amongst couples in more romantically-presented interactions, where more sexually-presented interactions seem to result in more productions of hyper-masculinity/femininity.

While there is no doubt that further strategies beyond those suggested here may be employed to signal romantic desire, our results show two of the potential ways in which a speaker may indicate romantic and/or sexual attraction. By utilising aspects of both accommodation and productions associated with stereotypical masculinity/femininity speakers may get the best of both worlds. On one hand they tap into notions of stereotypically attractive (fe)male voices, and on the other they can accommodate to reinforce a budding mutual kinship. These findings further highlight the usefulness of analysing more than one vocal attractiveness trait within the same speech sample.

Conclusions

Vocal attractiveness is an important aspect of the human experience. While studies of human attraction have been explored in terms of visual and olfactory attractiveness (e.g. Fugère, Leszczynski, & Cousins 2015), this paper has explored potential vocal strategies for ways that humans may indicate their attraction to a romantic partner. In this, we show that regardless of the flirting strategy, F0 and VFD variation is a potential resource which can be employed when engaging in flirting interactions. Furthermore, within our dataset, it seems that men rely on VFD more uniformly and women rely on F0 more uniformly, although both strategies are used by both men and women to some extent. In this, something interesting is observed for males with F0 and for females with VFD, wherein speakers may be using secondary vocal cues to accommodate to their partners. We suggest that vocal convergence to a romantic partner, *and*

performances of stereotypically performative gender (and therefore divergence) which fall in line with the sociocultural expectations of attractive female/male voices may both act as potential strategies either on their own or in combination when conveying sexual attraction and may therefore be employed in attempts to endear oneself to their partner. Romantic and sexual interactions thus represent an interesting case where both accommodation and non-accommodation can happen simultaneously between two interlocutors.

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An inclusive approach to creating a palette of TTS voices for gender diversity

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Abstract

Current text-to-speech (TTS) systems primarily support binary gender voices, often not representing the diversity of gender identities such as transgender and nonbinary individuals. This limitation is significant for users of Speech Generating Devices (SGDs) who seek voices that authentically reflect their identities. Our research introduces a novel methodology for constructing a controllable palette of gender-expansive TTS voices. Utilising recordings from 14 gender-expansive speakers, we apply Constrained Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to extract gender-independent speaker identity vectors, allowing for the modulation of acoustic Vocal Tract Length (aVTL) and emergent vocal properties in a neural TTS framework. We detail the design process influenced by community input from nonbinary SGD users, emphasising increased diversity and control over voice characteristics. We evaluate the system with a series of objective metrics to assess quality, speaker consistency and to measure the extent to which aVTL is modifiable for each speaker. Additionally, we perform a community-based qualitative evaluation using online interviews, to evaluate the system's capacity to generate adjustable and diverse vocal qualities. This work takes a step toward more inclusive voice technology that transcends traditional gender binaries, with the aim to support self-expression for gender-expansive individuals.

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How can quantitative measures of social age help us analyse uptalk?

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Abstract

Uptalk has been established to be indexically linked with certain social groups, including young, female speakers. This means this intonational feature has been claimed to index a young or youthful age. As recent work has attempted to broaden the sociolinguistic variable of *age* from chronology (the number of years lived) to encompass a speaker's biological and social age, the assessment of speakers' age groups is necessarily complicated. This paper investigates whether the uptalk produced by two female speakers of Tyneside English can be seen to co-vary with chronological and social age, and how various measures of social age may be used to initiate or triangulate sociophonetic analyses of age-related features such as uptalk. The paper exemplifies the way in which the linguist can productively investigate age beyond chronology.

Introduction

Analyses of speaker *age* in phonetics have tended to conceptualise this variable as resulting from a speaker's chronology, that is, their number of years lived. However, recent work (e.g. Bowie, 2011; Wagner, 2012; Pichler et al., 2018; Hejná & Jespersen, 2021; 2022) has pointed to the problems inherent in such an approach.

Firstly, this approach treats age as a monolith, whereby post-adolescent life is relatively stable across time and across speakers, and this is necessarily simplistic (see Pichler et al., 2018: 2).

Secondly, taking such a view entails the risk of overlooking important contributions to a person's vocal production (and perception) brought on by their individual age trajectories, such as physiological changes resulting from accelerated or decelerated biological ageing, or various ways of negotiation or stepping outside social age norms and categories.

Biological age (e.g. in the former example) can practicably be investigated by the ordinary phonetician as laid out in Hejná & Jespersen (2021). Social age identities, however, are more ephemeral and thus difficult to capture in an experimental setting. Nevertheless, operationalising age in way that goes beyond chronology is not impossible. This paper uses an analysis of *uptalk* to exemplify how the phonetician can operationalise social age and how social age measures can be used to initiate or triangulate qualitative sociophonetic analysis.

Uptalk rises are phrase-final rising F0 movements associated with declarative statements (e.g. Fletcher et al., 2005; Warren, 2016, Jespersen, 2019). Uptalk has shown generation-specific patterns in different varieties of English (Warren, 2016: 116-119), which is why this phenomenon has been chosen as a variable to consider here. Specifically, uptalk has often been claimed to index a young or youthful (chronological) age. However, it is less clear how well such indexicalities map onto social age, and how well the sociophonetician can access them in an experimental setting.

This paper thus sets out to address the following research questions:

RQ1: How well can social age be accessed through the proposed qualitative and quantitative measures?

RQ2: How useful are such measures to a phonetician?

RQ3: Can the measures provide evidence on whether uptalk is indexically linked with chronological or social age?

Methods

Speakers

The data for this study results from sociolinguistic interviews collected from 2 female speakers born and raised in Tyneside, North England (who are part of a dataset of 12 speakers). The speakers' chronological ages range from 19–57 years. Speakers' names and personal details have been anonymised.

Procedure

The data collection consisted of 1) a sociolinguistic interview with each participant, 2) a series of physical tests to provide information about their biological age. For more information about the latter, which will not form a part of this paper, see Hejná & Jespersen (2021, 2022).

The sociolinguistic interview data was recorded in a phonetics booth at Newcastle University with a Zoom 5 Handy recorder and an AKG C520 head-mounted microphone at a sampling rate of 44.1kHz. The interviews were conducted by the first author. Potential participants had been approached via Facebook and via the snowball method, and those recorded were financially compensated for their time.

Social age measures

As part of the sociolinguistic interview, participants were asked a series of questions to elicit information about their social age. In this paper, we will refer to participants' subjective age (the answer to the question “how old do you feel most of the time?”), as well as age categories, where participants are offered a choice between categories such as

“teenager”, “young adult”, “adult”, “older” or “elderly”.

Moreover, the present analysis will consider participants' self-identified life stage, a measure of social age which is co-constructed between the interviewer and the interviewee and can contain reference to any relevant aspect of a person's current life stage, such as “young mother”, “student”, “workaholic”, and which offers the participant flexibility to opt out, e.g. “in-between life stages”.

Finally, we provide an analysis of the participants' stancetaking, that is, the way they position themselves relative to the content or material under discussion through language use (Kiesling, 2022: 410; Du Bois, 2007: 141). We chose to include this analysis to exemplify the use of a qualitative operationalisation of social age. Here, we borrow from Kiesling's (2022) additions to Du Bois' (2007) conceptualisation of stancetaking through the so-called *Stance Triangle*.

In this framework, the *speaker* and an *interlocutor* are seen to interact with each other and with the person or idea under discussion – the *stance object*. Each interactant will evaluate the stance object through stance-taking. As the conversation flows, the interactants may accept or reject their interlocutor's previous stance, thus aligning or disaligning with them. Furthermore, stances differ in investment, or the degree to which the speaker is invested in an utterance.

We further note that stance in this model is seen as dynamic and interactive, in that any individual can take any stance, but that habitually taken stances index and are constitutive of enregistered identities (Kiesling, 2022: 412).

Investigating uptalk

The linguistic analysis focused on two sections of the sociolinguistic interview, namely speakers' answers to the questions “How do you feel about ageing?” and “Have you ever encountered ageism at any point in time?”. These were analysed for stancetaking, and any uptalk

risers were analysed as described below. After this, the passages were transcribed orthographically.

Rises were located by manual inspection of pitch traces in Praat (Borersma & Weenik, 2021) by the first author, who assigned fundamental frequency (F0) rises to the category of uptalk rises based on three criteria: 1. a pronounced upward trajectory from a metrically prominent syllable towards a phrasal boundary (thus including interference from the pitch tracker itself, and the effects introduced by the segmental environment), 2. the association of the F0 rise with the final intonational phrase of a declarative sentence (thus avoiding non-final rises such as those used in listing); 3. a smooth, domain-adjacent F0 rise rather than a rise-plateau or rise-plateau-slump associated with longer stretches of material, such as those associated with Urban Northern British rises (as these have found to be heard as different entities to uptalk rises, and might thus carry different indexical meanings; see e.g. Jespersen, 2019).

Analysis

In this section, we first set out to analyse two short, transcribed passages from the sociolinguistic interviews using more conventional methods for approaching social age. This analysis will attempt to link uptalk rises with the stances they co-occur with. These short extracts are meant to illustrate larger tendencies in the dataset, which, for reasons of space, we are not able to fully expand upon. After this, we look at the social age measures to investigate how these can help us nuance and support our interpretation of the speakers' use of uptalk.

Uptalk and stance

In the following, uptalk is represented in Autosegmental-Metrical (AM) notation. L* L-H% represents a low rise, L*H-H% is a high rise from a low onset, and H* H-H% is a high rise from a high onset. The notation (e.g. L* H-H%) marks

the start of the rise, and underlined material indicate the spread of the rise. Slashes (/ or //) represent the ends of intonational phrases. Three dots (...) represent a pause. Material in all caps (LIKE SO) signals the use of increased amplitude, or loudness. Colons (word::) represent increased duration. Significant paralinguistic cues are represented in double parentheses.

As the interviews were explicitly conducted on the topic of age and ageing, the speakers volunteered various stances on age, both their own and the variable in general. We begin by analysing a passage from Ava, 19, who evaluates her own age identity through stancetaking.

Extract 1: Ava, 19

AJ:((laughing)) You just want to be older, right?

Ava: Yeah I want to be older / but I think it's 'cause I had my older sister so I was like ohh I wanna be... I wanna do what [L* H-H%] she's doing and / cause mum and dad are like no, you're too young:: / I just wanna be / ((smiles)) I just wanna be older... ((laughing)) /

Here, Ava had just discussed her preference to befriend people of older age groups and how as a child she would often play with her older sister's friends. The identity work involved is a negotiation of her own age identity in relation to that of her older sister and to the expectations of her parents. Her stancetaking revolves around negative affective evaluations of her chronological age and its social limitations.

The uptalk rise, L* H-H%, runs through the phonetic material 'she's doing and'. Uptalk rises can be construed as Labovian stereotypes indexing a certain type of young, hip, American-oriented identity (Warren, 2019: 116-119). Its use here co-occurs with an attempt to align with Ava's older, "cooler" sister. We read this as uptalk being part of a

“cool” stance – a positive evaluation of her sister’s age group. The concurrent negative evaluation of her own age group further supports this interpretation.

Extract 2: Fee, 52

AJ: So you don’t feel bad about ageing /
Fee: I don’t feel [**H* H-H%**] too bad about / I think I keep myself quite FIT / and ACtive:: / and look after myself / but it’s getting to the stage now where I’m seeing friends:: [**L* H-H%**] SUFFER with ageing / and:: die through illnesses that are caused by ageing / so I think it’s bringing / the last couple of years I think it’s bringing it close to / closer to me that / I am actually [**L* L-H%**] old:: / I don’t feel it so much no /

In this conversation, Fee and the interviewer had just discussed Fee’s skin care routine in the context of being a busy working mum. The identity work involved in this extract is a negotiation of her social age identity through comparisons between biological ageing in herself and her friends of a similar chronological age group. Her stancetaking revolves around positive evaluations of her own biological age and negative affect towards ageing processes associated with her friends.

In Fee’s first three lines of speech, her relatively positive evaluation of the stance object, her own biological ageing, is centred on actions she has taken to mitigate the biological ageing process, but her investment in this stance can be argued to be quite low, as indicated by the hedging in phrase two. In the following four lines, she sets up a contrasting take on the ageing process, where negative evaluations are directed at “unsuccessful” examples of ageing in her own chronological age group. The last four lines conclude the exchange with a rise in investment. Here, she develops a negative evaluation of her own ageing process and offers an alternative to her

previously named age category, namely the social age identity “old”.

It is interesting that this second age category seems to be socially, rather than chronologically, based: despite her attempts to mitigate physiological ageing, and despite her self-identified life stage (a “busy working mum”), her alignment with her chronological age group means she is considering membership of a social category she defines as “old” to which she could conceivably belong.

This section features three uptalk rises in Fee’s 1st, 5th and 10th lines. The rises occur with the phrases ‘too bad about’, ‘SUFFER with ageing’, and ‘old::’. Note that the indexical links between uptalk and cool youth culture that are exploited by Ava do not seem to be activated in this extract. We can explain this difference with reference to Kiesling’s expanded notion of alignment.

In line two, the high uptalk rise is realised with the introduction to a series of relatively positive evaluations of Fee’s own age. This topic can be viewed as potentially face-threatening for Fee: a woman’s feelings about and actions towards her biological ageing is a socially complex topic. Consequently, Fee might arguably be attempting to minimise face-threat by signalling her wish to align with the interviewer on the topic of the relevant stance objects, drawing upon the first-order indexical links between uptalk and functions such as signalling uncertainty and audience engagement (see Warren, 2016).

This uptalk rise is a high-onset high rise, acoustically very high pitched (322–380 Hz) and near the very top of the speaker’s pitch range in this extract, which further supports the reading of this rise as a cue to high investment, and as indexing interlocutor engagement and uncertainty (see Ohala 1984). With the rises in Fee’s line 5 and 10, we also see uptalk realised with high-investment stances, that is, those involving socially challenging or complex topics: her

friends suffering with the effects of biological age (L5), and her own recasting as “old” (L10).

Here, higher-order indexicalities do not seem to be invoked. This provides additional evidence that indexical links between “youth” and uptalk use are available to speakers, but that uptalk is not exclusively used for age-related work (cf. Jespersen 2019). Furthermore, rather than signalling “youth” in general, we hypothesise that uptalk is linked for Ava to a specific social age group. The difference in uptalk use between Ava and Fee’s passages might thus be explained if this hypothesis holds water: the social age group which is seen by Ava as desirable is not relevant to Fee, who focuses her attention in this section on an “old” age group – to which she could conventionally be seen as belonging. Thus, the indexical links between uptalk and a “cool young person” identity could be seen as lessening the usefulness for Fee of using of uptalk to signal “youth”.

Uptalk and social markers

Table 1. Social age measures for Ava (19) and Fee (57).

Measure	Ava	Fee
Subjective age (mean)	18	40
Subject. age discrepancy	-0.5%	-30%
Age category	Young adult	Late middle to pensioner
Life stage	Early professional	Busy working mum

This section investigates the connections between our two speakers and the three social age markers included in this paper: subjective age, subjective age discrepancy (the difference between speakers’ chronological and subjective ages), life stages and age categories. Through this analysis, we hope to address the hypothesis laid out in the last section:

uptalk is linked to a certain social age group, and thus to social, not chronological, age.

Table 1 contains an overview of the social age markers investigated. Note that both speakers feel younger than their chronological age. However, Ava’s subjective age is much closer to her chronological age compared to Fee’s (0.5% versus 30% lower). Ava (19), a student, sees herself as a young adult and an early professional: she’s on her way up and already on her way onto the linguistic marketplace. The social age measures thus support our reading that social age comes into play in different ways for our two speakers.

For Ava, who in the extract above describe wanting association with older age groups, the social age markers correlate better with chronologically older age groups. Speakers over the age of 18 tend to feel approximately 20-30% younger than their chronological age. But not Ava. Her identity is future-oriented: although a student, she feels like an early professional already. Positing that her use of uptalk is indexically linked with chronological youth, then, does not mesh well with her self-identification. Instead, it co-occurs with stances that positively identify her with a chronologically older social group. It is not chronological youth that is desirable to Ava, but a certain social age group (defined more by “what [they’re] doing” (l. 4) than their chronological age.

For Fee (57), work and family share the limelight as she adjusts to being at the cusp of her pensioners’ age. There’s a tension between her current life stage (“busy working mum”) and her age category (“late middle to pensioner”). She is also looking forward, and thus youth in general, and “cool youth” in particular, is less relevant to her.

Evaluation of social age markers

It is clear from the space taken up by the stance analysis that it is not practicable

for most phoneticians to conduct such an analysis while also conducting experimental phonetic work. However, it is also, we hope, clear that a speaker's social age can influence the meaning of sociophonetic variables such as uptalk, and with that potentially their frequency and form (and *function*) in the dataset. Finally, we note the close agreement between the qualitative analysis of participants' stances on age (which is lengthy) and the quantitative social age measures (which are concise).

We therefore suggest that including social age measures such as *subjective age* (which can easily be included in a recruitment survey or in the introduction to the study) or *age categories* can be both useful and practical for the experimental (socio-)phonetician.

Conclusion

This paper has probed the claim that uptalk is indexically linked to perceived *chronological age* (RQ3). In doing so, it has evaluated several methods for approaching social age (RQ1), from both qualitative and quantitative perspectives. Furthermore, the practicality of these measures for the phonetician (RQ2) has been evaluated.

We proposed that uptalk is linked not to chronological youth, but to a social, achronological age group we termed "cool youth". We invite sociophoneticians to test this hypothesis, and argue that a useful way of accessing, or triangulating, age-related social indexicalities is with social age measures such as the ones trialled in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Newcastle University phoneticians and AUFF (Aarhus University, Denmark).

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Reference values for vowel formant frequencies in adult vocally healthy Swedish speakers: Comparison of text reading and carrier phrases

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Abstract

Vowel formant frequencies are utilized in various domains of speech-language pathology. Reference values from vocally healthy speakers are needed to enable comparison with values from patients. This study adds to the current body of research on Swedish formant frequencies (Fant, 1966; Eklund & Traunmüller, 1997; Persson & Jaeger, 2023). The purpose of the study was to present formant frequency data for Swedish vocally healthy female and male speakers and to compare results from different speaking tasks. This study is part of an ongoing research project at the Division of Speech and Language Pathology at Karolinska Institutet, “Svensk röstbank för referensdata”. Participants were 51 women and 23 men over the age of 18, recorded in a sound-treated booth using a standardized procedure. Formant frequencies F₁, F₂, F₃ and F₄ were analysed in the vowels /i:/, /i/, /a:/ and /a/ from a reading passage and carrier phrases (with and without hVd-context) using the Praat software and recommendations by Kent and Vorperian (2018). Results of inter- and intra-rater reliability indicated strong reliability (average ICC(2) was 0.91 and 0.95 respectively). The results showed a statistically significant difference in formant frequencies between men and women, as expected, with an average of 16.5% higher values for women. Furthermore, several differences associated with formant analysis were observed between the two speaking tasks based on both a quantitative and qualitative approach. In the reading passage, greater influence from complicating factors such as coarticulation, speaking rate and word stress was noted compared to the carrier phrases. Correlation between values from the two tasks was moderate (average ICC(2) was 0.56). Based on the results, carrier phrases are recommended for use in research studies and clinical application as they provide increased reliability in formant analysis compared to reading passages.

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Novelty Search on Vocal Models

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Abstract

Knowing which sounds can be produced by a simulated vocal model is not trivial. Being able to map this out can be interesting for applications that make use of the extended capabilities of a voice, e.g. singing. Novelty search is proposed as a method to explore acoustic capabilities of articulatory models, leveraging the representations of a human-like auditory perception model.

Introduction

Knowing which sounds a voice can make is not an easy question to answer, but important for singers, especially when they are still in training. It can be a help in deciding on what you should spend your practice time. If you know for sure that your physiology does not afford the production of certain kinds of sounds, then you can stop striving for it, and conversely – maybe even more importantly – if you know that a sound is possible, but you do not know how to make it yet, it is an incentive for vocal exploration.

Despite computer-implemented articulatory-acoustic models being more observable than the vocal mechanism of a living person, their acoustic potentials are not easily deducible from their implementations because of the non-linear relationships between the articulatory control parameters, their acoustic consequences and human auditory perception. Thus, when studying these models in terms of their suitability to emulate singing, one is faced with a similar question as the living singer: What sounds can this model actually produce? Some limitations might be obvious from the

model specifications (e.g. only vowels), while others (e.g. What timbres are within reach?) might be much more difficult to answer by only looking at the model design.

In contrast to methods that attempt to optimize model parameters to fit a certain auditory target (e.g. the vowel *a*) we propose using *novelty search* (Gomes, Mariano, & Christensen, 2015; Lehman & Stanley, 2011) to automate the exploration of the model parameter space to find sounds perceived as meaningfully different. To conduct a novelty search, we have to specify a dissimilarity measure. As we are aiming for the domain of (human) singing, this measure should preferably be informed by human auditory perception. Machine hearing as the modeling of human auditory perception is a field of study in itself, with a good introductory text in Lyon (2017). Finally, this method produces a corpus of sounds exhibiting the sonic variety that the model can produce, together with the input parameters that produce them.

There are several benefits to producing sound and parameter collections that attempt to acoustically characterize a vocal model. Most obviously, having such a corpus enables a characterization and possibly a taxonomy in terms of what the model can do. Furthermore, through the analysis of overlap and differences, these corpora can form a basis for comparing one model with other models as well as with corpora of human utterances. Studying whether similar sounds were produced by similar articulatory configurations and vice versa might also be revealing. If an

articulatory voice model makes a sufficiently close approximation of a real human voice, this would hold the promise of giving a useful pointer to human singers as to how to achieve this sound with their own instruments.

In the following, we first shortly review some related work and then delve into the three components of this experiment: Articulatory vocal models, novelty search, and human-like perception models. Then, we give some specifics of the experiments we intend to perform and of which we might be able to report some preliminary results at Fonetik 2024. While some of the named benefits can apply to both articulatory and non-articulatory vocal models, we limit our scope to the former category. We end with a discussion and conclusion.

Related work

As an articulatory-acoustic model can be seen as a synthesizer with a specific parameter set, exploring the sound space of a musical synthesizer is conceptually the same problem as the one described above. Novelty search has been used in that context to generate diverse sounds (e.g. Masuda & Saito, 2023), albeit in a sound matching context.

In the realm of speech, there have been several attempts to emulate the process of baby-babbling, in which a baby explores its vocal endowments and learns to produce syllables. This process is simulated with the Maeda (1979, 1990) model by Moulin-Frier et al. (2014) and by Philippsen (2021) in the context of Vocal Tract Lab (Birkholz, 2013). While these systems implement goal-directed and intrinsically motivated exploration, they do not attempt to explore model potential as such.

Non-articulatory Singing Voice Synthesis has been around since at least 1977 with the KTH MUSSE system (Sundberg, 2006). In those early years it was mainly a research instrument for analysis by synthesis aimed at perception and musical performance research.

While MUSSE started as an analog signal processing system driven by a rule-based performance system, nowadays the field is dominated by dataset driven neural approaches (Cho et al., 2021; Cui et al., 2024; e.g. Katahira, Adachi, Tai, Takashima, & Takiguchi, 2020; Shimizu et al., 2022; Sugahara et al., 2023) and achieves a very high degree of naturalness, which allows it to be used in digital music production.

Articulatory-acoustic models

Kröger (2022) surveys computer-implemented articulatory models for speech since the 1960s. Where these models originally had the goal of producing high-quality speech through replicating the human speech organs, they have long been outperformed by non-articulatory models in this domain. Nowadays they mainly serve as a research tool. These models have control parameters that correspond to configurations of the articulators, which can be either static positions or dynamic trajectories. Of the 21 articulatory models described in the survey, we are interested only in the 10 models with an acoustic component, i.e. that can produce sound. It should be mentioned that all these models are meant primarily for speech research, so certain design choices might have been made that do not suit singing very well. This would be another reason to explore and analyze their capabilities.

For our purposes, the models should have an existing, fast implementation that is available for research use, as novelty search requires many iterations. Examples of implementations are the Maeda model as a part of DIVA (Guenther, 2006; Tourville & Guenther, 2011)ⁱ and Vocal Tract Labⁱⁱ, but also *gnuspeech*ⁱⁱⁱ and Thapen's *Pink Trombone*^{iv}.

Novelty search

Lehman and Stanley (2008, 2010, 2011) promote novelty search as an alternative to objective driven optimization in

deceptive problem spaces, i.e. problems where the solver tends to get stuck in local minima. In their evolutionary algorithms, they use *novelty* as a criterion instead of a typical fitness function that measures proximity to a goal. Just like a typical optimizing fitness function, novelty is defined in the phenotypical space. In our case we choose the auditory perception domain as the phenotypical space, further called “perception space”. Contrary to typical fitness, novelty is defined in relation to neighboring points in a space, not in relation to a fixed objective.

Let p be an articulatory parameter vector for a vocal model VM . Through the vocal model, we obtain a sampled acoustic waveform $x = VM(p)$. The perception model PM then projects x into the perception space $z = PM(x)$. We then define the novelty $\rho(z)$ at some evolutionary iteration as the sparseness of its neighborhood with respect to sounds so far generated by the model. We adapt the definition of sparseness by Lehman & Stanley (2011), thus defining the novelty z as the mean distance to its k nearest neighbors:

$$\rho(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \text{dist}(z, \mu_i) \quad (1)$$

where $\text{dist}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a dissimilarity measure defined in the perception space. The neighbors μ_i come from the current population generated by the evolutionary algorithm, as well as from a possible archive of sounds that has been kept over the course of the calculations. As $\rho(z)$ increases, the closest neighbors are at a larger distance, meaning that the current sound collection is sparser around point z in perception space.

The novelty search algorithm tries in every iteration to maximize the sparseness for every produced sound. In a genetic algorithm, this will make the population diverge to different regions of the perception space.

As mentioned before, one can keep an archive of previously calculated sounds, which can be included as

neighbors in the sparsity calculation. Sounds can be included in the archive on different grounds e.g. based on a novelty threshold, or at random with a certain probability (Gomes et al., 2015).

The intended result of the novelty search algorithm is an exploration of the goal-space that should be significantly more effective than a random walk and that does not get stuck in local minima.

Novelty search might require a considerable number of evolutionary generations to give a good idea of a model’s capabilities. Initially, therefore, we must work with fast vocal and perception models, and parallelize the procedure as much as possible.

Human-like perception models

With our focus on singing, it is important that perception be focused on music, not on speech. For example, two or three formants might be enough to characterize speech vowels, but not for conveying the timbral resolution that is necessary for singing.

As mentioned in the previous section, we need a dissimilarity measure that is not defined in the articulatory space, but in perception space. In order to aim for sounds that are meaningfully different to humans, we need an auditory dissimilarity measure that reflects human perception.

One way to achieve this is to leverage methods that aim to directly emulate the signal processing in human hearing as measured by psychoacoustic experiments, e.g. the gammatone (Patterson, Allerhand, & Giguère, 1995) and gammachirp (Iriño & Unoki, 1998) filterbanks. Another strategy is to model the functional components of the auditory system, like Lyon’s (2017) CARFAC and SAI models, that emulate the cochlea and the auditory representation in the brain stem. More recently, deep learning strategies with the same goal have appeared (e.g. Baby, Van Den Broucke, & Verhulst, 2021).

In the previously mentioned studies on baby-babbling (Moulin-Frier et al., 2014; Philippsen, 2021), the authors make use of ad-hoc auditory perception models. Moulin-Frier et al. (2014) devise a strategy that includes only the intensity and the first two formant frequencies, while Philippsen (2021) uses three formants for her experiments with static sounds. When working with dynamic vocal trajectories, she starts out with MFCC features. As with the filterbanks above, this entails that samples of different length also tend to be considered as very different. Philippsen mitigates this by embedding these features with a small RNN and a subsequent dimensionality reduction by PCA and LDA.

The recent appearance of the deep learning-based CLAP-model (Elizalde, Deshmukh, Al Ismail, & Wang, 2023; Elizalde, Deshmukh, & Wang, 2024; Wu et al., 2023) trained on massive amounts of sound and text captions might offer another way of tackling this problem. Its embeddings (fixed length vector representation of audio) offer an audio representation that is cheap to compute and relates to human perception through the human involvement in the selection of the sound recordings in its dataset as well as through their text captions. This might be one of the first things to try.

Forthcoming experiments

As this study is still in an early stage, we cannot show any experimental results yet. We hope to be able to show some preliminary results in the conference presentation. Similar to Lehman & Stanley (2010) we intend to implement novelty search based on a genetic algorithm, for which we will have to define the mapping between the genome and the articulatory control parameters that affords the genetic operations of crossover and mutation in a meaningful way. We will start with static vowels, and subsequently possibly expand our scope to

consonants and more dynamic situations. Apart from listening to the generated sound samples, more rigorous evaluation could comprise statistical analyses of the audio features present in the generated corpus, as well as the extent to which the articulatory input parameter ranges have been used.

Discussion

One question that only the experiments can answer is whether novelty search will work in high-dimensional perceptive goal spaces. Lehman & Stanley (2011) show that increasing the dimensionality does not hurt performance in their use case, but the NEAT algorithm they are using (Stanley & Miikkulainen, 2002) evolves behavioral neural architectures. In their case, it is the behavior exhibited by these architectures that should be novel. In addition, NEAT also has a built-in tendency to generate architectures that increase in complexity over time.

Secondly, our hope is that the generated corpora could be a way to investigate the quantal theory of speech (Stevens, 1989). According to this theory, there are certain regions in the articulatory space that are acoustically stable in the sense that larger parameter changes do not entail big changes in sound. Conversely, there are also regions where smaller parameter changes have a big impact. As a result, aiming well into the middle of the stable regions makes speech, and possibly even singing, robust to inevitable noise in vocal control. Last but not least, we hope that the resulting corpora might become good datasets to train inverse dynamics for these articulatory models, meaning that a machine learning model that is given a sound efficiently could generate the parameters that would produce that sound.

Conclusion

In this report on work in progress we have presented the motivation behind and the ingredients of our coming

experiments with novelty search to characterize the singing potential of articulatory-acoustic vocal models.

Acknowledgements

This work is an outcome of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (MUSAiC, Grant agreement No. 864189).

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ⁱ <https://sites.bu.edu/guentherlab/software/diva-source-code/>

ⁱⁱ <https://www.vocaltractlab.de>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.gnu.org/software/gnuspeech>

^{iv} <http://dood.al/pinktrombone> or reimplemented on <https://github.com/zakaton/Pink-Trombone>

Simulating hypernasality with phonological features in Swedish TTS

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Abstract

This study explores the use of phonological features in text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis by simulating hypernasal resonance. By training neural TTS with phonological features instead of more traditional input methods, we are capable of producing speech sounds unseen in the training data, letting us manipulate the voice in our current task: to produce disordered speech. The results of an acoustic analysis indicate successful manipulation of hypernasal resonance, although a perceptual evaluation showed lacking authenticity, particularly in certain prosodic aspects. Despite limitations, our approach using synthetic speech with simulated hyper-nasal resonance shows potential in the use of perceptual training for speech-language pathology (SLP) students, provided that relevant improvements are implemented.

Introduction

Hypernasal resonance, or *hypernasality*, is a resonance disorder typically caused by speech motor difficulties or structural deficits in the speech apparatus. Hypernasality manifests as nasal resonance on speech sounds where none is expected, making vowels nasalized while also affecting voiced consonants. As a symptom, it is known to be difficult to assess successfully for licensed SLP practitioners. Reliable assessment of hypernasality is therefore key for ensuring suitable

clinical care but learning material for perceptual assessment training is not always available.

Text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis has gone through a rapid development for the past decade in the production of synthetic speech, achieving human-like results (see e.g. Tan et al., 2021). However, its potential in simulating disordered speech is not nearly as explored.

Using phonological features as input to TTS gives us the ability to map features of the voice to a range of numerical values, which can then be manipulated by increasing or decreasing the value. This method allows TTS synthesis to produce speech sounds which are absent from the training data. For example, nasality could be increased for all speech sounds in a sentence, creating nasal resonances where there otherwise would not be any.

In this study, we aim to explore whether the method used can generate speech with the acoustical characteristics that is inherent in hyper-nasality. The generated speech will be measured and analysed both acoustically and perceptually.

Background

Phonological features and TTS

With “Preliminaries to Speech Analysis”, Jakobson et al. (1952) defined speech sounds as a set of features based

on articulatory criteria. These features were binary, for example Vocalic/Consonantal, Grave/Acute and Nasal/Oral. Their work is viewed as part of the foundation for what is called phonological features today.

As input method for neural TTS synthesis, phonological features are more detailed and less commonly used, but gives us increased control over the output compared to the more common TTS input methods, such as graphemes or phonemes.

In our approach, these features are represented by gradual values between 0 and 1 for various degrees of a specific feature. The task of the TTS model is then to learn the relations between the phonological feature values and the speech in the training data. During synthesis, it is possible to use feature values that did not occur in the training data as input, including values below 0 and above 1. This makes it possible to synthesize speech sounds which the original speaker never produced.

Little research has been done on the topic of simulating disordered speech, and even less combined with the use of phonological features as input. Moëll et al. (2022), used phonemic feature vectors to synthesize speech data augmentation for automatic phoneme recognition of aphasic speech (phonemic paraphasia). Moëll et al. used a set of binary features proposed by Chomsky and Halle (1968). The resulting TTS voice was used as training material to improve automatic speech recognition (ASR) models for patients with aphasia, showing improved results. Another study used phonemes as input to TTS, simulating dysarthric speech also to serve as training data for ASR with noticeable improvements to the ASR model (Soleymanpour et al., 2022).

Hypernasality

Hypernasality is defined as a resonance disorder caused by a velopharyngeal dysfunction. The dysfunction results in

insufficient closure of the velopharyngeal port, creating nasal resonance also during the production of oral speech sounds. In addition, the insufficient closure allows air leaking through the nasal cavity during the production of plosives, causing voiced plosives to turn into voiced, nasal speech sounds.

Acoustically, nasalised vowels are characterised by the existence of additional resonances and anti-resonances in the vowel caused by the coupling between the nasal and the oral cavity. The nasal resonances will enhance harmonics relative to their surroundings which results in “nasal peaks” or “nasal formants” (Styler, 2017a). Also, due to “nasal zeros” or “nasal antiformants” occurring in the nasal cavity, the voice should see a reduction of spectral energy in certain frequency ranges.

The most recommended method for measuring nasal resonance in vowels is A1-P0 (Styler, 2017a) in which we subtract P0, a nasal formant occurring between 250 to 450 Hz, from A1, the amplitude of F1. The resulting value is lower the more nasal resonance exists in a vowel due to A1 being lowered by the nasal zeros and P0 rising due to the nasal resonances.

Given that A1-P0 is affected by specific vowels, Chen (1996) recommends A1-P0 to be adjusted for vowel types and offers a function which uses the relative bandwidths and position of formants. This “compensated” measurement will be referred to as A1-P0(comp) throughout this paper.

Method

The TTS voice

The model used in this study was trained on over 12 000 Swedish sentences read by a female professional speaker, originally recorded for unit selection TTS by the Swedish Agency for Accessible Media, as part of the Filibuster project (Ericsson et al., 2007).

The data was originally segmented into phonemes, and each phoneme were then converted into a phonological feature vector of 15 phonological features and one language feature. Each feature was assigned a value between 0.0 and 1.0. Consequently, the nasality feature was 0.0 for oral speech sounds and 1.0 for nasal consonants and vowels. Oral vowels in nasal contexts were given +0.25 nasality for each adjacent nasal speech sound.

The neural TTS voice used was trained using OverFlow (Mehta et al., 2023) as encoder and HiFi-GAN (Kong et al., 2020) as vocoder. Overflow is based on a neural hidden Markov model (HMM) with normalizing flows. The decoder/vocoder HiFi-GAN is a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) designed for high-fidelity speech synthesis. HiFi-GAN performed faster and produced more human-like speech than the best publicly available models of its time during its release in 2020 and Overflow was shown to produce speech with fewer mispronunciations than comparable methods in 2023.

Test data

For the acoustic analysis of vowels, the five peripheral vowels /i: e: u: o: a:/ were chosen. The vowels were put between voiced alveolar or bilabial plosives as context, either /b/ or /d/ as both onset and coda and inserted in the carrier phrase “Jag säger --- igen”, (English: “I’m saying --- again”). Five degrees of nasality were applied, ranging from 0.0 to 1.0 with a 0.25 increment, affecting all speech sounds by the same value for all sentences. Recordings from the human voice underlying the training of the TTS voice were included as reference in the analysis, referred to as “test data” throughout this paper.

The sentences used for the perception test were taken from SVANTE (Lohmander et al., 2015). These sentences are designed to enable assessment of articulation and nasal resonance,

through their consonant patterns and lack of nasals. Five sentences were chosen:

1. Bibbi bara jobbar
2. David å du leder
3. Kicki kokar korv
4. Giggi vill väga guld
5. Lollo lurar Ella

The values used for the degrees of simulated nasality differed from the data used in the acoustic measurements. In this case, the values 0.33, 0.67 and 1.0 were used for all speech sounds, as well as 0.67 and 1.0 for vowels only, resulting in a total of five different nasality settings. The reason for the split between affecting all speech sounds and affecting vowels only was to investigate which of these two methods provided a more perceptually accurate simulation of hypernasality.

A1-P0

A1-P0 were measured using Styler's and Scarborough's (2017b) Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2024) script for nasality measurement. The script required the audio files to be annotated in Praat Textgrids with two tiers; vowel and word. Annotation of the words were done manually by finding the beginning and end of the target word in each carrier phrase. Annotation of the vowels were done by identifying a 0.05 second interval in the middle of the vowel. The script was set to run with standard settings except for the number of measurements per vowel, set to three. This setting means that the script measured the vowel at three separate points, in the beginning, middle and end of the annotated segment.

Consonant substitution

A manual annotation was made on the same words used in measuring A1-P0(comp) but only for the degrees of 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 because of it being unlikely that any substitutions would take place if

Figure 1. Spectral slices for synthesized /ε:/ with the applied nasality degrees of 0.0 (left) and 1.0 (right).

no, or close to no, manipulation takes place (degree 0.0 and 0.25). The annotation was done by the first author who counted the plosives and nasals, respectively, in the target word. If a plosive had been substituted by a nasal it was also documented if the place of articulation remained the same or if it changed. Each word had two plosives each, which made the data used into a total of 40 words and 80 consonants per nasality value.

Perception test

Five licensed speech pathologists, the majority of whom were some of the leading experts on hypernasality in Sweden, took a survey made in Google Forms. They were instructed to use headphones and to assess the degree of hypernasal resonance in manipulated speech, with the alternatives None, Slight, Moderate and Severe. Three additional questions concerned their experience of hypernasality assessment, how they experienced the speech samples in the perception test, and finally if they found any potential in using simulated speech disorders in perceptual skill training for SLP students.

Results

Figure 1 shows spectral slices for the nasality degrees 0.0 and 1.0 in the manipulated voice. An increase in P0 and a decrease in A1 is indeed visible when nasality is set to 1.0, indicating that the manipulation of nasality worked as expected. In addition, the degree of 1.0 was associated with other acoustic markers

of nasality, such as presence of anti-formants, indicated by the sudden drop in energy around 500 Hz and 2300 Hz. We can also see an increase in energy around 1000 Hz, most likely corresponding to P1, another nasal formant.

Figure 2 shows A1-P0(comp) for all the data points separated by the different degrees of applied nasality in the simulated voice together with the recordings made by the original speaker (test data). As can be seen there is a decrease in A1-P0 for the highest degree of manipulation (1.0) indicating an increased nasal resonance in vowels. The differences show no obvious pattern in the lower values. Notably, the recordings from the test data deviates slightly from the unmanipulated voice (0.0) by showing a slightly wider spread of data points.

Figure 2. A1-P0(comp) for all vowels

The results from the manual annotation of consonants with nasality degrees 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 can be seen in Table 1. It shows a clear shift in nasal substitution

the more simulated nasal resonance is applied to the voice, with almost every

Table 1. Number of substitutions for every word and value split by place of articulation. The values range from 0 to 8, where 8 is the maximum number of substitutions possible for a given word and degree.

Word	0.5	0.75	1.0	Place
/bi:b/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	0	8	alveolar
/be:b/	0	0	7	bilabial
	0	0	0	alveolar
/ba:b/	0	3	8	bilabial
	0	0	0	alveolar
/bo:b/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	0	8	alveolar
/bu:b/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	0	8	alveolar
/di:d/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	0	8	alveolar
/dɛ:d/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	0	7	alveolar
/da:d/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	8	8	alveolar
/do:d/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	4	8	alveolar
/du:d/	0	0	0	bilabial
	0	3	8	alveolar

plosive substituted by a nasal when the nasality was set to 1.0.

Some differences between the vowels did occur. At 0.75 almost all the nasal substitutions happened in /ɑ:/ for both contexts with some occurrences in /u:/ and /o:/ as well. At 1.0, all the plosives had turned nasals except one of the occurrences of /be:b/.

The plosives substituted by nasals generally retained their place of articulation, though not always: the bilabial plosives in /bi:b/, /bo:b/ and /bu:b/ were substituted to the more posterior position by the alveolar /n/.

For the bilabial contexts, /ba:b/ and /be:b/ were the only words where the plosives kept their place of articulation. The alveolar contexts followed the same

pattern, where the plosives were replaced by the alveolar nasal /n/.

The perception test involved both quantitative and qualitative questions, of which the quantitative results can be seen in Table 2. Here, the median score was taken for the combined answers for each audio file, grouped by degree of nasality. 1.0 on all speech sounds received a median score of “Moderate” while the lower degrees all received a median score of “None”.

Table 2. Median scores from the perception test for each degree of nasality applied on all speech sounds or vowels only.

Degree of nasality	Applied on	Median
0.33	all	none
0.67	vowels	none
0.67	all	none
1.0	vowels	none
1.0	all	moderate

The respondents agreed that simulated speech disorders could potentially be used in perceptual assessment training for SLP students, but there was also a consensus that the provided audio files were not good enough for this purpose. Comments concerned the quality of consonants being deviant in an unrealistic manner and the intonation was increasingly deviant the higher nasality degree was applied. It was also noted that real-life patients rarely exhibit hypernasality and no other symptoms. Lastly, a few remarks were made about the lack of credibility due to the speaker not being a child.

Discussion

This study sought to find out whether the manipulated voice would show the acoustical characteristics that is inherent in hyper-nasality. This hypothesis proved to be correct, indicated by the facts that A1-P0 were lower at the higher degrees of manipulation and that all consonants except one out of 80 were

substituted by a nasal for the highest degree of manipulation (1.0).

A1-P0 is proven to work well for measuring nasal resonances in vowels (Styler, 2017a). One interesting finding of the present study was that the TTS voice showed a generally lower median score of A1-P0 and a slightly larger spread of data points than the recordings of the speaker's natural voice used as training data. Given that it is technically a different voice with different contexts used for the vowels, both of which are factors proven to influence A1-P0, this finding is in line with previous research (Styler, 2017a).

Regarding nasal substitution, the involvement of only one annotator is a limitation, preventing evaluation of annotation reliability. If the substitution would have been between speech sounds more alike each other, a more precise way of measurement would have been appropriate.

It could have been interesting to include more natural test data sentences, as a complement to the standardized SVANTE sentences and the carrier phrases with target words, both for the acoustic measurements and in the perception tests.

The open questions in the survey provided us with important information and gave us further insights in the potential of the TTS voice. There was a consensus among the participants that simulated speech disorders of this kind could be beneficial for perceptual skill training in speech therapy studies, provided that certain aspects of the synthesized speech were improved to enhance authenticity.

The TTS voice used was trained using some of the best performing models currently available. Regarding the features used, we used a set of phonological features that is currently under development. It is designed for experimentation with non-binary features in Swedish neural TTS. In this study, the only feature that was manipulated and used in a

non-binary manner was the investigated nasality feature. Using a fully binary features set would have excluded the possibility of investigating different degrees of simulated nasality. The rest of the feature set matches a standard Swedish phoneme description and is in practice equivalent to typical phoneme-based training.

Conclusions

The TTS voice managed to create synthetic speech with hypernasal resonance, demonstrated by a reduced A1-P0 in vowels and substituted/reduced consonants. We conclude that the synthesized speech with simulated hypernasal resonance shows some potential, but is not yet suitable for direct application in SLP e-learning or educational settings.

Overall, this study contributes to advancing the understanding of using phonological features in TTS synthesis. Future research could focus on fine-tuning the feature manipulation, combining commonly co-occurring speech disorders commonly found together as well as exploring using a child TTS voice.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the individuals who participated in the survey for their valuable answers.

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Autophon.org

An online tool for automatic phonetic annotation

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Abstract

Autophon (autophon.org) is a free web application that facilitates automatic phonetic annotation. It supports both Nordic and low-resource languages, addressing critical gaps in phonetic research. The platform reduces technical barriers, saving time for students and researchers. Rigorous validation ensures the accuracy and reliability of its tools, making it a valuable resource for the linguistic community.

Introduction

We introduce Autophon (autophon.org), a free worldwide web application designed to facilitate phonetics research through forced alignment technology. This initiative simplifies phonetic annotation by using neural networks via systems like The Montreal Forced Aligner (McAuliffe, Socolof, Mihuc, Wagner, & Sonderegger, 2017). It automatically timestamps speech recordings, aligning them with transcriptions to produce phonetic annotations in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2024), optimizing user inputs and expediting tasks that traditionally required significant manual investments. This is especially beneficial in regions like Scandinavia where the high labor cost for manual phonetic annotation can eat up research budgets.

The project's mission is to democratize forced alignment tools, evident in its free accessibility and focus on Nordic languages. In bypassing complex command-line programs, it empowers students and researchers to use speech analysis tools efficiently. Security and privacy of user data are ensured, with files

deleted after alignment. Despite being in *beta*, efforts towards stability and bug fixes are ongoing.

Background

Forced alignment technology automates the alignment of speech recordings with their transcripts, ensuring precise synchronization of phonetic segments. Traditionally, this was done manually, which was labor-intensive and prone to errors. We offer a short review of this technology here; however, for a more exhaustive review, refer to Young & McGarrah (2023). The early 2000s saw the rise of Gaussian Mixture Models in computational linguistics (Young, Woodland, & Byrne, 1993), which phoneticians used to construct forced aligners such as FAVE-Align (Rosenfelder, Fruehwald, Evanini, & Yuan, 2011) and The Multilingual Annotation and Alignment Tool MAUS (Schiel, Draxler, & Harrington, 2011).

Recently, the field has shifted over to Deep Neural Networks on frameworks like Kaldi (Povey et al., 2011), leading to the Montreal Forced Aligner (MFA). Autophon, the web app discussed here, currently uses MFA vers. 1.0 for its backend operations.

WebMAUS marked a different milestone by offering this technology on an online portal (Schiel, Draxler, & Harrington, 2011). While certainly enhancing accessibility for researchers, it has also faced challenges like codec specificity, compatibility errors, and limited technical support. Other online portals providing access to forced alignment

➕ Add files

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Language	Tiers	Size MB	Words	Missing Words	Last status
<input type="checkbox"/>	008F_beg 2024/05/19 - 15:48:17	English - North America					2 minutes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Lavkebenhavnsk 2024/05/19 - 15:47:20	Danish (DanFA 3.0) (suggested)					3 minutes
<input type="checkbox"/>	Exp Ling A Batch 240518 16:25 2024/05/18 - 16:25:41	French - France (suggested)	File pairs: 8	0.2	76	4	Completed
<input type="checkbox"/>	Exp Ling A Batch 240518 16:22 2024/05/18 - 16:22:57	German - Germany (suggested)	File pairs: 5	0.1	40	9	Completed
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ljud_1_Augustinsson_ch1 2024/05/18 - 16:20:08	Swedish - Sweden (suggested)	1	24.7	839	11	Completed
<input type="checkbox"/>	031_interview 2024/05/18 - 14:50:05	Norwegian - Bokmål (suggested)	1	67.1	695	21	Completed

Figure 1. A screenshot of the Autophon application.

tools include the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Forced Aligner¹ and the North Carolina State University Forced Alignment Service². While valuable, these platforms often suffer from the same weaknesses as WebMAUS.

Autophon distinguishes itself by offering an intuitive UX and a codec-agnostic engine, improving accessibility, efficiency, and reliability. In the ensuing prose, we highlight the app’s three main focuses: (1) integrating diverse forced alignment tools into a user-friendly interface, (2) developing new models for Nordic languages, and (3) bootstrapping models for low-resource languages.

Focus 1: User ease

Access first

Figure 1 illustrates a screenshot of Autophon’s user interface (UX). By *access first* we mean that even the most accurate phonetic tools are of little utility if (a) the barrier to access is too tedious or time-consuming and/or (b) validating accuracy is too difficult. The abundance of command-line tools in the field necessitates a need to remove barriers, facilitate user access (UX), and offer support. What is more, researchers often face a *paradox of choice* where too many options can lead to a sort of decision paralysis that hinders productivity (Iyengar &

Lepper, 2000; Schwartz, 2004). Evaluating and testing multiple programs becomes a task unto itself, diverting time and effort from primary research objectives.

We try to meet this challenge with Autophon by consolidating various tools into a unified platform. It currently features MFA vers. 1.0 with plans to incorporate other tools like MFA vers. 3.0, FAVE/Penn Forced Aligner, LG-FAVE, and – further in the future – Wav2vec. By providing diverse tools in one place, Autophon streamlines the selection process, allowing researchers to efficiently identify and utilize the most effective tools without being overwhelmed. This empowers users to focus on research rather than the complexities of tool implementation and evaluation.

Search engine optimization

Searching “online forced aligner” or “automatic phonetic annotation Nordic languages” on Google brings up Autophon as a top result. Such effective search engine optimization (SEO) facilitates accessibility and visibility, ensuring that researchers – regardless of network connections – can easily find and use the app. In a place like Scandinavia where research networks often are siloed and invitation-only, SEO makes access

¹ <https://web.uwm.edu/forced-aligner>

² <https://phon.chass.ncsu.edu/cgi-bin/step7.cgi>

more horizontal, fostering a broader community of scholars.

Intuitive UX

Autophon’s intuitive user interface (UX) helps reduce the learning curve and time investment for users. It is built to streamline the onboarding process, enabling users to quickly understand and use the application’s features. This is particularly important in phonetics, where technical barriers often deter students, especially undergraduates. But even seasoned researchers require efficient tools and workflows as they face off against performance pressure in academia. Phonetics as a field requires exorbitant time for data collection, annotation, and processing. In the neoliberal academic environment and an increasingly market-driven research funding milieu, this reduces the “competitiveness” of phonetics compared to less technical humanities disciplines. The UX is designed to minimize the time spent on processing, allowing phoneticians to reallocate their time to empiric inquiry and theory.

Tech support

Autophon provides tech support, setting it apart from traditional open-source web and desktop programs. Desktop applications require individualized troubleshooting, which often makes them resource-intensive and subject to unpredictable funding streams. In contrast, Autophon’s web-based platform allows for scalable problem-solving and what we call *altruistic debugging*: when one user’s problem is fixed, it benefits all users. The approach makes the app resilient to various operating systems and their technical issues. Further, Autophon’s commitment to tech support enhances the user experience and contributes to a more inviting environment for phonetics research.

Accuracy metrics

Significant resources have been dedicated to validating models against

manual corrections, with current validation statistics available for Danish, English, Norwegian, Swedish. Validation helps researchers make and justify their choices, ensuring accountability and replicability in their work. Standard established metrics for validation are used such as median and mean offset time and percentage of offsets that fall within ten and 20 milliseconds from the manual gold standard (Young & McGarrah, 2023, p. 113).

Focus 2: Nordic languages

Although the mainland Scandinavian languages are considered high-resource by most measurements, forced alignment technology has lagged for them, being mostly only available for “super-resource” languages like English and French (c.f. Lindh, 2007a). It is our view that this may be one reason behind the scarcity of large-scale phonetically annotated corpora of spontaneous Scandinavian. This section briefly examines the current state of forced alignment for Nordic languages, our view on the implications for linguistic research, and our efforts to address these challenges.

Current state in Scandinavia

Advancements in automatic phonetic annotation for English have coincided with numerous public corpora of phonetically annotated *naturally occurring spontaneous speech* (Kendall & Farrington, 2023; Pitt, Dille, Johnson, Kiesling, Raymond, Hume, & Fosler-Lussier, 2007; Coleman, Baghai-Ravary, Pybus, & Grau, 2012). In contrast, Nordic languages have remained underserved. For example, the Swedish Dialect Database *SweDia 2000* only has its read-aloud section phonetically annotated (Eriksson, 2004, p. 39). The RUNDKAST corpus, a Norwegian Broadcast News Speech Corpus, includes only 50 minutes of annotated read-aloud speech and ten minutes of spontaneous speech (Amdal et al., 2008). The DanPASS corpus for Danish

provides phonetic annotation only at the syllabic level for spontaneous speech (Grønnum, 2009). To our knowledge, the only publicly available corpus of a Nordic language with phonetically annotated spontaneous speech is the ten minutes from RUNDKAST, highlighting a significant gap in resources.

With Autophon, the aim is to help close this gap by lowering the technological barrier to annotating naturally occurring Scandinavian speech. This is particularly crucial for two fields; namely, (1) research on language variation and change and (2) forensic speaker comparison. We offer a case in point below for each.

Pertaining to variation and change, recent public inquiries were made into Swedish multiethnolect and its phonetic spread into standard Swedish (SVT Nyheter, 2024; Sveriges Radio, 2024). In response to this inquiry, Swedish academia had few studies to refer the public to (cf. Gross, Boyd, Leinonen & Walker, 2016; Gross, 2018; Young, 2021). Pertaining to forensic speaker comparison (Jessen, 2008), reference corpora of urban Swedish are absent, which increases the risk of false positives because typicality must be calculated on more modest regional data like, e.g., Lindh (2007b). The current proliferation of telephone fraud cases in Sweden (SVT Play, 2024) underscores the acute need for phonetically annotated reference corpora that include spontaneous speech from speakers of newer urban sociolects.

Autophon's contributions

Autophon is one small cog within the research enterprise, merely a tool. However, this tool provides a unified space where researchers of Nordic phonetics and phonology can access the latest forced alignment tools, significantly reducing the time and effort required to navigate and evaluate multiple programs. This inclusive approach not only simplifies the research process but also empowers researchers to focus on their

primary objectives rather than the complexities of tool vetting and implementation.

Focus 3: Smaller languages

With this tool, we seek to bridge the gap in forced alignment technology for low-resource languages by offering *bootstrap models*, a method that has proven effective in previous studies (Coto-Solano & Solórzano, 2017; Young & McGarrah, 2023). Bootstrapping means adapting existing models from one language to a second genealogically close language.

Methodology

The methodology for bootstrapping involves several steps. Initially, existing models that are trained on a resource-rich language are adapted to a new target language. This adaptation is done by leveraging phonetic and linguistic similarities between the source and target phonemes. Subsequent alignments produced by the bootstrap model can then be manually corrected and used to train native models for the target language.

Young (2017a) demonstrated the bootstrap approach with a Swedish-language adaptation of FAVE-Align, showing that it is robust and reliable for both spontaneous and read-aloud Stockholm Swedish. This same procedure was later also conducted for Danish (Young, 2017b). By starting with the existing Hidden Markov Models trained on English in FAVE-Align (Rosenfelder et al., 2011), significant reductions in manual segmentation time were achieved with a substantial proportion of boundaries falling within acceptable error margins compared to manual alignments (Young & McGarrah, 2023).

Faroese and Icelandic

Autophon has adopted this bootstrapping approach to develop aligners for Faroese and Icelandic based on a Norwegian language model (Young, 2020). These aligners offer a starting point for

researchers working on these languages, enabling them to conduct initial phonetic annotations, which can later be refined and corrected. This iterative process will eventually help develop fully native models for these languages.

Limitations and future directions

No formal validation statistics are available for our bootstrap models, so we are seeking collaborations with researchers to assist in calculating them. By working together, the goal is to gather enough manually corrected data to construct robust models that meet established accuracy benchmarks. As part of the initiative to bootstrap models for low-resource languages, prototypes for Elfdalian and Greenlandic are also being developed by leveraging existing resources (e.g., Oqaasileriffik, 2007; Steensland, 2021).

Conclusion

The Autophon project is a forward-thinking approach to overcoming challenges in phonetic research, particularly for Nordic and other low-resource languages. The platform prioritizes access and use, reducing the learning curve for students and researchers. By integrating multiple forced alignment tools into a user-friendly web application, it minimizes complexities typically associated with phonetic annotation, allowing users to focus on their core research objectives.

A significant contribution of this project is its support for educational environments. The intuitive user interface and comprehensive resources make it ideal for teaching phonetics and linguistics, enabling students to engage with advanced speech analysis tools without technical barriers. This accessibility enhances learning and encourages deeper exploration of phonetic phenomena.

For researchers, the project offers a streamlined phonetic annotation process, saving substantial time, effort, and money. The focus on creating models

tailored to Nordic languages addresses a critical gap, with bootstrap models facilitating initial alignments and further refinement. This iterative process fosters collaboration and continuous improvement, contributing to high-quality linguistic resources.

The commitment to validation underscores the project's dedication to supporting the research community. By validating models against manual corrections and adhering to established metrics, the platform ensures reliability and trustworthiness. Ongoing validation efforts demonstrate a strong commitment to quality.

In summary, this initiative represents a significant advancement in phonetic research tools, offering substantial benefits for both teaching and research. By bridging the gap between computational methods and the practicalities of access, Autophon supports research efficiencies, the aim of which is to foster a more relevant and rigorous field of phonetics.

Abbreviations

MFA – Montreal Forced Aligner
SEO – search engine optimization
UX – user interface

Acknowledgements

Autophon was funded in part by a grant from the Swedish Academy, a grant from the Department of Linguistics and Scandinavian Studies at The University of Oslo, and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892963.

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Towards quality transcriptions of large, limited domain archive data

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Abstract

Despite the proliferation of speech data in public archives, research in areas such as speech science and, more broadly, (digital) humanities and social science is often hampered by the lack of search facilities. Recent advances in automatic speech recognition (ASR) help, but custom ASR systems, specifically adapted to the characteristics of an archive, can still outperform more general solutions.

In this work, we explore the use of general-purpose ASR to obtain training data for archival transcription. We use Swedish parliamentary data as a near-ideal example in which existing partial transcripts can be used to support the process, and aim to apply these methods to less ideal archives, such as broadcast news, where the only associated text resources are weakly related materials such as contemporary news from print media.

Results indicate that while fine-tuning on the intersection of outputs from two ASR systems does not surpass state-of-the-art performance, it does show promise for further refinement.

Introduction

Parliamentary recordings are interesting for many reasons, not least from a speech science and speech technology perspective. In addition to their well-established use for training speech-to-text systems, or *automatic speech recognition* (ASR), they are rich in unique characteristics that are interesting in their own right. Because they cover a large time span, they can

serve as a primary source for diachronic investigations. They also serve as a bridge between read and spontaneous speech: although speakers typically begin with a prepared script, they often deviate in response to other speeches or events during the same session. And as parliamentary speakers come from all regions of a country, they contain a wide range of dialects. Furthermore, the diversity of topics discussed leads to both detached discourse, speeches brimming with affect, and displays of sentiment for rhetorical effect.

We present an investigation that utilises ASR to iteratively improve automatic transcriptions of Swedish parliamentary recordings with several parallel objectives. Beyond creating accurate transcriptions, we seek a methodology that allows us to use general-purpose ASR to efficiently obtain task-specific training data for archival speech materials. We focus on parliamentary speech with an eye towards other limited domain archives that share similar characteristics. For example, broadcast news also involves a finite number of speakers under similar speaking conditions.

The development of bespoke ASR systems we aim for will bridge gaps in the public record, broadening the scope of research outside speech technology (or “AI”) and speech science, for example in digital humanities.

Our intention is that this work be used as a yardstick for other planned projects, both for Swedish and the other languages of Sweden, as it represents an approximation of ideal conditions. The experiences here will determine our

approach towards projects where conditions are less favourable and serve towards directing our efforts where they are best placed, not least within the scope of the creation and maintenance of national research infrastructure for speech technology and speech science in Språkbanken Tal.

Background

Parliamentary data in ASR training

The availability of transcripts makes parliamentary recordings attractive for the development of ASR systems: for many languages, it is the only source of transcribed speech in sufficient quantity of speech and diversity of speakers to train an ASR system (e.g., Solberg & Ortiz, 2022). In many cases, however, they are limited to scheduled speeches that were filed in advance, with no guarantee that the transcript reflects where a speaker went off script, nor of interactions outside of that script.

Research access to speech archives

The current work is carried out in the context of two large-scale projects that investigate speech archives: *SweTerror* (Edlund et al., 2021) and *Increasing the availability of the audiovisual collections of the Swedish National Library*. Both projects address the gaps in the records, aiming for an improved representation of the speech archives.

The focus on parliamentary data is partially due to the goals of the former project, partially because access to other sources of archival speech such as broadcast speech is limited by obstacles that have proven difficult to reconcile.

In addition, the parliamentary audio is accompanied by a large amount of transcribed text; in other domains this will not be available, or available only indirectly and in part. In broadcast news, for example, we can assume that the

news as broadcast on television will broadly match that as reported in print to enough of an extent that we can extract at least direct quotations.

Swedish ASR

Two systems stand out as the current state-of-the-art for freely available Swedish ASR: Whisper (Radford et al., 2022) and a wav2vec2-based system (Baeovski et al., 2020) using a model pre-trained on over 10 000 hours of Swedish speech (Malmsten et al., 2022), VoxRex¹.

Whisper has received attention partly because of its accuracy, its multilingual capabilities, its ability to translate to English, and its ability to generate capitalised and punctuated output. When capitalisation and punctuation are removed, however, the VoxRex model, on the other hand, is still the most accurate model available for Swedish.

Method

The extensive data available in Riksdagens Öppna Data points to two key questions:

Intersection of ASR Systems. Can the intersection of outputs from two ASR systems provide a sufficient basis for developing a bespoke ASR system tailored to our specific needs?

Alignment with print news. Is the potential improvement from integrating print news with the parliamentary recordings substantial enough to justify the effort involved?

In addition to these technological questions, we consider the question of how much effort will be involved in obtaining human transcriptions for a human-in-the-loop approach.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/KBLab/wav2vec2-large-voxr-ex-swedish>

Data acquisition

Our data is drawn from the proceedings of the Swedish parliament (Riksdag) over an almost 10-year period, from September 2012 to January 2022. The public API was queried for items containing video, and the API results for each video was stored. The API response contains metadata, such as the date of the session, the URI of the video, and, in many cases, broadly timed information about individual speeches within the session, containing the name of the speaker, their political party, and a transcript of the speech.

A further decade of material is available through the API, recorded under similar conditions, which we have also downloaded but have not yet processed. Recordings are available for an earlier 50 years of debates, albeit with decreasing amounts of accompanying text. This material, which is not available through the API, is currently being collected with the help of Riksdagen and the Swedish National Library and prepared for use in our continued work.

The downloaded data produced by the Swedish parliament in the last decade alone amount to 5 925 hours of video recordings: manually transcribing this is infeasible. (Partial) transcripts are sometimes available, but of the 9 372 video files in our data, 2 864 came without any transcription at all.

Automatic transcription

The videos were automatically transcribed using both Whisper and VoxRex. Whisper, for all its merits, has drawbacks, likely due to the use of YouTube subtitles in training. In one sample file, which began with 5 minutes of silence, it repeatedly output the phrase “Tack till mina supporters via www.patreon.com” (“Thanks to my supporters via www.patreon.com”); and

while Whisper was, in at least one case, able to override the language setting for a video in English, in at least one other case, it translated the English audio to Swedish—an impressive feat, as it was only directly trained to translate *to* English.

The texts were aligned using scripts based on those used in the creation of Librispeech (Panayotov et al., 2015), adapted to operate on the Riksdag API. This will form part of a pipeline for continuous processing of new videos as they are made available through the API, and the source code² is available under the Apache Public License.

Two separate sets of alignments were computed: one based on the output of VoxRex and the official transcripts, one based on the intersection of both ASR systems. We also realigned the output of VoxRex and the official transcripts, by first passing the transcripts through a text normalisation system: we ran a new ASR pass employing biased 3-gram language models derived from the normalised text and aligned it to the normalised text.

For word-level timings, the output of VoxRex was used in both cases. Word-level timings are important both for further processing the data, and for the ability to search the data itself. We want researchers to have access not merely to the fact that a word was spoken, but also to how it was spoken, which necessitates access to the actual speech. Timings from Whisper were disregarded, as the prediction model Whisper uses to estimate timings results in unpredictable granularity (some files have timings with sub-second timings, others whole seconds only), and utterance (sentence) level timings only.

Test and validation sets

For testing and validation, a set of speakers were selected at random, balanced for gender: 8 men and women

² <https://github.com/jimregan/sync-asr>

for each set. Two continuous segments of speech lasting no less than two minutes was selected for each speaker.

The segments were professionally transcribed independently by three transcribers. The first transcriber prepared two sets of transcriptions, for both two-minute segments, while the other transcribers prepared only the first set of segments.

In addition to the text transcription, these subsets are additionally annotated with markings to represent other acoustic events—such as lip smacks, breaths, and coughs—with false starts and other partially articulated words transcribed to the extent possible and marked. No express guidelines were given regarding numbers: all three annotators elected to spell out some, while using digits for others.

As part of the transcription process, a record was kept of the amount of time spent on each annotation. The times are summarised in Table 1; the average time per minute of recorded audio, taking transcription and quality assurance into account, is 9.27 minutes—roughly 10 times real time.

The test and validation sets were not designed for ASR as it is commonly understood and have phonetically-motivated transcriptions for some high frequency Swedish words that better reflect their quickly spoken pronunciations. Word Error Rate (WER) calculated on the outputs of conventional ASR systems—all of those mentioned in this work—can be expected to incur a penalty of up to 3.62, but as this can be expected to affect all systems equally, we have not attempted to adjust for it, although the vast majority of adjustments required consists of removing high-granularity information and could reliably be done automatically.

Table 1: Times spent by annotator on transcription and quality control of approx. 32 minutes of audio (64 in the case of A1). All times given in minutes.

ID	Transcription	Quality assurance
A1	532	95
A2	202	42
A3	264	52

Text normalisation

Text normalisation was performed using NVIDIA's NeMo text processing library (Zhang et al., 2021), to which we contributed support for Swedish. The system is based on (Ebden & Sproat, 2014).

Training

Hyperparameters were kept across all training instances as our concern was the effect of data selection on model quality.

Fine-tuning was performed using 8 NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPUs, and took approximately 5.8 hours to reach 12 000 steps. The models were allowed to continue further, but none improved WER beyond that point.

The base model used was the KB-wav2vec model described in Malmsten et al., (2022)—the same base model as VoxRex—which the authors kindly shared. This model is pretrained on 10 000 hours of Swedish, selected to represent a broad range of accents.

The base model was fine-tuned by adding a layer on top of the model, trained to classify into the characters of the Swedish alphabet along with two punctuation characters necessary for orthographic conventions, and a space character. The classifier was trained using Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) loss (Graves et al., 2006). Fine tuning was performed using the `fairseq` toolkit.

All resulting models have been made available via the Huggingface hub, where full training metrics can be viewed. The configuration file for each model is included in the repository.

Results

The results of our experiments are summarised in Table 2, along with results from state-of-the-art systems, for comparison.

VoxRex outperforms our models by quite a margin—this is unsurprising, as theirs was fine-tuned on a larger dataset that was constructed to be phonetically diverse, with a range of dialects.

The most surprising result is that doubling the size of the training data for the system using the intersection of two ASR systems did not have any effect. This may be explained by the intersection being the lowest common denominator of two systems. We have 1 186 hours in total of similar data: the increase in the scale of the data may be enough by itself to boost the performance of the system.

The relative increase gained by matching ASR output with the official transcript suggests that the intersection of the ASR systems included common errors. The VoxRex model already produces high-quality output, and the mismatches are quite often due to divergences from the official transcript.

The relatively small improvement from adding a biased language model and normalisation is not disheartening, as the text normalisation system we used is intended for more generic use, while parliamentary texts contain some very specific items, such as legal code references, that require extra support. It is worth considering that the size of the training data for this model was slightly less than half that of the others; the slight improvement did not seem worth it by itself to justify processing more data, but moving to a more flexible system that can produce more than a single possible normalisation does seem worthwhile.

Table 2: WER results

Model	WER
Whisper small	25.47
Whisper large v2	14.38
VoxRex	12.87
100h, whisper + wav2vec ³	16.38
200h, whisper + wav2vec ⁴	16.38
100h, wav2vec/transcripts, no LM ⁵	14.44
49h, wav2vec/transcripts, LM, norm ⁶	13.98

Discussion

Because of the requirement of contiguous segments, the test and validation sets overwhelmingly contain audio that commences at the start of a speech: they typically begin with a phrase like “tack herr/fru talman” (“thanks mister/madam speaker”). The words “herr” and “fru” are relatively uncommon in modern Swedish, and are typically misrecognised by both VoxRex and Whisper: VoxRex, because of their similarity in pronunciation to other, more common words; Whisper, because it typically omits them: many of the speeches appear with subtitles on the Riksdag Youtube channel, and follow transcription conventions, which include starting all speeches with “Talman!”, no matter what was actually spoken.

A factor in favour of our 49-hour model is the use of text normalisation: although only one possible representation was generated, it was risk-free, as the string of digits would not otherwise have matched the output of VoxRex. We have extended our work on normalisation to the audio-based normalisation described by Bakhturina et al., (2022), which allows multiple possible outputs to be generated before being filtered by the acoustic evidence, but it was not completed in time to be used in this work.

The output of this audio-based normalisation can also be used as a

³ <https://huggingface.co/jimregan/wav2vec2-swedish-riksdag-100h>

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/jimregan/wav2vec2-swedish-riksdag-200h>

⁵ <https://huggingface.co/jimregan/wav2vec2-swedish-riksdag-100h-transcripts-nolm>

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/jimregan/wav2vec2-swedish-riksdag-49h-transcripts-lm>

means of automatically creating a relatively reliable corpus, for use with more current neural network-based methods of text normalisation (Sproat & Jaitly, 2017), as there currently does not exist any suitable corpus for Swedish (Tännander & Edlund, 2022).

Conclusions

We have examined the creation of custom ASR systems for transcribing archival data to support speech-centric research in various fields. Due to its availability, as well as the availability of partial transcripts, we concentrated on parliamentary data, and assessed the viability of using the intersection of outputs from two ASR systems as training data. While the current attempt does not surpass state-of-the-art performance, it comes close, so we view these results as promising although further refinement is required.

Acknowledgements

The work presented is funded by Riksbankens Jubileumsfond (In19-0144:1_RJ) and the Swedish Research Council (2020-05052_VR). The results will be made more widely available through the Swedish research infrastructure Språkbanken (2023-00161_VR).

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Why only a “great” primate discovered speech: A progress report on evolving vocal repertoires

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Abstract

There are hundreds of extant species of primate. Is it a coincidence that the only known species to develop fluid speech was part of the species-poor primate clade characterized by substantially greater relative body size? In this position paper, we discuss pertinent evidence from four species of American monkey, seven species of Afroeurasian monkey, and multiple species of ape including all extant great ape genera. The evidence indicates that a propensity to utilize distinctive formant dispersions (“vowel-like” qualities) is facilitated by vocal tract length. Smaller primates appear to make greater widespread use of source variations, constrained from effective communicative use of formants by their relatively short vocal tracts and small vocal folds (facilitating high- f_0 signals). Exceptions to these apparent trends are discussed. This work

highlights the roles of anatomy in shaping species’ vocalizations and vocal behavior and explores several emerging trends of relevance for the evolution of primate call repertoires.

Introduction

This work is a contribution toward the Symposium celebrating the contributions to speech science of Professor Björn Lindblom on his 90th birthday, held at the annual *Fonetik* Congress in Stockholm, Sweden. Lindblom’s (1984, 1990 2000) contributions to an evolutionary science of human speech are part of a small but rich literature on human spoken language and communication as an emergent property (e.g., Carré et al., 1995; Studdert-Kennedy, 2005; Ekström & Edlund, 2023). In his 2017 InterSpeech keynote lecture¹, Lindblom explored why humans “gave up” being like the other apes. Here, we explore a

¹ [youtube.com/watch?v=k1j5wRb4cF0](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k1j5wRb4cF0)

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Table 1. Species studied as of May 2024.

Platyrrhines	Black howler monkey Geoffroy's spider monkey Black-capped squirrel monkey Common marmoset
Catarrhines	Vervet monkey Lesser spot-nosed monkey Sooty mangabey Diana monkey Thomas' langur Guinea baboon
<i>Apes</i>	Gibbon* Siamang
<i>Great apes</i>	Bornean orangutan Western gorilla Western chimpanzee Bonobo

*Several species sampled.

similar theoretical issue, asking why, out of all the hundreds of species of primates, the only species to evolve speech, came from a narrow selection of larger bodied taxa. This work combines observations of vocalization data from four species of American monkeys – howler monkeys (*Alouatta pigra*) (Briseño-Jaramillo et al., 2017), spider monkeys (*Ateles geoffroyi*) (Briseño-Jaramillo et al., 2018), Bolivian squirrel monkeys (*Saimiri boliviensis boliviensis*), and common marmosets (*Callithrix jacchus*) – seven species of Old World monkey – including vervet monkeys (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) (Deshpande et al., 2023), lesser spot-nosed monkeys (*Cercopithecus pataurista*) (Le Floch et al., 2021), sooty mangabeys (*Cercocebus atys*), Diana monkeys (*Cercopithecus diana*) (Zuberbühler, 2000), Thomas' langurs (*Presbytis thomasi*) (Wich et al., 2003)

and Guinea baboons (*Papio papio*) (Fischer et al., 2002) – as well as apes, including gibbons (*Hylobates .spp*) and siamangs (*Symphalangus syndactylus*), Bornean orangutans (*Pongo pygmaeus*) (Lameira & Wich, 2008; Ekström et al., 2023), Western gorillas (*Gorilla gorilla*) (Salmi et al., 2014) and Western chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*) (Grawunder et al., 2022). We outline two main directions and schools of thought that have emerged through this series of comparisons, which will be explored further in subsequent research.

Trends in smaller primates

Chucks, whinnies, and whoops

Across descriptions of primate vocal repertoires, onomatopoeic naming conventions are widespread. For smaller primates, names assigned to species' calls – from the “chucks” of squirrel monkeys, “tcha-kow” calls of lesser spot-nosed monkeys, and the “whinnies” of spider monkeys – often evidently correspond to distinct fundamental frequency variations. The would-be consonant-to-vowel distinction in a “chuck”, for example, corresponds to a significant drop from high-frequency phonation or noise (the “ch”) to a relatively lower frequency threshold (the “uck”). Such naming conventions stand in contrast with names assigned to calls by larger primates like baboon “wahoo”, and chimpanzee “hoots”, which are named for their apparent and distinct vowel-like qualities, verifiable through spectrographic analysis (Salmi et al., 2014; Boë et al., 2017; Grawunder et al., 2022; Ekström et al., 2023, 2024a).

Acoustics of short vocal tracts

It is a fact of physics that shorter vocal tracts will produce higher resonant frequencies; is this a meaningful determinant of speech-like behavior in primates? In a series of in-prep speech acoustics computer simulation works, we have investigated the impact on

vowel quality of increasingly limiting vocal tract lengths. By scaling vocal tracts down but maintaining vocal tract proportions, we can investigate speech signals corresponding to a hypothetical “small” speaker. These simulations suggest that length of the vocal tract (and therefore the animal) may be a determinant as to whether an animal develops a “spectral peak-based” vocal repertoire (i.e., one where formant-like patterns distinguish some or all contrasting vocal signals). When vocal tract lengths are shorter, even highly distinct formant dispersions, such as those observed for close front unrounded vowel [i], become markedly more difficult to distinguish, owing to higher formants being shifted up and toward the higher end of the spectrum of human perceivability (Table 2). For short vocal tracts, the lowest formant frequency (F1) may be the greatest determinant of vowel quality. Speech, as spoken by all normally developing humans, requires a long enough vocal tract.

Trends in larger primates: Vowel quality and vowel-like quality

Vowel quality is traditionally reducible to the constellation of the first and second formants (F2), where F1 roughly corresponds to jaw height and degree of stricture, and F2 corresponds to the position of the stricture (Fant, 1960). The third formant (F3) is traditionally said to correspond to the degree of mouth closure. These assumptions, while simplistic, allow for fairly reliable inference of vocal tract dynamics underlying speech behavior in real time, even from acoustic data alone. However, reflecting the comparative shapes of nonhuman vocal tracts (Negus, 1949; Harrison, 1995), these assumptions cannot be extended to primates a priori. Formant data has been reported for baboons (Fischer et al., 2002; Boë et al., 2017), orangutans (Ekström et al., 2023), gorillas (Ekström et al., 2024a),

and chimpanzees (Grawunder et al., 2022). In chimpanzees, these support consonant-vowel spectrographic patterns (Ekström et al., 2024b). There are also indications of similar speech-like properties in vocalizations by howler monkeys (Schön Ybarra, 1986) - a markedly smaller primate (relative to great apes) and American monkey. These studies have, however, been performed with formants averaged over a window of time: reported data are effectively snapshots, which cannot be used to infer vocal tract dynamics per se. To what extent do these “vowel-like” vocalizations reflect human-like production?

Exceptions to the trends?

A highly derived anatomy

We do not mean to suggest the tendencies discussed above are universal or without exceptions. With regard to relatively “small” primates, for example, the vocal anatomy of the *Alouatta* genus is likely one of the most derived in nature (Figure 1), likely reflecting a unique eco-behavioral strategy (Dunn et al., 2015; Youlatos et al., 2015). Effectively, the presence of additional resonant frequencies at relatively low

Table 2. Formants for [i], scaled to the average adult female VTL, and to VTL = 8 cm. Scaled linearly. Original values (17 cm) for Swedish male speakers from Fant (1959). Maintaining consistent vocal tract proportions, shorter vocal tracts will produce formants increasingly beyond the optimal window for perception, and their contribution to vowel quality becomes increasingly small.

VTL	F1	F2	F3
8	574	4866	6396
14	328	2780	3655
17	270	2290	3010

thresholds induces a “vowel-like” quality in a manner distinct from that of other primates (large or otherwise). Howlers have achieved this vocal repertoire via the evolution of a highly specialized hyolaryngeal complex, typified by a hypertrophied hyoid bulla, that is theorized to act as a resonating chamber which aids the production of their ~90 dB vocalizations. The divergence in aerodigestive tract anatomy from the apes, which exhibit larger body mass and utilize soft-tissue air sacs to aid in vocalization, demonstrates a possible case of parallel evolution towards the ability to produce “vowel-like” vocalizations. The howler monkeys’ case underscores vocal anatomy’s relevance to the evolution of vocal production strategies.

Figure 1. Bisected Howler monkey (*Alouatta seniculus*) vocal tract. The prominent species-typical hyoid bulla is visible inferior to the mandible. The scale bar is 1 cm. Photo credit: B. Shearer.

High-frequency calls in a large primate

Bonobos are great apes of the *Pan* genus. Their vocal repertoire is mainly composed of relatively high-frequency calls (Hohmann & Fruth, 1994): there is no reported instance of any bonobo producing a call overlapping in vowel-like quality to that of, for example, orangutan long calls (Ekström et al., 2023). Bonobos possess specialized vocal fold anatomy, including markedly

shortened vocal folds (Grawunder et al., 2018). Rather than a counterexample, the case of bonobos likely provides another example of systems of vocalizations reflecting complex combinations of selection pressures.

Discussion

The vocal tracts of subadult and adult chimpanzees overlap in length with those of humans (Nishimura, 2005); while those of adult baboons overlap with human preteens (Boë et al., 2017). Both allow for a range of vowel-like qualities (Boë et al., 2017; Berthommier, 2020; Grawunder et al., 2022). Here, a necessary distinction must be made. Namely, Boë et al. (2017) interpret the argument that the reconfiguration of the hominin vocal tract (involving a marked expansion of the pharynx and descent of the tongue root) expanded the phonetic potential of human ancestors to mean that all speech would be impossible without it (Boë et al., 2017). This interpretation is refuted in Ekström (2024a).

In reality, limitations on primate phonetic potential are not seriously disputed by any speech-centric work (Ekström, 2024b) and become more untenable still in light of speech biomechanics (Takemoto, 2008; Iwasaki et al., 2019; Ekström & Edlund, 2023). Analyses of primate lingual biomechanics (Takemoto, 2001, 2008) demonstrate that “flat” primate tongues (Negus, 1949) possess disparate degrees of freedom, meaning that any fluid speech capacity available to primates would be markedly different from that of humans. Literature on the evolution of speech has concentrated on a hypothetical conflict between “anatomical” and “neural” evolution (Lieberman et al., 1972; Fitch et al., 2016). Accumulated evidence shows that neither sufficiently explains the differences between primate communication systems and human spoken language (Berthommier, 2020;

Ekström, 2024b). It is imperative that we move toward an evolutionarily coherent model.

There are several hundreds of extant species of primate - an order characterized by relatively large brains relative to body size, a pronounced selection pressure for visual acuity, and group social complexity. The vocalizations of primates are highly diverse, and human spoken language constitutes a particularly remarkable example. We have expounded on a range of observations from primate vocal behavior, with two main takeaways.

First, there are likely ecological, social, and morphological underpinnings that determine the evolution of primate vocal repertoires, which may be studied with reference to comparative acoustic data. Second, one such principle underlying the structural and acoustic bias of human speech communication was likely permissible through the size of our ancestors. The characteristics of human speech were unlikely to evolve in a small primate. Lindblom's (1984, 2000) contributions to speech-centric science explore the foundational principles by which speech behaviors emerge. Here, we have sought to outline avenues for future research by which we hope to and understand the organizing principles structuring the development of primate vocal repertoires.

Acknowledgments

The results of this work and the tools used will be made more widely accessible through the national infrastructure Språkbanken Tal under funding from the Swedish Research Council (2017–00626). SM and DF were funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (PCEFP1_186841).

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Vocal tract proportions and the evolution of speech: New data to answer old questions

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Abstract

In evolutionary phonetics research, important distinctions between humans and human ancestors are contingent on observations that modern humans possess “roughly 1:1” proportions between horizontal and vertical vocal tract sections. However, few descriptions of diverse adult speaker samples exist. We measured horizontal distance between the anterior-most point of the lower lip and the posterior wall of the pharynx, and vertical distance between staphylion and the superior margin of the posterior lamina of the cricoid cartilage. Our results show that proportions exhibit moderate variation between speakers. We discuss these findings in the context of the purported speech capacities of human ancestors.

Introduction

Modern humans are born with “monkey-like” vocal tracts. That is, children are born with flat tongues contained almost wholly in the oral cavity, high larynges and narrow pharynges (Crelin, 1973; Bosma, 1975; Kent, 1981; Kent & Vorperian, 1995) – a set of vocal tract features that closely resemble those of extant non-human primates (Negus, 1949; Lieberman et al., 1969, 1972,

1992; Nishimura, 2005; Takemoto, 2008). In comparison, the development of the adult human vocal tract is characterized by a suite of morphological changes from infancy to adulthood, including descent of the larynx and hyoid, and partial descent of the tongue root into the pharynx, with the vocal tract bending at its midpoint to form a right angle in the nasopharyngeal region. The “adult” vocal tract is attained only throughout the course of maturation, around the ages of 6-8 (Lieberman & McCarthy, 1999; Fitch & Giedd, 1999; Lieberman et al., 2001; Vorperian et al., 2005, 2009).

Literature on the evolution of speech capacities in the human lineage, beginning as early as Victor Negus’ (1949) writings on the comparative anatomy of the airways. Negus hypothesized that the uniquely human vocal tract configuration reflected an evolutionary selection pressure for improved speech communication. Yet, this anatomy contributes to an elevated risk of choking (as food may get lodged in the trachea). Thus, the positive benefits of the human vocal tract configuration must have offset the negative effect of the increased risk of choking, implying that the human condition represents an evolutionary

tradeoff (Negus, 1949; Lieberman, 2012, 2017; Ekström, 2024). In this view, the human vocal tract became differentiated from that of its closest extant relatives “... for purposes of speech” (Negus, 1949, p. 198). Would-be benefits to speech production include attaining “optimal” configurations for the full range of speech sounds (Carré et al., 1995, 2017; de Boer, 2010a, 2010b; but see Badin et al., 2014), and in the view of Lieberman (Lieberman et al., 1972; Lieberman, 2012) facilitating the production of “quantal” vowels (Stevens, 1972, 1989) and the robustness of consonant distinctions (Lieberman et al., 1967; Lieberman et al., 1992). Vocal tract reconfiguration would also have resulted in an increased ability to readily close off the velum, facilitating non-nasalized phonemic contrasts (e.g., Lieberman, 1991).

In light of this line of argument, it is surprising that while extensive investigations have sought to uncover mechanisms of maturation *per se*, and the developmental trajectories of a variety of vocal tract structures (Crelin, 1973; Bosma, 1975; Lieberman & McCarthy, 1999; Fitch & Giedd, 1999; Lieberman et al., 2001; Vorperian et al., 2005, 2009), there are few descriptions of the variation of inter-structure relationships in diverse samples of adult speakers. Specifically, providing descriptions of variations of such measurements is necessary to either support, refute, or nuance central tenets of the dominant model of the evolution of speech anatomy (Lieberman, 2012; Ekström, 2024). Here, we provide such a description.

Methods

Vocal tract data

We measured horizontal and vertical supralaryngeal vocal tract lengths (SVT_H , SVT_V) and proportions from the University from the Southern California Speech and Vocal Tract Morphology MRI Database (Sorensen et al., 2017; Lim et al.,

2021). The dataset contains real-time magnetic resonance images (rtMRI) of vocal tract shapes observed during read and spontaneous speech from a diverse speaker sample ($N=75$, 40 females). The speaker sample was aged 18-59 years of age. The sample consists of 49 native and 26 non-native American English speakers (29 females). We used data from neutral/resting positions, in order to avoid any distortion from real-time speech.

Figure 1. SVT_H and SVT_V were measured linearly.

Measurement procedure

SVT_H was measured as the horizontal distance between the anteriormost point on the lower lip and the posterior wall of the pharynx (composed primarily of the constrictor muscles). SVT_V was measured as vertical distance between staphylion (the posteriormost point of the hard palate, typically discernable as the convergence of the void related to cortical bone, the opaque cancellous bone within the palate, and the superior border of the soft palate) and the superior margin of the posterior lamina of the cricoid cartilage (often, although not always, discernable as a slender vertically oriented oval anterior to the vertebral column; the vocal ligament arises from the vocal process of the arytenoid cartilages that sit above the posterior lamina, so this point approximates the superiormost portion of the vocal ligament, see Figure 1).

Results

Of the 75 available subjects, 55 (27 females) were acceptable for our study. Images from the rest were either deemed too poor in quality or had the subject in (qualitatively) highly flexed or highly extended neck postures. Our measurements are likely affected by subjects being in a supine position while the rtMRI data was collected. Our results showed a moderate degree of inter-subject variation with regard to SVT_H - SVT_V proportions. We also observed a significant sex difference between male and female speakers (t-test, $p = 0.002$), with male proportions falling closer to the 1:1 ratio (see Figure 2, Table 1).

Figure 1. Boxplot of SVT_H - SVT_V ratio for male and female subjects.

Table 1. Summary of SVT_H - SVT_V ratio observed in our sample.

	SVT_H - SVT_V		
	All ($N=55$)	Male ($N=28$)	Female ($N=27$)
<i>Avg.</i>	1.05	1.00	1.10
<i>St.Dev</i>	.12	.12	0.12
<i>Min.</i>	0.79	0.79	0.82
<i>Max.</i>	1.24	1.19	1.24

Discussion

Vocal tracts of extinct hominins

The oft-purported benefits of “roughly equal” vocal tract proportions have long been a staple of research on the evolution of speech (Lieberman, 1991, 2012; Carré et al., 1995; de Boer, 2010a, 2010b; Badin et al., 2014). In particular, Neanderthal phonetic capacities

estimated by Lieberman and colleagues – the first modern efforts to attempt a quantification (see overview in Ekström & Moran, 2024) – concluded that the species would have been limited from the extent of fully modern human speech. Lieberman and colleagues argued that the different proportions restricted the ability to create “abrupt mid-point discontinuities” – argued to be necessary to articulate the extreme “quantal” vowels. According to these estimates, and due to a relatively long face and short neck, Neanderthal vocal tracts would have been precluded from vowels [a], [i], and [u], but included [ɪ], [æ], and [ɛ]. While the empirical bases of these estimates (i.e., the assumption that the angle of the basicranium provides reliable information about the shape of vocal tracts) have been refuted (Lieberman & McCarthy, 1999; Fitch & Giedd, 1999), later estimates have effectively reinforced the conclusions of these original efforts. Estimates by McCarthy (reported in Lieberman, 2007) and Barney and colleagues (2012) have both indicated a relatively limited phonetic potential in Neanderthals. On the other hand, Badin et al. (2014) have argued these objections may be overstated. Our data have potential implications for this line of research.

Why proportions matter

The influence on phonetic output resulting from variations in vocal tract anatomy is a topic of substantial interest in speech-centric sciences (Simpson, 2002). For example, Johnson and colleagues (1993) considered consequences resulting from degrees of palatal doming (higher in males); more significant doming effectively results in a greater physical space that must be traversed in order to execute a given phonemic transition that involves that space. More pertinent to our data, de Boer (2010a, p. 351), in modeling the influence of various laryngeal heights found that “there is an optimal larynx height at which the largest

range of signals can be produced and that at this height, the vertical and horizontal parts are approximately equally long.” Because sex differences (relatively longer pharynges in males due to a second process of laryngeal descent) emerge during puberty, de Boer (2010) argued that the apparent phonetic efficiency bestowed by a SVT_H - SVT_V configuration which “corresponds closely to human female anatomy”, was offset in males for the purpose of “size exaggeration.” The format of the present text does not allow for an in-depth review of relevant literature on the influence of variations in vocal tract anatomy on phonetic output; it should be mentioned, however, that Badin et al. (2014) have challenged de Boer’s model (but not the results presented by Carré et al., 1995, 2017). Nevertheless, in a broad sense, the influence of vocal tract proportions is likely meaningful. However, works on the phonetic capacities of extinct hominins suffer from an apparent weakness, which must, in light of presently presented data, be adequately addressed.

Toward evolutionary biomechanics

The early estimates by Lieberman and colleagues (1972, p. 297) suggested that [u] was “virtually impossible for the chimpanzee to articulate.” Allegedly, this was due to anatomy which prevented “the tongue body motion found in man.” Vocal tract proportions in extant primates is indeed drastically disparate from those observed in humans, and those inferred for extinct hominins; for example, the adult chimpanzee possess an SVT_H more than twice the length of tits SVT_V (Nishimura, 2005). Nevertheless, recent works on the phonetic aspects of great ape call repertoires have documented [u]-like calls, overlapping almost perfectly with vowel formants typically estimated for [u] (Grawunder et al., 2022; Ekström et al., 2023). The articulatory configurations underlying these vowel-like formant dispersions are as of yet unknown. Nonetheless, this

evidence suggests that (some) extremes of human vowel space can be achieved by extant non-human great apes by executing different vocal tract configurations than speaking humans (Ekström, 2024a). Moving forward, it will be necessary to recognize that counter to a long-running tradition in “evolutionary phonetics” sciences (overview in Ekström, 2024b), phonetic capacities are not reasonably estimated from isolated vowel production capacities alone. Realistic articulatory modeling will be necessary to determine biomechanics of how vowel tract proportions unlike those of modern humans may (or may not) execute sequences of speech sounds. Toward this end, detailed descriptions of variability in vocal tract anatomy are a pertinent line of evidence.

Acknowledgements

We thank the DFG Center for Advanced Studies “Words, Bones, Genes, Tools: Tracking Linguistic, Cultural and Biological Trajectories of the Human Past”. Special thanks to Tiena Danner. SM and DF were funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF; PCEFP1_186841) and DF by the NCCR Evolving Language (SNF: 51NF40_18088). The results of this work and the tools used will be made more widely accessible through the national infrastructure Språkbanken Tal under funding from the Swedish Research Council (2017–00626).

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Apical [u] (and other impractical articulations)

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Abstract

The human vocal tract allows compensatory articulation, maintaining phonetic target consistency even in abnormal conditions, such as fitted with bite blocks (Gay et al., 1981) or exposed to perturbed auditory (MacDonald et al., 2010; Mitsuya et al., 2011) and somatosensory feedback (Houde & Jordan, 1998; Katseff et al., 2012). While speakers can compensate for many circumstances, the resulting alternative articulatory configurations may carry a higher cost in terms of effort. As an example extraordinary, we explore the apical production of /u/, in which the tip of the tongue is curved back towards velum to create a constriction somewhat similar to that of a typical /u/. We conducted a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) single-subject case study at the Stockholm University Brain Imaging Center (SUBIC). The scanner was a Siemens Prisma 3 Tesla whole-body MRI. Data collection used the “FLASH” sequence - a spoiled gradient echo with a flip angle of 5 degrees, an echo time of 1.7 ms, and a repetition time of 4 ms. The field of view was 280(freq) x 278(phase) mm, with a resolution of 224(freq) x 156(phase) and a bandwidth = 500 Hz/px. The subject was a single adult male aged 28 at the time of recording. The speaker produced /u/ and “apical /u/” as sustained phonation, and as VCV and VCVCV sequences for /p l n t k/. Each form was uttered ten times as /u/, and subsequently ten times as “apical /u/”. In producing “apical /u/”, our speaker was able to maintain vowel quality and formant characteristics typical of /u/. Coarticulatory potential was highly variable, being mostly unaffected for /p/, but highly destructive to intelligibility for /n/ and /l/ - both of which typically involve the tongue tip or blade and are not straightforwardly compensated for by the dorsum. /t/ and /k/ were reasonably compensated for through movements of the dorsum and tongue root, mostly maintaining auditory equivalence.

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The Emergence of Stability in Infant Vocal Production: A Model Based on Acoustic Analysis

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Abstract

Repeated babble production during early vocal development lays the groundwork for incipient motor control and creates stable motor-sensory mappings readily available for speech production. Investigation of this emergence of motor stabilisation has so far relied primarily on phonetic transcription and has therefore been unable to quantify continuous variability in speech production. In this longitudinal study, we leverage acoustic analysis to investigate how spectral centroids in the release phase of 5634 plosives change in 28 infants between the ages of 9 and 18 months. Modelling developmental change in hierarchical Bayesian location-scale models, we find a reliable non-linear increase followed by a gradual decrease in production variability. We argue that this U-shaped developmental trajectory reflects a point of transition, with exploration and subsequent consolidation of new vocal behaviours.

Introduction

Babble is a rhythmic vocal behaviour that emerges at around the same time as rhythmic stereotypies in other motor areas (Kent, 1984; Thelen, 1981) in both humans and non-human animals (Davis & MacNeilage, 2000; Lindblom, 2000; Leitão & Gahr, 2024), regardless of ambient language or amount of input (Peute & Casillas, 2022). Between the emergence of consonant-vowel syllables in babble (6-8 months: Oller, 2000) and first word production (typically about 3-

5 months later: Fagan, 2009), infants' vocalisations tend to settle on two or more well-practised vocal routines that remain frequent and stable across longitudinal observations (McCune & Vihman, 2001). The emergence of these 'vocal motor schemes' constitutes a pivotal moment in vocal development because it allows infants to discover and explore sensory-motor associations (Vihman et al., 2014) and supports retention of word forms (Keren-Portnoy et al., 2010; Vihman, 2022). Experimental and observational work has shown that a child's individual production experience exerts an influence on their attention to sounds in the speech stream (DePaolis et al., 2011, 2013; Majorano et al., 2014; Laing & Bergelson, 2020; Vilain et al., 2019) and creates individual trajectories of downstream development in babble and word production (McCune & Vihman, 2001; Keren-Portnoy et al., 2010). Children thus play an active role in shaping their own vocal development (Elmlinger et al., 2019, 2023; Goldstein & Schwade, 2008; Laing & Bergelson, 2020). Longitudinal studies of continuous change in infants' production patterns hold the potential to improve our understanding of variability in these individual developmental trajectories.

Aims of the current study

The identification of the emergence of vocal motor schemes are typically based on phonetic transcriptions (McCune & Vihman, 2001). Children, however, often produce speech sounds that fall between traditional target sounds (Kent &

Murray, 1982; Frisch & Wright, 2002) and exhibit more protracted production variability when assessed by acoustic analysis than by transcription alone (Lee et al., 1999; Munson, 2004). In the following analyses, we leverage acoustic analysis to measure continuous change in children's speech production and explore the following questions:

- i. What are the developmental trajectories of production variability at each place of articulation as the infant starts to stabilise their motor routines?
- ii. How do these trajectories relate to transcription-based time points of vocal motor scheme attainment?

Material and methods

Participants

The speech recordings for this study consisted of vocalisations from 28 infants recorded every two weeks between the ages of 9 and 18 months. All vocalisations were transcribed, and each child was coded for vocal motor schemes from these transcribed records according to the following two criteria from previous studies (McCune & Vihman, 2001; DePaolis et al., 2011; Majorano et al., 2014). A consonant:

- i. is produced at least 10 times in each of three out of four successive sessions, or
- ii. occurs 50 times within one to three sessions.

These criteria attempt to capture the consistency and frequency that characterise the individual production experience of each child (McCune & Vihman, 2001). To observe how acoustic variability develops around the point of VMS attainment in this study, we converted the time point of vocal motor scheme attainment for each infant to a continuous predictor by computing the number of days from vocal motor scheme attainment for each child. We used days from *second* vocal

motor scheme attainment in the following analyses, as this marks the onset of emergent vocal control and phonological systematicity (McCune & Vihman, 2001).

Acoustic analysis

The onset and offset of each burst in the 5634 plosives (1788 bilabial, 2709 coronal, 1137 dorsal) were manually marked with boundaries in Praat (Boersma and Weenink, 2013). Recordings were resampled at 16 kHz, pre-emphasized above 1000 Hz, and high-pass filtered at 200 Hz to reduce the influence of low-frequency glottal vibration (Forrest et al., 1988). For each burst, a smoothed spectrum was calculated by averaging the squared amplitude values of seven 64-point FFT spectra taken from 3ms Hamming windows. As our primary measure, we calculated the power-weighted average frequency of the spectrum (i.e., centre of gravity, or spectral centroid). The centroid at plosive release depends on the cavities surrounding the point of constriction; for example, we would expect dorsal plosives to exhibit a lower spectral centroid than coronal plosives because the cavity in front of the dorsal release is larger and has a lower resonant frequency (Chodroff & Wilson, 2014).

Statistical Models

Hierarchical Bayesian location-scale models were fitted to the acoustic data with weakly informative priors. To model how the location (centroid) and scale (variability) of the spectral centroids at each place of articulation change over developmental time for each participant, we allowed the intercepts and slopes for both the dependent variable and the sigma to vary for each participant. Because the three places of articulation (i.e., bilabial, coronal and dorsal) may exhibit different developmental trajectories, we estimated change in the sigma parameter for each of the three places of articulation and added

Figure 1: Panel of three plots of i) Posterior estimates of spectral centroids across bilabial, coronal, and dorsal plosives (top-left); ii) Estimates as a function of days from attainment of second vocal motor scheme (VMS) – 0 indicates the day each child attains their second VMS (bottom-left); iii) Posterior estimates for place of articulation of plosives before different vowel contexts (right).

a factor smooth spline term to capture potential non-linear changes in production variability.

All computations were performed in R 4.2.0 (R Core Team, 2020) using brms 2.16 (Bürkner, 2017) and cmdstanr 2.28.2 (Carpenter et al., 2017). We chose weakly informative priors in order to discount extreme values as unlikely and to ensure minimal influence on the posterior estimates of the model. In what follows, we provide estimates and report 95% credible intervals and evidence ratios. The credible interval refers to the range of values that have 95% probability of containing the true parameter value given the assumptions of the model. We report these intervals in square brackets. The evidence ratio denotes the ratio of likelihood in favour of a hypothesis. An evidence ratio of 10, then, implies that the hypothesis is 10 times more likely than the alternative. An evidence ratio of ‘Inf’ (infinite) occurs when all the posterior samples conform to the direction of the hypothesis and not to alternative directions.

Results

Spectral Centroids

The spectral centroid estimates exhibited differentiation according to place of articulation (bilabial: 1929.15 Hz [1880, 1977], coronal: 2603 Hz [2559, 2648], dorsal: 2384 Hz [2327, 2440]) (Figure 1, top-left) and showed no reliable changes with development (bilabial: -1.39 Hz [-122, 111], ER: 1.03; coronal: -26.26 Hz [-150, 101], ER: 1.91; dorsal: -48.15 Hz [-197, 103], ER: 2.76) (Figure 1, bottom-left). Fronter following vowels (Figure 1, right) made no changes to bilabial plosives (ER \approx 1), but raised spectral centroids for dorsal plosives (335 Hz [232, 435], ER: Inf) and lowered them for coronal plosives (-102 Hz [-189, -15], ER: 33).

Variability in Spectral Centroids

Production variability in the plosives showed a non-linear decrease over time (Figure 2, left). Coronal plosives exhibited more variability (796 Hz [757, 846]) than bilabial (659 Hz [626, 699])

Figure 2: Panel of two plots of i) Posterior estimates of the development of sigma (i.e., variability) across bilabial, coronal, and dorsal plosives where coloured faded lines represent individual child trajectories and orange faded area show 95% credible intervals (left); ii) Posterior estimates of the development of sigma for plosives before different vowel contexts where faded areas show 95% credible intervals (right).

or dorsal (679 Hz [633, 721]) plosives (ER: Inf). The time point of peak production variability was on average within 27 days of attainment of two vocal motor schemes; however, these vertices exhibited a high degree of variability across children and place of articulation (SD = 69 days). Bilabial plosives exhibited more variability before back vowels (706 Hz [626, 796], ER: Inf), and dorsal plosives showed more production variability before front vowels (679 Hz [602, 765], ER: 442) (Figure 2, right).

Discussion

By leveraging acoustic analysis to measure continuous change in infants' production of plosives, we showed that the spectral centroids exhibited clear differentiation as a function of the transcribed place of articulation, no reliable developmental changes, and robust effects of coarticulation with the following vowel (Figure 1). We also found evidence for non-linear patterns of development in variability across all three places of articulation; that is, an initial increase in production variability (especially in bilabial and coronal plosives) followed by a gradual decrease over time (Figure 2).

These findings indicate that infants can draw upon their babble experience to succeed in executing crude articulatory production targets (cf., Kent, 2022; McCune & Vihman, 2001). However, the integration of these articulatory movements into dynamic motor constellations remains characterised by a high degree of production variability, the peak of which falls shortly after the transcription-based point of attainment of the second vocal motor scheme (McCune & Vihman, 2001). The finding of peak variability around the time point of infants' attainment of their second vocal motor scheme accords with studies showing that variability is characteristic of the plasticity of an open system (Studdert-Kennedy, 1986), and that a reduction in variability often co-occurs with the stabilisation of adaptive motor behaviours (Piek, 2002; Thelen et al., 1987; Vihman, 1993). The tendency for infants to exhibit more production variability in bilabial plosives before back vowels and in dorsal plosives before front vowels may indicate that infants are still learning to control the dynamics of articulatory transitions, from various types of constrictions to more open configurations of the vocal tract (cf.

Lindblom, 2000). The above finding of a gradual decrease in production variability over time in parallel with no reliable change in the location of the spectral centroids indicates that with repeated practice and the gradual stabilisation of these sensorimotor routines over time, infants build up a repertoire of consistent phonetic output forms (Vihman, 1993; Ekström, 2022). This repertoire of motor constellations in turn leads to the formation of phonetic concepts in memory and shapes infants' attention to the speech input through the 'articulatory filter', which leads them to retain word forms that contain the sounds they can most easily reproduce (Vihman, 2022).

Conclusion

By investigating continuous change in the variability of infants' motor routines, this study adds to our understanding of how infants transition from the variable vocalisations they display early in life to the stable patterns needed for word production. The sudden increase and subsequent gradual decrease in variability among the plosives speak in favor of a production system in a period of transition. During this early stage of vocal development, the infant is learning to connect the phonetic gestures involved in speech with their corresponding acoustic patterns. The child's repeated use of these motor routines leads to the stabilisation of phonetic concepts in memory and reduction of production variability over time.

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Anatomical correlates of articulatory ranges of motion: An EMA study

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between anatomical features and articulatory ranges of motion in speech production using electromagnetic articulography (EMA) data. Utilizing canonical correlation analysis (CCA), we identified significant associations between anatomical dimensions – such as vocal tract length and mandible length – and the movements of the tongue, jaw, and lips. The results indicate that longer vocal tracts and mandibles are linked to greater vertical tongue movements but smaller vertical mandibular movements. Additionally, short mandible lengths are associated with extended horizontal lower lip movements, suggesting a form of biomechanical adaptation. Furthermore, the analysis revealed an association between the tongue's swallowing range and various articulatory variables. These findings highlight the role of anatomical structures in shaping articulatory patterns, offering insights into biomechanical constraints and adaptations in speech production.

Introduction

The study of how vocal tract anatomy influences speech production has garnered significant attention in the field of phonetics. Research suggests that individual anatomical variations, such as vocal tract length, palate shape, and

mandibular dimensions, are critical in shaping articulatory patterns (e.g., Johnson, 2023; Lammert, Proctor, & Narayanan, 2013; Simpson, 2001).

Variations in anatomy have been shown to constrain strategies for vowel and consonant production and could potentially even bias the realization of suprasegmental features. As early as the 1970s, Lindblom and Sundberg (1971) presented an articulatory model demonstrating the acoustical consequences of variations in lip, tongue, jaw, and larynx movements, underscoring the synergistic role of jaw position in vowel production. More recently, Brunner, Fuchs, and Perrier (2009) demonstrated that palate shape significantly influences articulatory behavior, leading to variations in tongue placement and movement. Specifically, they found that speakers with flat palates reduce their articulatory variability to maintain consistent acoustic output. Fuchs, Winkler, and Perrier (2008) explored how vocal tract geometry impacts vowel production strategies, finding that speakers with a longer pharynx produce larger displacements between low back and high front vowels. Honda, Maeda, Hashi, Dembowski, and Westbury (1996) and Winkler, Fuchs, Perrier, and Tiede (2011) examined the consequences of anatomical constraints on articulatory variability, showing that anatomical limitations can lead to distinct speech patterns among

individuals. Perkell, Matthies, Svirsky, and Jordan (1995) emphasized how goal-based speech motor control varies with anatomical differences, suggesting that speakers with different anatomical features adopt unique strategies to achieve phonetic targets. Weirich and Fuchs (2013) showed that palate morphology could affect the realization of phonemic contrasts, influencing how specific sounds are articulated and perceived. Most recently, Johnson (2023) found that speakers with larger vocal tracts exhibit greater vertical tongue motion during vowel production, whereas those with smaller vocal tracts show increased vertical jaw movement. These findings suggest a complex interaction between anatomical features and speech production mechanisms.

Our study utilizes electromagnetic articulography (EMA) to investigate how various anatomical dimensions affect articulatory dynamics. By correlating the vertical and horizontal ranges of tongue, lip, and jaw movements with anatomical features, we aim to elucidate the role of anatomical variation in shaping phonetic diversity and provide new insights into the biomechanical basis of speech production.

Methods

Participants

Fifteen native German speakers (7f, 8m) participated in this study. Participants were aged between 20 and 30 years (mean age: 23.57 years, SD = 2.98) and had no history of speech, hearing, or neurological disorders. All participants provided informed consent prior to their participation in the study.

Data Collection and Processing

Articulatory data were recorded at a sampling rate of 1250 Hz using a Carstens AG-501 EMA system. Sensors were attached midsagittally to various points, including the vermilion borders

of the upper and lower lips, upper and lower incisors, tongue dorsum, tongue body, and tongue tip. To determine the precise contact points for tongue sensor placement, we applied a line of ink midsagittally to the palate and asked participants to produce [t] and [k]. This resulted in contact points on the tongue tip for [t] and the tongue dorsum for [k]. The tongue body sensor was positioned midway between the [t] and [k] contact points. The sensors were then glued using Epiglu and Ketac cement. Reference sensors were placed on the bite plane for calibration and on the mastoid processes and nasion to correct for head movement. The raw EMA data were processed using Carstens' built-in Calcpos and Normpos applications and custom MATLAB scripts.

Speech Material

Participants produced a range of speech utterances, including trisyllabic nonsense words with balanced articulatory trajectories, e.g., [pi:ta:ku:], [ku:ta:pi:], [ta:ku:pi:], at comfortable ($N=180$) and maximally fast ($N=120$) production rates; minimal pairs containing all long German vowels ($N=16$), words with a schwa vowel in the final syllable ($N=6$); all long German vowels in isolation ($N=16$); and recordings of a read passage ("Nordwind und die Sonne") ($N=2$). Analyses were conducted on entire speech sequences rather than on annotated and labeled data, incorporating 500ms before and after the acoustic onsets and offsets to ensure the inclusion of full articulatory movements.

Anatomical Measurements

Table 1 shows the anatomical measurements analyzed for each participant. A digital caliper was used to measure distances between cephalometric landmarks on the jaw and mouth. Vocal tract length (VTL) was estimated using different acoustic-to-anatomical conversion techniques based

on formant frequencies (Lammert & Narayanan, 2015; Flego, 2018). A mean VTL from these estimates was calculated for each talker. Talkers were also recorded during tongue protrusion and swallowing trials. The maximum tongue protrusion and swallowing were quantified by calculating the Euclidean distance between the furthest points of movement for the tongue dorsum, body, and tip. The mean of these distances was then calculated to represent the overall measure for each talker.

Jaw	<p>Mandible Length: Distance between condyion (Co) and gnathion (Gn).</p> <p>Mandible Perimeter: Overall side length of the triangle with corners at Co, gonion (Go), and Gn.</p> <p>Maximum Jaw Opening: Vertical distance between upper and lower incisors at maximum jaw opening.</p>
Mouth	<p>Maximum Vertical Mouth Opening: Distance between mid-points of the upper and lower lips at maximum jaw opening.</p> <p>Maximum Horizontal Mouth Opening: Distance between the lip corners at maximum jaw opening.</p>
Tongue	<p>Maximum Tongue Protrusion Swallowing</p>
VT	<p>Vocal Tract Length: Estimated based on formant frequencies.</p>

Articulatory Measurements

In this study, we focused on a range of motion analysis. Therefore, vertical and horizontal ranges of motion were calculated for all sensors attached to the tongue, lips, and jaw (see Table 2), considering only data between the 10th and 90th percentiles to exclude outliers.

Jaw	<p><i>Mandibular motion</i></p> <p>Sensor position: lower incisor (LI)</p>
Lips	<p><i>Upper lip (UL) motion</i></p> <p><i>Lower lip (LL) motion</i></p>
Tongue	<p><i>Tongue tip (TT) motion</i></p> <p><i>Tongue body (TB) motion</i></p> <p><i>Tongue dorsum (TD) motion</i></p>

*Vertical (v) and horizontal (h) motions were analyzed for each sensor.

Data Analysis

Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA) with L2 regularization and cross-validation was performed to investigate the relationships between anatomical and articulatory properties. The method follows the approach described by Johnson (2023). In this analysis, positive loadings indicate that as the anatomical measure increases, the related articulatory canonical variable also increases. Conversely, negative loadings indicate that as the anatomical measure increases, the related articulatory canonical variable decreases. The loadings also highlight which individual variables contribute the most to the canonical variables, with higher absolute values indicating stronger contributions.

Results

The analysis revealed two significant canonical correlations: the first canonical correlation (CC1) was 0.8972, and the second canonical correlation (CC2) was 0.7854, indicating a strong relationship between anatomical and articulatory properties. These values indicate a strong relationship between the sets of anatomical and articulatory properties. Wilks' lambda was used to test the significance of the canonical correlations. For CC1, the test yielded a Wilks' lambda of 0.0148, with a chi-square statistic of 1150.7 ($df = 96, p < 0.001$). For CC2, Wilks' lambda was 0.0702, with a chi-square statistic of 730.5 ($df = 77, p < 0.001$). These results confirm a statistically significant relationship between the anatomical and articulatory properties. Canonical loadings were examined to understand the contributions of the original variables to the canonical variables. For the anatomical properties, the highest loadings for CC1 were observed for

Figure 1. EMA Trajectories of Four Talkers Demonstrating Variations in Vocal Tract Length, Mandible Length, and Canonical Correlation Scores. The top row shows articulatory patterns for the first canonical correlation (CC1). The left panel illustrates the pattern for a talker with a long vocal tract (17.05 cm) and a positive CC1 loading, while the right panel shows the pattern for a talker with a short vocal tract (13.26 cm) and a negative CC1 loading. The bottom row displays articulatory patterns for the second canonical correlation (CC2). The left panel illustrates the pattern for a talker with a long mandible (13.85 cm), and the right panel shows the pattern for a talker with a short mandible (10.11 cm) and a negative CC2 loading. Arrows indicate the extended ranges of motion of the respective articulators. The positional data were aligned such that the sensor attached to the upper incisor is positioned at the (0,0) coordinate.

vocal tract length, mandible length, and maximum vertical jaw opening. For the CC2, the highest loadings were observed for vocal tract length, maximum vertical jaw opening, and mandible length. These results suggest that these anatomical features play a significant role in shaping the articulatory movements. For the articulatory properties, CC1 had high positive loadings for tongue back vertical range and tongue back horizontal range, while negative loadings were found for mandible vertical range and mandible horizontal range. This indicates that the tongue's movements, both vertically and horizontally, are strongly related to the anatomical features highlighted, while

mandible movements are inversely related. For CC2, high positive loadings were found for tongue body vertical range and tongue body horizontal range, whereas negative loadings were observed for lower lip vertical range and lower lip horizontal range. This suggests that the vertical and horizontal movements of the tongue blade are positively associated with the anatomical variables, whereas the lower lip movements show a negative association.

Additionally, our analysis showed that the tongue's swallowing motion range had noteworthy contributions to both CC1 and CC2, indicating its involvement in the broader relationship

between anatomical and articulatory properties.

Fig. 1 shows EMA trajectories illustrating the articulatory kinematics for four speakers with varying vocal tract and mandible length, illustrating the main findings of CC1 and CC2.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide evidence that anatomical features such as vocal tract length and mandible size significantly influence articulatory patterns in speech production. The strong canonical correlations observed in our results underscore the crucial role these anatomical characteristics play in shaping tongue, lip, and jaw movements during speech. Consistent with Johnson (2023) and Johnson, Ladefoged, and Lindau (1993), we found that larger vocal tracts exhibit greater vertical tongue movement, while smaller vocal tracts show increased vertical jaw movement. This supports the idea that anatomical constraints not only shape individual articulatory patterns but also influence the overall biomechanical strategies employed during speech. However, it must be noted that VTL was estimated from formant frequencies, which inherently links VTL and tongue movement. This methodological aspect suggests a degree of interdependence between VTL and the articulatory movements. Therefore, incorporating direct anatomical measurements of VTL, such as imaging techniques or pharyngometry, in future research could further validate (or refute) these findings and thus provide additional insights. The significant associations between jaw length and tongue movement reinforce the hypothesis that larger vocal tracts and greater tongue mobility might contribute to more expansive vowel spaces, potentially leading to richer vowel inventories. This aligns with the findings of Fuchs, Winkler, and Perrier (2008), who demonstrate that speakers with longer pharynxes produce larger

articulatory displacements between certain vowel pairs, suggesting that a larger vocal tract allows for greater articulatory flexibility and thus more expansive vowel spaces. Conversely, smaller vocal tracts with larger jaw movements could potentially affect syllable structure complexity due to the relationship between jaw opening and speech amplitude envelope patterns. MacNeilage (1998) suggested that jaw movements are crucial to the temporal organization of speech, which varies with vocal tract size and dynamics. In smaller vocal tracts, larger jaw movements may require adjustments in speech timing and sequencing, leading to more complex syllable structures. Speakers might use additional articulatory features, such as increased lip use, to maintain clarity. Limited space in smaller vocal tracts can impact consonant production, necessitating exaggerated or precise articulatory gestures to ensure clear differentiation and achieve the desired acoustic outcomes.

One interesting finding is the relatively strong positive association between the swallowing range of the tongue and various articulatory variables. This suggests that the dynamics of swallowing might play a role in speech articulation, indicating a biomechanical linkage between these two processes.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that vocal tract anatomy, particularly vocal tract length and mandible size, significantly influences articulatory patterns in speech production. Future research should also consider cross-linguistic comparisons to determine if the observed relationships between anatomical features and articulatory patterns hold across different languages. This would provide valuable insights into the universality versus language-specificity of these biomechanical

constraints and adaptations and their implications for phonetic and phonological theory. Overall, this study underscores the importance of considering anatomical factors in speech production research and highlights the complex interplay between anatomy and articulation in shaping human speech.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by the NCCR Evolving Language, funded through the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) Agreement #51NF40_18088. DF and SM received further funding through the SNSF (Grant No. PCEFP1_186841). We also thank Tiena Danner for useful feedback. The results of this work and the tools used will be made more widely accessible through the national infrastructure Språkbanken Tal under funding from the Swedish Research Council (2017–00626).

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Jaw complex: openness, prominence, and dynamics

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Abstract

This paper introduces the term *jaw complex* as a way to describe the various functions of jaw openness in speech production. We here present three ongoing studies, in various stages, with preliminary results. The studies cover prominence, phonemic contexts, and dynamics, while utilizing different methodologies (EMA, MARRYS and ultrasound) appropriate for achieving each of the research goals.

Introduction

The lower jaw is constantly active during speech: in opening the oral cavity for vowel productions, and in closing for constrictions of various consonants. If anything, it is absolutely indispensable in the creation of syllables. One can go so far as to say that speech is a string of syllables, produced with the help of the jaw. This approach follows Frame/Content theory where the jaw is the frame which the rest of the articulation fill with content (MacNeilage & Davis 1990).

But, of course, the lower jaw is biomechanically integrated with the rest of the articulation, not least with the lips, and it is hardly possible to see the organs as isolated single articulators. Although we often like to describe bilabials as consisting of lip movements, vowels of tongue body movements, alveolars of the tip of the tongue, etc., one cannot overlook the fact that the jaw participates in all these aforementioned movements. For example, both manner and place of articulation correlate with jaw openness; bilabials usually display a higher jaw than coronals, except for nasals that despite place of articulation

usually display a lower jaw (Lindblom 1983; Mooshammer et al. 2007; Kawahara et al., 2014). Vowel production is naturally correlated with the jaw: less mandible lowering for the tongue positions of /i e/ and more mandible lowering (= more displacement) in e.g. /a o/ (Lindblom 1971; Wood 1979; Menezes & Erickson 2013). This also greatly affects the jaw openness degree of the neighbouring constrictions (Lindblom 1983; Mooshammer et al. 2007).

Mandibular openness is also highly correlated with syllable strength, as an effect of localised hyperarticulation (de Jong 1995). Thus, a prominent syllable means faster movements, a more open cavity (Beckman & Edwards 1994), and more acceleration (Svensson Lundmark 2024) compared to a non-prominent syllable, which affects the coarticulatory degree of consonants and vowels (Lindblom et al. 2007).

That higher levels of prominence correlate with jaw opening is most evident when we compare the prosodic metrical structure of different languages (Erickson & Niebuhr 2023; Erickson et al. *accepted*). This research is inspired by Fujimura's C/D model (Fujimura 2000) which purports that prosody is the basis of spoken language, and more specifically, the patterns of mandible lowering give prosodic structure to spoken utterances. This work on jaw (mandible) lowering and language rhythm (prominence) patterns has been done on a number of languages, including English (Erickson et al. 2012), Japanese (Kawahara et al. 2014), French (Erickson and Kawahara 2016; Smith et al. 2019), Mandarin (Erickson et al. 2016), and most

recently, Brazilian Portuguese (Erickson et al. *submitted*).

Thus, differences in mouth cavity opening, no matter the reason, affect the movement patterns of other articulators which are all contributing to the acoustical outcome (Lindblom 1971). But, not only spatial positions affect the inter-articulatory coordination: also structured timing relations of speech postures, and the transitions between them, as has been shown using acceleration peaks to separate postures from fast movements of lower jaw, tongue tip and lips (Svensson Lundmark & Erickson 2024).

The lower jaw is evidently not acting in isolation, with both extrinsic and intrinsic effects on speech articulation. For this reason, we introduce the phrase “jaw complex” to symbolize its complex function in speech production. Studies on the jaw complex is an area of research where we are still only seeing the tip of the iceberg. In this paper, we present preliminary results from three ongoing research studies with different approaches to jaw lowering/openness:

1. Jaw openness as an indicator of prominence (rhythm) structure
2. Jaw complex in stressed vs unstressed syllables
3. Jaw complex and tongue: introducing a new method

Material and methods

Study 1: Prominence structure

Currently, the technique that is being used to record jaw movement is EMA, an electromagnetic articulographic set up that, despite its spatio-temporal resolution, has some limitations due to being expensive, immobile, invasive, and time-consuming. A more user-friendly device for mechanical recordings of jaw lowering, the MARRYS, has been developed at University of Southern Denmark (Erickson et al. 2020; Gudmundsson et al. *submitted*). Elastic bands attached to a rigid bike helmet are moving while you speak, and these stretching’s

are picked up by bending sensors, transformed into signals of more or less relative mandible openness (Fig 1).

Figure 1. MARRYS helmet for mechanical measure of lower jaw displacement.

MARRYS may be used in classroom settings, fieldwork etc. To test its methodological applicability we compared it to EMA (Carstens AG501) in a pilot recording at Haskins Laboratories, New Haven, with 6 American English (AmE) speakers (Svensson Lundmark et al. 2023) (Fig 2).

Figure 2. The EMA/MARRYS setup at Haskins Laboratories. Mview: EMA sensors placed on the MARRYS (top) and the jaw, and the MARRYS left and right sensors. The sentence: *No, the fat cat sat with PAT.*

Initial co-collection tests found no interference of signals. The AmE speakers read the following sentence, repeated six times: *The fat cat sat with Mat.* Leading questions read by the experimenter directed the attention of the focus

to either of the monosyllables, such as *Did the THIN cat sit with Mat?* (here: focus on *fat*). So far, preliminary analyses on one speaker in Mview (Tiede 2010) indicate that EMA and MARRYS signals follow each other (Fig 2). See Results section for correlation between jaw openness and prominence structure.

Study 2: Stressed vs unstressed

Here we look at dynamics of jaw openness in stressed and unstressed syllables, using an EMA corpus with 21 South Swedish speakers, recorded with a Carstens AG501 (250 Hz) at the Lund University Humanities Laboratory (detailed information: Svensson Lundmark 2020). The aggregated data set consists of ten speakers and the disyllabic words: /nana/ /mama/ /papa/, with stress on the first syllable (242 tokens). Vertical and horizontal positions of EMA sensors on the lower lip (LL), the tongue tip (TT) and the lower incisors (JW) were used to calculate *displacement* and *peak velocity* during the release from C to V in each syllable. Calculations and statistical analysis (Welch Two Sample t-test) were done in R (R core team 2021).

Study 3: Jaw complex and tongue

The third study focuses on tongue movements and jaw openness. Ultrasound has the advantage that movement of the posterior tongue surface and hyoid can be monitored, which the EMA does not allow. However, even though ultrasound is cost-effective and non-invasive, the analysis of edge detecting is sometimes fooled by imaging artefacts. Combining the high temporal accuracy and point-tracking of EMA with ultrasound has shown promising results (Kirkham et al. 2023). Here we explore combining ultrasound instead with MARRYS, applicable for research questions directly related to jaw openness. Construction and testing of the device were done at the Division of Speech and Hearing Sciences, Queen Margaret University (see more in Results section).

Results

Study 1: Prominence structure

The preliminary analyses show that in the broad focus condition, the speaker produces alternating weak and strong syllables (Fig 3). When producing a contrastive focus, the jaw is lowered for that word. However, in order to maintain the weak/strong pattern across the phrase, jaw openness of the other syllables are also affected, and an already strong syllable (as in *cat* and *Mat*) seems to attract more jaw displacement in contrast to the other words.

Figure 3. Results from Study 1 on one speaker. Strong/weak syllables in broad focus; below: the jaw lowers more for focus.

Study 2: Stressed vs unstressed

Openness (displacement)

Here we compare movement of the three sensors, JW, TT and LL, specifically releases in /n/, /m/ and /p/ between stressed/unstressed syllables, starting with openness. First, JW lowers slightly more for the stressed syllable than the unstressed ($t = 13.343$, $df = 406.27$, $p < .001$). No difference is found due to type of constriction, be it done with TT (as in /n/) or with LL (as in /m/ and /p/) (Fig 4).

Figure 4. JW, LL, TT displacement (mm) in /n m p/ in stressed/unstressed syllables

LL follows the pattern of JW (Fig 4) and lowers more in the stressed syllable ($t = 9.8$, $df = 344.04$, $p < .001$). However, in /m/ and /p/ there is more LL displacement in both syllables, as an indication of its active role in these constrictions, independent from movement of the mandible (Fig 4). Only in /n/ does LL seem to be in a strict control unit with JW.

/n/ display a large TT displacement (Fig 4), slightly more in the stressed syllable ($t = 2.53$, $df = 63.529$, $p < .05$). However, for the bilabials, where TT is not active, there is a large difference in displacement ($t = 20.32$, $df = 113.84$, $p < .001$). This might be an indicator of TT being part of the tongue organ, and as such follows its movements, which lowers more in a stressed syllable, due to a more lowered jaw (Fig 4).

Speed (peak velocity)

JW speeds up during the stressed syllable (Fig 5). There is a significant difference between the stressed/unstressed

condition ($t = -10.87$, $df = 447.21$, $p < .001$), but not between the constrictions.

Figure 5. JW, LL, TT peak velocity (cm/s) in /n m p/ in stressed/unstressed syllables

LL is faster than JW, most evidently when it is active (the bilabials) (Fig 5). Some difference is seen between constrictions (/n/ vs /m p/), still, peak velocity of LL shows a significant difference between a stressed and an unstressed syllable ($t = -4.86$, $df = 448.05$, $p < .001$).

TT moves faster in the stressed /n/ ($t = -2.97$, $df = 150$, $p < .01$). But during stressed /m/ and /p/, TT moves almost slower than JW (Fig 5). The exception is /p/ in the unstressed syllable, where TT is moving very fast. This result is unexpected and hard to explain. The landmark seems to be in the right place for the speakers; hence the anomaly is not because of methodological reasons.

Study 3: Jaw complex and tongue

The complex movements of the tongue body are best captured with imaging techniques such as ultrasound. However, the role of the ultrasound probe needs to

be evaluated. As it is the reference point in ultrasound imaging, it needs to be stable, i.e. the use of headsets. However, the placement of the probe below the chin may potentially restrict jaw movement. The interference seems to depend on vowel context (Pucher et al. 2020). Here we suggest a novel approach for addressing this relationship, by combining ultrasound with MARRYS (Fig 6). We hope this may be a low-cost approach to also understanding the jaw complex in connection with tongue movements during speech. Stay tuned for future developments and results.

Figure 6. Spare parts of an Ultrasound Stabilisation Headset attached to the MARRYS.

Discussion

Results from Study 1 are only preliminary but show promising robust patterns of jaw openness correlation with metrical tree structure. The weak/strong relations seem to be directly implemented in jaw patterns: when focused strong becomes even stronger, also affecting the weak syllables (Fig 7). It remains to be seen if all speakers show this pattern.

Figure 7. Metrical tree structure: a weak syllable is stronger in a strong foot.

Study 2 shows that jaw is lowered more also for stress. Lips and jaw are commonly referred to as a “control unit” because of the biomechanical connection, but they also act independently (Svensson Lundmark & Erickson 2023). Our results show that the independence, in speed and openness, occurs only when the lips are crucial for a constriction.

The tongue tip is affected by stress in any word, which we assume is because of the tongue in /a/, which can be examined further by comparing to other vowels. Both TT and LL moves faster than JW, but not much more when unstressed, hence a smaller mass cannot fully explain these dynamical patterns. TT’s fast release in the word-final plosive remains to be investigated.

Conclusions

While Study 1 shows that mandible lowering interacts with metrical structure, Study 2 shows that other articulators, LL and TT, behave differently as an effect of the mandible lowering in prominent syllables. For future research, we hope Study 3 will shed light on the effect of tongue shape in the interaction between the jaw complex and other articulators.

With this paper we wish to highlight some possibilities and limitations of studying the jaw complex, and how interactive and crucial jaw openness is for speech production end results.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by an International Postdoc grant from the Swedish Research Council (Grant No. 2021-00334). First author wishes to thank Bryan Gick and Bob Ladd for discussions, and James Scobbie for inspiration and aid with the MARRYS/UIT.

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Effects of Information Load and Pragmatic Load on the Hypo-Hyper Continuum

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Abstract

Stance-taking (pragmatic load) and linguistic surprisal (informational load) have both been shown to modulate the hyper-articulated-reduced continuum in speech; however, the extent to which these factors interact with one another has not been investigated. In this study, we examine two measures of hyper-articulation, vowel space expansion (repulsive force) and vowel duration, in the context of high informational and high pragmatic load, operationalized as lexical surprisal and stance-taking strength. We find that surprisal and stance-taking have significant effects on the repulsive force in the vowel space, with significant interactions between surprisal and stance strength. While both factors affected vowel duration, the evidence for interactions between them is less clear. We interpret the observed hyper-articulation in the context of Lindblom's 1990 H&H theory.

Introduction

The speech signal has many parallel channels of information including pragmatic, sociolinguistic, discourse, lexical, indexical, etc., each of which can affect the degree of reduction/hyper-articulation depending on the speaking context. Previous work (e.g., Freeman, 2014) has shown that strong stance-taking, a dimension of pragmatic load, motivates hyper-

articulation. Similarly, there are well-known findings that words which are less predictable from the speaking context (i.e., those with higher informational load) motivate hyper-articulation as well (e.g., (Jurafsky, Bell, Gregory, & Raymond, 2001)). These findings are compatible with the H&H theory's (Lindblom, 1990) prediction that sections of an utterance which bear a higher communicative load, such as high pragmatic load (strong-stance) and high informational load (high-surprisal), should be marked by increased hyper-articulation as the talker adjusts their speech to accommodate the assumed need of the interlocutor to recover the transmitted information. However, previous work has not explored the relative compounding effect of factors causing hyper- or hypo-articulation. In this study, we investigate the interaction between stance-taking and lexical surprisal using two measures of hyper-articulation, vowel space expansion and vowel duration. We use Generalized Additive Modeling to compare the effect of stance and surprisal on the repulsive force and duration of vowels, paying particular attention to the interaction of these factors.

Background Work

Lindblom's 1990 (Lindblom, 1990) H&H Theory drew on previous findings in the literature to propose an explanation for systematic variation in speech — talkers tend towards reduction when

there is sufficient context for the listener to recover the information in the utterance, but hyper-articulate when the communication demands it. In subsequent years, a variety of experimental and modeling findings have broadened our knowledge of and refined thinking around systematic variation in human speech and the underlying communicative contexts (e.g., Anderson, Bard, Sotillo, Newlands, & Doherty-Sneddon, 1997; Aylett & Turk, 2006; Baker & Bradlow, 2009; Katz & Selkirk, 2011; Tomita, 2008; Wright, 2004). As the picture has become fuller, more channels of situational information have been explored. In this context, we use the ATAROS corpus (Freeman et al., 2014) of dyadic problem-solving tasks to study the more thoroughly explored effects informational load, the less well-known effects of pragmatic load, and their interactions.

Methods

Dataset and Stance Annotation

We investigate these effects in English using the ATAROS dataset. This dataset contains dyadic conversations between 34 pairs of speakers on free-form collaborative tasks. We consider the inventory task (where dyads arrange inventory in a department store) and the budget task (where dyads balance the municipal budget of an invented county), totalling 116 recordings. We use the manually-annotated coarse stance labels provided in ATAROS (Freeman, 2015, pp. 16–18). Stance is defined on dimensions of strength (range 0-3, where 0 is the absence of stance-taking, and 3 is strong stance, discrete) and polarity (negative, neutral, or positive).

We consider all stressed vowels in content words.¹ Stress labels are taken

from dictionary pronunciations from the CMU pronouncing dictionary.² Word classes are tagged using the pre-trained Greedy Averaged Perceptron tagger from NLTK (Bird, Klein, & Loper, 2009).

Table 1 gives the counts of the stressed vowels in content words, grouped by stance type.

Table 1. Counts of vowel instances in the ATAROS dataset budget and inventory tasks, grouped by stance strength and polarity.

	–	Neutral	+
None	0	15374	0
Weak	403	19751	12064
Moderate	3749	15003	3344
Strong	282	341	51

Lexical Surprisal

We approximate the linguistic surprisal of speech with the lexical surprisal of a language model which has been trained on comparable data. Specifically, we train a Long Short-Term Memory network (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997), a neural network whose objective is to learn to predict the next word in a sequence of words. Parts 1 and 2 of the Fisher dataset (Cieri, Miller, & Walker, 2004) are used to train their model based on its similarity to the ATAROS dataset (both dyadic, spontaneous conversations). A model with hidden dimension 1024 and embedding dimension 50, using gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1, is trained for 50 epochs with batch size 128. We use cross entropy loss with a weighted mean reduction as the training objective. A learning rate scheduler decreases the learning rate every 10 epochs, with multiplicative factor $\gamma = 0.1$. Once trained, this model can be used to associate probabilities to

¹ Specifically, we include the following Penn Treebank categories: ‘CD’, ‘FW’, ‘JJ’, ‘JJR’, ‘JJS’, ‘NN’, ‘NNS’, ‘NNPS’, ‘PDT’, ‘RB’,

‘RBR’, ‘RBS’, ‘UH’, ‘VB’, ‘VBD’, ‘VBG’, ‘VBN’, ‘VBP’, ‘VBZ.’

² <http://www.speech.cs.cmu.edu/cgi-bin/cmudict>

words in context.

The surprisal of a sentence with word sequence W is defined as the average log probability of the content words in the sequence, as produced by passing the entire sentence through the language model (Equation 1).

$$s(W) = -\frac{\sum_{w_{content} \in W} \log_2(p(w))}{|W|} \quad (1)$$

Repulsive Force Ratio

Following the adaptation of Lindblom’s gravitational force (Liljencrants, Lindblom, & Lindblom, 1972) found in McCloy, (2013); McCloy, Wright, & Souza, (2015); Wright, (2004), we categorize the relative expansion of the vowel space by considering the repulsive force of vowels relative to vowels produced by the same speaker. To compare the expansion of individual vowels rather than the vowel space in general, we modify the repulsive force employed in McCloy, (2013), normalizing by the average repulsive force of all instances of the same vowel.

Let l be the vowel index $l \in \{\Lambda, \upsilon, aI, u, ou, \ae, \varepsilon, i, \alpha, I, \text{ɜ}, \text{ɔ}, eI, au, \text{ɔ}I\}$ and for each vowel l (inscribed as a superscript), i is a single instance of the vowel $i = 1, \dots, n_l$ (inscribed as subscript), where n_l is the number of vowels with label l . A vowel instance v_i^l is represented by the mean F1 and F2 across its entire duration. Let $d(v_i^l, v_j^k)$ be the Euclidean distance between vowels v_i^l and v_j^k in the F1xF2 plane. The repulsive force $r(v_i^l)$ for the vowel instance v_i^l is the sum of the inverse square distances between v_i^l and all other vowel instances with a different label (Equation 2).

$$r(v_i^l) = \sum_{v_j^k, k \neq l} \frac{1}{d(v_i^l, v_j^k)^2} \quad (2)$$

Higher values of repulsive force correspond to greater degrees of phoneme overlap or encroachment, indicating hypoarticulation. Conversely, lower values indicate hyper-articulation.

The normalizing factor of repulsive force for vowel v_i^l is the average repulsive force for all vowels with the same label (Equation 3).

$$\bar{r}(v_i^l) = \frac{r(v_i^l)}{\sum_{v_j^k, k=l} r(v_j^l)} \quad (3)$$

Duration

We compute vowel duration from the timings from phone-level transcriptions force-aligned using the Penn Phonetics Lab Forced Aligner (P2FA, Yuan & Liberman, 2008). For comparability, we analyze all vowels that were included according to the criteria of the repulsive force ratio.

Statistical Comparison

We use Generalized Additive Modeling (Wood, 2017) as implemented in the ‘mgcv’ package (Wood, 2011) in R (using Gamma model family) to investigate the relationship between surprisal, stance-taking, and vowel space expansion and duration. This is a non-parametric modeling method, capable of modeling non-linear relationships between data which has been used in similar studies of acoustic distinctiveness (e.g., Kelley, 2021, p. 28 used a variant with mixed effects to study the impact of various acoustic measures on listener response times). In addition to stance and surprisal (smoothed via thin plate regression splines, Wood, 2003) variables, we include interactions between polarity and strength, and surprisal. We fit separate models for strength and polarity (both including surprisal and an interaction term).³ Neutral polarity, zero stance strength are treated as the intercept

³ In the syntax of mgcv, the formula that defines the model is `gam(repulsive force`

`| distance) ~ s(surprisal) + stance {polarity|strength} +`

conditions.

Results

Figure 1 shows the distributions of the repulsive force ratio and vowel duration for the vowels of interest.

Figure 1. Kernel density estimates of repulsive force ratio (blue) and duration (red).

Table 2. Summary of GAM linear stance strength coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting the repulsive force ratio, with and without interacting effects. Stance strength 0 is intercept. Only significant interactions included.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	1.011	***	1.011	***
	1	-.004	ns	-.004	ns
	2	-.028	***	-.028	***
	3	-.058	***	-0.56	**
EDF	srp	6.6	***	8.3	***
	srp.2	n/a		7.1	*
	srp.3	n/a		3.4	**

Table 3. Summary of GAM linear stance strength coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting duration, with and without interacting effects. Stance strength 0 is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	8.43	***	8.42	***
	1	0.52	***	0.54	***
	2	1.55	***	1.54	***

	3	1.20	***	1.16	ns
EDF	srp	8.8	***	7.8	ns

In tables where significance is reported we use the following notation: *** = $p < 0.001$, ** = $p < 0.01$, * = $p < 0.05$. Significance of parametric coefficients is derived from the Bayesian estimated covariance matrix of the parameter estimators. For smoothed parameters, the effective degrees of freedom (EDF) estimates the degree polynomial needed to fit each term, and the associated significance is derived from ANOVA tests.

Tables 2 and 3 summarize the estimated linear coefficients of stance strength and surprisal EDF when modeling repulsive force ratio and duration, respectively. The coefficients indicate the impact of the stance conditions on the predicted value (e.g., duration). Interaction terms are abbreviated with the syntax $srp.x$, where x is the stance condition. We compare models which include (right) and exclude (left) the interaction term. Tables 4 and 5 analogously report the coefficients and EDF of stance polarity-based models of repulsive force and duration, respectively.

Table 4. Summary of GAM linear stance polarity coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting the repulsive force ratio, with and without interacting effects. Stance polarity neutral (0) is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	1.000	***	1.011	***
	-	-.023	***	-.022	***
	+	-.005	*	-.005	*
EDF	srp	6.4	***	1.7	ns

Discussion

The statistical evidence supports previous findings that both pragmatic and informational load (operationalized as

```
s(surprisal, by = stance {polarity|strength})
```

stance-taking and surprisal) are sources of hyper-articulation, using quantitative measures repulsive force and duration.

Table 5. Summary of GAM linear stance polarity coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting duration, with and without interacting effects. Stance polarity neutral (0) is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	9.33	***	9.34	***
	-	.16	ns	.10	ns
	+	-.88	***	-.84	***
EDF	srp	8.8	***	8.6	**

Without interactions, highly significant effects were found for stronger stance strength as well as surprisal for both repulsive force ratio and duration. Consistent with hyper-articulation, increasing stance reduces the repulsive force ratio and increases duration. When interaction terms are included in models with stance strength, they are only significant between surprisal and stronger stances (see Table 2). The inclusion of interaction terms can reduce the significance of other terms where there are interactions, i.e., between surprisal and strong stance. For duration, no interaction terms are significant, so including them leads to overfitting and reduces significance of strong stance which is associated with fewer instances.

In models without interaction terms, the most significant effects of stance polarity are: i) negative stance reduced repulsive force, consistent with hyper-articulation, and ii) positive stance reduced duration, consistent with hypo-articulation. This may be explained by the fact that most positive stance vowels are associated with weak stance taking, whereas most negative stance vowels are medium or strong stance levels. Surprisal is highly significant, but interaction terms are not useful and adding them reduces its significance.

The presence of significant interactions between surprisal and stronger levels of stance, but not polarity, provides new insight for the interpretation of competing motivations within the H&H framework.

Limitations and Future Work

These findings are representative of one slice of linguistic variation that may exist for informationally-marked or pragmatically-laden speech behaviours. It is not known whether similar interactions would be found for speakers of other languages or in other sociolinguistic contexts (e.g., in different cultural contexts or with familiar interlocutors).

In this work, vowel identity is not controlled for in the duration measure. This may have impacted the findings and is an area for future work.

Conclusion

We demonstrate that both stance-taking and linguistic surprisal significantly motivate changes in articulation, particularly in the gravitational force of the vowel space. Surprisal and stance-taking were found to interactively influence vowels' repulsive force. While both factors also affect vowel duration, the evidence for their interactions in this context is less definitive. These findings underscore the complex acoustic behaviors that result from competition in the H&H framework through different communicative needs.

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Human speech Thinking about the how and the why

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Abstract

This text gives a brief account of why speech and hi-speed phonology are uniquely human. It provides a new view of sound structure – new in that it derives speech sounds from behavioural antecedents. In real-time phonology phonetic segments arise as *emergents* of open-ended vocabulary growth. The classical ‘inescapable’ form-substance distinction plays no role in this account.

An early start

The last common ancestors with the chimpanzees (LCA’s) lost their rain forest habitat (> 4-6 Ma) and came under tremendous pressure to adapt to the new conditions. An entry point to speech seems to have been the tacit demand for improved cooperative communication, a cognitive skill that took on a life-saving role.

Mechanisms of change

For biologists the principal mechanism of evolutionary change is *natural selection* which builds cumulatively on existing capacities. It favors individuals with traits useful for survival. It resembles an amplifier operating also on traits that are only weakly present in the population.

When our ancestors acquired the ability to imitate and learn from each other they added a cultural dimension to selections. Culture is part of biology since cultural traits can determine the success and survival of individuals and groups, e.g., having language or not (Richerson & Boyd).

Habitat loss: A homeless ape

Long ago a period of major geological unrest occurred that drastically transformed East Africa. It went from a flat and jungle-like landscape to a drier and more open region with deserts, deep lakes, and high plateaus, volcanos and savannas. The disappearance of the rain forest made many species homeless - among them our ancestors, a population of ancient chimp-like apes, known as the first *hominins*. This transition forced our ancestors to come up with new routines for managing basic things such as finding food and water, coping with the hot sun, and protecting themselves and their young.

Since the savanna was sparse in familiar foods (fruits and plants) they significantly expanded the range of foraging. They made treks that took them far afield as indicated by the spread of tools left behind at feeding sites. Tools were carried along, handy should an abandoned carcass come in their way. Analyses of teeth microwear suggest a diet including more meat.

Natural selection appears to have favored those who were better at taking the heat and walking long distances. In response to the challenges their anatomy changed – (and their behavior, more anon). Over generations they adopted bipedal gait, got longer legs and taller bodies, lost body hair and added more sweat glands – all adaptations helping them expand their foraging range and manage the heat better.

Fig 1. Fossil data on brain volume for five bipedal species. *H sapiens* data points are about three times as large as the average value for modern chimpanzees (Lieberman).

Where to hide and hunt

The oldest fossils (> 1,8 Ma) have been found along the East African Rift (EAR). The EAR is a gigantic gash in the Earth's shell with both deep lakes and higher grounds. It runs south from present Ethiopia down into Mozambique. The region shows an unusual number of volcanos and its soil is rich in eroded sediments and volcanic ashes, a favourable environment for the preservation of ancient fossil remains. One hypothesis suggests that our ancestors actively sought out places where the ground had been radically broken up by tectonic shifts and had been replaced by rough, hilly and mountainous terrain. That rough topography gave them places where they could hide and use for hunting. Animals could be tricked into entering paths in the rocky terrain where they would be easier to catch and kill. For instance, there would be plenty of opportunities for *ambush hunting*.

A disproportionately large brain

Brain tissue is metabolically expensive. Human brains use about 20-25% of the energy supplied by what we eat. For other animals' brain metabolism is considerably lower, less than 10 % for other primates and 5 % for non-primate mammals. These costs arise because

potentials across axonal membranes must be maintained and the continual synthesis of neurotransmitters requires energy. It follows that the larger the number of neurons in a brain, the greater the need for metabolic fuel. The human brain does not get its energy from an increase in the basal metabolic rate. Neither does it "steal" energy from other expensive organs such as heart, kidneys, liver and the gastro-intestinal tract.

Rather, for evolution to produce a disproportionately large brain - a brain that is larger than what would be expected from the animal's body weight - a drastic increase in the nutritional value of the diet would have been needed. In short, that is exactly what evolution delivered. The hunting scenario just mentioned indicates how hominins may have come across the necessarily large amounts of animal foods needed for this disproportionate brain growth.

From innate to learned signals

How did the hominins communicate? What were they like? Fossil and molecular evidence suggests that they were similar to today's chimpanzees in anatomy and lifestyle (Pilbeam & Lieberman). Psychologists have shown that young children use pointing communicatively before they can express themselves in speech. This behavior reflects a

cognitive maturity that chimps lack. Chimpanzees are not motivated to cooperate and share; they do not understand communicative intentions; they follow gaze, but they do not establish the joint attention and common communicative ground needed to understand the meaning of gestures. Hence chimp-like gestures would not have been a useful platform for improving communication.

The vocal system of the common chimpanzee consists of a fixed, small number of innate signals that are reflexively triggered by internal or external stimuli. Vocal learning and vocal imitation do not seem to occur. Remarkably, all of these characteristics are also found in the vocal behaviour of other apes. The similarity includes signal categories labeled: *hoots*, *whimpers*, *screams* and *squeaks*, *grunts* and *pants* (Slocombe & Zuberbühler). This cross-species match is surprising in view of the millions of years that separate their respective speciations. It implies considerable evolutionary stability. That is an important observation because it strongly supports assuming that *the vocal skills of our earliest forebears did not include vocal learning or an ability to imitate vocal signals*.

Volitional VT motor control

We cannot speak to the details of how our ancestors' cognitive skills and social behavior evolved. But, in broad strokes, we can suggest a few stages of a speculative, but plausible scenario.

Under strong threat hominins probably behaved like modern apes: They put their competitive, individualistic personalities on hold and responded by increasing troop cohesion. Their talent for 'togetherness' was reinforced by the enlargement of their brains which were fuelled by the new diet. New neurons and synapses were pruned by genes and experience and maintained according to the 'use-it-or-lose-it' rule. Evolution seems to have met the tacit demand for improved communication by building an

extension to the existing sound production mechanism. The result was two coordinated modules both connected to the motoneurons of vocalization: one emotionally triggered (old) and one providing full volitional control via direct cortical connections to a broad array of motoneurons including those for articulation, phonation and respiration.

In retrospect, this development was a milestone along the path to speech. It was a *game changer* in that it paved the way for new skills such as vocal imitation and vocal learning. Once in place it reshaped human cognition promoting a collective behavior and mentality with intersubjectivity, mutuality and shared intentionality. It also gave culture a significant role to play in the evolutionary process.

Still far from speech but

At this point in our narrative, let us assume that our ancestral ape is a bipedal with a smaller, retracted jaw, less posterior foramen magnum, lowered larynx and rounded (non-flat) tongue (Lieberman). He has a bigger brain and a more advanced cognition. He has just begun to experiment with his VT, making noises different from his own reflexive calls. He has also started to imitate others. He is more social and multi-modally communicative than his predecessors, but he and his conspecifics are still far from modern speech.

Symbolic reference

Animals communicate vocally. Vervet monkeys make alarm calls. Male humpback whales sing, but they do not invent symbolic signals (Deacon). Human children do. Our infants come highly motivated to interact socially. They seek people's attention. Not yet able to speak, they often use pointing in combination with grunts and other vocalizations. Over time the gestural component is omitted and the voice alone does the "pointing". This vocal activity is first triggered by context. The object referred

to has to be present. Then the behavior becomes more abstract. When the child uses her words without a contextual prompt, she has had the ‘nominal insight’. She says ‘ball’ or ‘doll’ also in the absence of these objects. She understands that ‘things have names’ and has thus grasped the notion of *symbolic reference* (Vihman).

It does not seem unreasonable to picture our ancestors’ first use of signals going through a similar process. As their cognitive capacities grew, they could represent their ecological and social environment in greater detail. Expressive needs became stronger. A shared, open-ended space of semantic information emerged. How could a matching open-ended production mechanism evolve – one that linked a distinct sound pattern to every possible meaning? Problem: The current view is that primates show open-ended comprehension, but have highly inflexible production skills (Seyfarth & Cheney).

Exploration

Cortical control of the VT offered new ways of making acoustic signals. Initially all modalities may have been used but, as hand and body messages grew more elaborate, they eventually reached a complexity that favored faster and more precise ways of communicating. The vocal/auditory modality offered an independent, omnidirectional channel useful at a distance and in the dark. It did not impede locomotion, gestures, or manual work (Donald).

New meaning-carrying signals were derived and tested. All troop members would participate contributing their own attempts and imitating each other. From this collective activity there emerged a distribution of shared signals, *selected*, I assume, *on the basis of their articulatory, perceptual and cognitive merits*. This explorative activity revealed that the VT is not an indivisible whole, but is biomechanically made up a number of semi-independent subsystems (larynx,

lips, soft palate, tongue blade and body). They came across different sound sources (voicing, fricative noise, transients) and found that their acoustic output could be varied by manipulating articulators and modifying the shape of the VT.

Segmentation

Out of the large number of signals that our ancestors are certain to have produced, evolution seems to have singled out the *jaw-based babble* as a template for expanding vocabularies.

Fig 2. Stylized ‘chunky’ waveform envelope produced by opening and closing the VT. Claim: This quantal singularity is the source of modern vowels and consonants (MacNeilage).

So where do discrete phonetic segments come from? Because (i) up-and-down jaw movement had a uniquely large quantal and salient effect on the acoustic signal; (ii) because co-opting the jaw CPG network (Grillner) minimized motor programming; (iii) because using jaw oscillation as a carrier solved the serial organization problem (Lashley); (iv) because the segments of the babble were ideally suited for making combinatorially organized signals.

Boot-strapping imitative skills

Exploration also served the purpose of boot-strapping vocal imitation. It has been proposed that the child’s babbling gives the brain an opportunity to map the possibilities of the vocal system (Vihman). Articulation is combined with phonation in a variety of ways. The motor learning that takes place then is absolutely basic to the acquisition of speech. An auditory-motor mapping takes place. As sound-producing movements are repeated again and again, a strong link is

forged between tactual and kinesthetic impressions and the auditory sensations that the child receives from his own utterances.

Deriving motor commands

When the child then wishes to replicate sounds spoken by others, she has at her disposal a store of orosensory and auditory associations to consult in deciding how to program her own vocal system. For example, when imitating a certain vowel, the motor commands are shaped by the afferent pattern stored for that particular vowel - its AFF-ID. In words, the brain's message is: Move articulators so as to produce a match between the incoming afferent pattern and the vowel's stored AFF-ID.

Invariants

Invariant attributes for a prototypical speech sound are specified at the orosensory (tactual and kinesthetic) level. This choice solves the classical invariance problem because, in the speech chain, the orosensory stage comes before the brain imposes coarticulation on the motor commands.

Differentiation

If mandibular oscillation served as the template for vocabulary expansion, how were template slots phonetically differentiated?. A primary constraint on these selections was perceptual: *Different meanings must sound different*. Phoneticians have concluded that the distribution of the world's vowel qualities is governed by a *principle of dispersion* which tends to drive vowels apart in the acoustic vowel space. Vowels tend to be single-constriction articulations. Articulatory modeling and physiological analyses have shown that the space for vowels is largely determined by the tongue's three extrinsic muscles plus the jaw, the larynx height and the lips. Numerical models of tongue shapes accurately generate arbitrary vowels as a linear combination of the relative activities in m.

genioglossus, m. styloglossus and m. hyoglossus. Informally, these three could be called the [i]-muscle, the [u]-muscle and [a]-muscle.

The UPSID data base lists a total of about 650 consonants observed in 451 languages. Individual languages converge on inventory sizes between 20 and 37 consonants. Remarkably they make similar selections. The bilabial, dental/alveolar and velar places of articulation is a preferred choice (Maddieson). As systems get bigger more places get added, but the stronger trend is to reuse those three places in combination with different sources and manners. Differentiation of the dental/alveolar place has a particularly long lists of possibilities. The basic mechanism in building a consonant inventory is reuse which modifies existing patterns by adding new dimensions (e.g. phonation types, as in Fig 3, bottom), or by making new small incremental changes (enhancing stops by making releases aspirated / ejective, or making their voicing implosive, Fig 3, top).

NAMBIQUARA				
	bil	alv	velar	bil velar
voiceless	p	t	k	kW
vl aspirated	ph	th	kh	kWh
vl ejective	p'	t'	k'	kW'
vd implosive	b<	d<		

Hindi-Urdu		
	bil	dent
plain	m	ɳ
breathl	m ^h	ɳ ^h

Fig 3. Reuse in stop system (top), nasal system (bottom).

Mixtec				
	plain		nasalized	
high	i	u	i~	u~
mid	ɛ	o	ɛ~	o~
low	a		a~	

Fig 4. Dispersion and reuse. 10-vowel system of Mixtec.

The above remarks suggest that vowel and consonant inventories may be constructed differently. That is in not

necessarily the case. When a large vowel system is needed differentiation uses both dispersion and reuse (Fig 4).

Neural reuse

Neuroscience shows that it is quite common for neural circuits established for one purpose to be exapted during evolution, or recycled during normal development. Adding a new function need not require drastic re-wirings, only new connections and/or sharing of existing circuitry (Anderson). A question for future research: Is reuse during phonetic learning facilitated by neural reuse?

Easy way sounds OK.

All languages have syllables. All languages have speech sounds built at specific places of articulation and differentiated by their manners of articulation; Manner is here construed as a specific combination of articulatory subsystem activities. Possible interpretation: Syllables and the patterning of speech sounds offer phenomena that children are likely to come across by chance during their VT exploration. Hence, they are universally present in languages to make phonetic learning easier. *Easy way sounds OK!*

Devil in the msec: Coarticulation

In adult speech, articulatory movements have time constants that make the duration of a vowel gesture (activation + deactivation) longer than its corresponding acoustic segment duration. In real-time phonology that difference shows up as soon as articulatory position control of segment content is applied to the template. Hence coarticulation is present early in life and is a very ancient property of speech.

Fig 5 A schematic of a 9-month-old child's attempt at saying 'baby'. The result was [pepe:]. Note the timing of motor commands (arrows). Also note that the movements (bell-shaped curves) are longer than the acoustic segments.

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Norwegian dialect identification: is prosody enough?

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Abstract

Conventional wisdom dictates that Norwegians primarily use prosodic cues to place dialects into regions (e.g., (Hognestad, 2008)). Earlier work has monotonized intonation and shown that loss of prosodic information obfuscates correct dialectal classification (Gooskens, 2005). However, to the authors' knowledge, no attempt has been made to test the inverse: retaining only the prosodic information in a dialect classification task. Given that the actual hypothesis afforded by conventional wisdom is that prosody is the main contributor to regional dialect placement, the authors believe it to be of paramount importance to confront this hypothesis directly with empirical evidence.

This paper reports results from a pilot of a study implementing such a direct test. In our experiment, we low pass filtered audio of spontaneous Norwegian speech at 400Hz to remove non-prosodic information. Participants were asked to classify the audio into four dialect regions and provided their responses voluntarily through an online form. Analysis of the 25 responses received indicate that Norwegians are highly accurate (cumulative accuracy of 95.65%) at dialect identification when all audio queues are present. When presented with purely prosodic information, the accuracy drops to 50.33%. Even with the reduced performance, this accuracy is well above chance levels (25%), showing that prosody is a strong predictor of dialects for Norwegians.

As this work reports the result from a pilot, we are currently running a more expansive survey. For those interested in participating it can be accessed at <https://nettskjema.no/a/dialekter> (native Norwegians only).

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Neural semantic effects of Swedish word accents

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Abstract

Swedish is a pitch accent language with two distinctive tonal members: a H*L contour for *accent 1* and L*HL for *accent 2* in South Swedish. Since tonal features are not extensively used for lexical distinction, indirectly suggested by the low number of minimal pairs, the lack of tonal manifestation in the absence of a phrasal prominence, and the strong tendency of stem tone - suffix combinations, the two-way contrastive tonal system has been questioned (Bruce & Gårding, 1978; Elert, 1972; Myrberg & Riad, 2015; Riad, 2014). While *accent 2* has been considered the “marked” member (Riad, 1998), *accent 1* has been repeatedly found to facilitate speech perception by allowing the prediction of unfolding full word forms (Roll, 2015, 2022; Roll et al., 2015; Söderström et al., 2016). In the present study, using minimal pairs and contextual constraints in an auditory comprehension task, we found that the tone accents are employed at the lexicosemantic level of processing. Incongruent tone accents were observed to impose difficulty in understanding the utterances, indicated by decreased accuracy of sentence comprehension, increased response times and elevated amplitude of the N400 ERP component, which reflects increased processing difficulty for the brain. Our study presents the first evidence of neural processing of the Swedish tonal minimal pairs and an auditory semantic N400 effect produced by contextually incongruent word accents. The findings further shed light on the multidimensional utilities of the functional load carried by the Swedish tone accents, in which several functions are accommodated by these tonal figures, including morphological and phonological roles as well as predictive functions in the lexical domain.

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The Cumulative-Cue Hypotheses: An account of understanding the multimodal nature of prosodic prominence

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Abstract

Prosodic prominence can be argued to be multimodal, because co-speech gestures tend to temporally align with prominent units in speech (e.g., Flecha-García, 2010; Leonard and Cummins, 2011; Esteve-Gibert et al., 2017), in line with the phonological synchronization rule by McNeill (1992). In addition, speech and gesture may converge not only in the temporal, but also in the “spatial” domain, displaying correlations between the presence and “strength” of gestures (magnitude or complexity) and the strength of acoustic parameters in the production of prosodic prominence as reflected, for instance, in the accentual f_0 range (e.g., Krahmer and Swerts, 2007; Parrell et al., 2014; Pouw et al., 2021; Berger and Zellers, 2022; or see Ambrazaitis and House, 2023, for a review). This spatial convergence has been formulated in terms of the *Cumulative-Cue Hypothesis* (Ambrazaitis and House, 2022, 2023) and has been argued to result from an underlying compulsion to express prominence in both speech and gesture, all else being equal. This compulsion could be understood as part of a revised *Effort Code* (Gussenhoven, 2004): To signal prominence, we tend to produce vocal and gestural signals indicating an increased level of effort. In our talk, we will discuss this idea in more detail and present empirical evidence in favour of it, taken both from published research and our own previous and ongoing studies. For instance, in a data set comprising news readings from Swedish Television, we found a significant trend for larger f_0 rises in sentence-level pitch accents (so-called big accents, a.k.a. sentence accent or focal accent) as gestural complexity increased, measured in terms of number of accompanying head or eyebrow movements (no gesture vs. head vs. head plus eyebrows). In an ongoing study, we aim to replicate the previous analysis with spontaneous speech (Edlund et al., 2010), also including manual gesture strokes.

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Modeling, synthesis and 3D printing of tube vocal tract models with a codeless graphical user interface

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Abstract

Calculating and predicting formants have many uses in speech-centric science. However, a significant imposition to widespread use across phonetics is the lack of accessible programs. In particular, students and scientists in phonetics often have little training in computational sciences or programming languages. We present the *TubeN* graphical user interface (GUI), a coherent speech acoustics software environment for modeling tube vocal tract models, including the ability to synthesize utterances, illustrate vocal tract transfer functions, and produce 3D-printable files for use outside the virtual environment. The program is publicly accessible and can be run without using code.

Introduction

This text serves the double purpose of (i) introducing the program and graphical user interface (GUI) to a speech-centric audience, and (ii) serving as user manual for this first published version of the program. The following sections describe each of the GUIs main functionalities, divided into three subsections. First, the historical, algorithmic, and computational bases of the implemented formant prediction procedure are described with reference to published formant data from real-life speakers. In the second section, functionalities of the GUI are described, including instructions on how to generate tube model sequences, synthesize

vowel sounds based on user input data, generate illustrations of vocal tract transfer functions corresponding to the input model, and generate 3D-printable files for inspection and use outside of the software environment. The third subsection describes how tube sequences created in the GUI may be 3D printed and the sound physically realized. We argue that *TubeN* can serve as a valuable teaching tool in speech-centric hearing sciences.

TubeN

Tube modelling

The vocal tract as tube

The idea of the vocal tract as a tube is several hundreds of years old. It was idea was arguably first tested in proper by the German physicist Christian Gottlieb Kratzenstein, who invented a “vowel organ” to test the “tonal differences between the five vowels A, E, I, O and U” – a prompt issued by the academy in Saint Petersburg in 1778. Kratzenstein’s organ, now lost, possessed a set of pipes, with each pipe corresponding to a unique resonance quality for each vowel sound (Story, 2019). The modern application of the concept, however, owes its form to the descriptions of the physical aspects of speech by Chiba and Kajiyama (1942) and to the circuit theory established by Fant (1970) through publication of his seminal work in *The acoustic theory of speech production*.

The Liljencrants-Fant algorithm

In their 1975 publication, *Computer program for VT-resonance frequency calculations*, Liljencrants and Fant (1975) introduced a program for algorithmically deriving vocal tract resonances based on the circuit theory and wall effects by Fant (1972). The method derives vocal tract resonance frequencies from area functions of tube representations of vocal tracts, based on volume-velocity glottal-lip transfer. Such vocal tract tube models, assuming rigid rounded structures cannot realistically capture intricate acoustic properties of flesh, cartilage, bone, and viscosity that make up real-life vocal tracts. However, their proper implementation allows for principled variation of parameters affecting properties of filtered voice signals.

TubeN reintroduces the program, and provide a use case for illustrating its potential use by researchers. The code supplied in the original publication has been converted into Python and made publicly available online. As in the original program, the user may manually input the number and lengths $A(N)$, and section areas of tubes $L(N)$; the shape of the resultant model is then graphically rendered, and – new to *TubeN* – resultant formant frequencies may be automatically synthesized as .wav files (using a static vowel formant synthesis, *formantsynt*), which can be used to inspect by ear the vowel qualities resulting from the given vocal tract shape. The user may also select the number of predicted formants. Because the mathematical bases of the program have been retained from the original publication (Liljencrants & Fant, 1975), they will not be described here: interested parties are referred to the original publication, and the available code.

Randomized sequences

To provide an illustration of how *TubeN* may be used by researchers, we computed vocal tract area transfer functions

for tubes corresponding to formant values observed for “point vowels” [a], [i] and [u] (the vowels in “ma”, “boot”, and “see”, respectively), corresponding to extremities of articulatory space. We targeted vowel formants for Swedish vowels reported by Fant et al. (1969). Using *TubeN*, we then computed a set of 50,000 randomized sequences of tubes, varying only VT area transfer function configurations, and holding the lengths of the four tubes constant at 2 cm, 6 cm, 6 cm, and 2 cm (corresponding to a total VT length of 16 cm). We then computed best fit based on predicted first, second, and third formant frequencies (F1, F2, F3). Tube segments are summarized in Table 1, formants are summarized in Table 2. The exercise confirmed the appropriateness of the method for its intended purposes. The code has also been used in previous published works (Ekström & Edlund, 2024).

Table 1. Four-tube sequences generated through the “brute force” method.

Vowel	Area(s) (cm ²)				
[a]	2.0	5.0	0.2	0.2	2.0
[i]	2.0	0.2	5.0	5.0	2.0
[u]	0.1	5.0	1.0	1.0	2.0

Functionalities

Example settings

Vocal tract configurations for [a i u] were derived from Fant (1970) and implemented as example settings. These configurations can be implemented with single clicks directly from the GUI.

Add

The *Add* button allows the user to type in lengths and areas of a tube or sequence of tubes. An interactive schematic diagram of the tube is displayed and updated with every new segment added (Figure 1). Alternatively, the program can read a text file, wherein lengths and areas of segments are provided.

Remove

The *Remove* function allows the user to remove a given section. It can be executed by clicking a segment and using the clickable *Remove* button.

Alter

The *Alter* command changes the size and area of any individual section. To execute, the user clicks any given tube section, clicks the clickable *Alter* button, and types in the new length and area number.

Scale

The *Scale* command enables the user to linearly scale the input tube sequence, maintaining proportionally appropriate relationships between tube segments. The scaling command can be executed either by clicking up or down on the appropriate small black triangle button of the Double Spin Box (the program scales in increments of .1 times the original sequences), or type in the desired scale change. The user executes the scaling by pressing the *Scale* button, generating a new tube sequence. The scaling algorithm scales the entirety of the tube sequence linearly, such that sections remain proportional.

Table 2. Vowel formants for adult male native Swedish speakers speaking [a i u] (Fant et al., 1969), and closest fit for each computed by random four-tube sequences.

Vowel	Fant et al.	<i>TubeN</i>
[a]	F1 = 600	F1 = 592
	F2 = 925	F2 = 960
	F3 = 2540	F3 = 2817
[i]	F1 = 255	F1 = 256
	F2 = 2190	F2 = 2199
	F3 = 3150	F3 = 2986
[u]	F1 = 290	F1 = 276
	F2 = 595	F2 = 668
	F3 = 2330	F3 = 2629

Obliviate

The *Obliviate* command empties current input and removes the implemented tube sequence, allowing users to start anew.

Speech synthesis

Synthesis

The *Generate Sound* button synthesizes a .wav audio file based on the current tube information. To avoid naming conflict problems, each audio is for a timestamp (the time it is created), in the format of hour-minute-second (e.g., 15-50-56.wav). In this first iteration of the program, vowels are synthesized with a constant $f_0 = 100$ Hz and a length of 1 s.

Trajectory

The *Trajectory* command allows users to synthesize formant transitions (“ai”, “au”, etc.). Users can manually input anchor values or select from a provided F1-F2 vowel space.

Play

The user can inspect the synthetic sound by pressing the “play” button. Upon synthesis, the file is automatically saved in .wav format to the user’s hard drive.

Illustration

The *Illustrate* button is used to plot the Tube model, peak function and area transfer function. The plot is displayed on the Graphics View widget, which opens as a new window (Figure 3). Illustrations are automatically saved to the user’s hard drive with a .png file-name extension.

3D printing

The *3D File* button creates a 3D-printable (.stl) file based on the current input. Users may then slice the file with settings of the desired 3D printer in order to customize the relevant G-code and print the tube using methods derived from Trimesh Python library (<https://trimesh.org/>). We have sought to make this process as straightforward as possible:

details of this procedure is described in an accompanying .pdf manual.

Continuous model

We sought to 3D-print a generated tube model as a single consistent object, from a single .stl file. This is achieved by reusing and connecting single tube sections, and each section is made by subtracting a cylinder from a larger unit. In this manner, differences between tube areas are straightforwardly sealed by adding a “lid” in between, and without additional modeling. A “continuous” model provides a realization of the GUI-constructed tube and, in demonstrations, proved to reliably reproduce the intended vowel quality (in these demonstrations, a duck call was used as a substitute for the voice source). A “continuous” model printed after the “[i] tube” design seen in Figures 1 and 3, can be seen in Figure 4. As a note of caution, we observed that in printing our “continuous” models, in order to maintain the balance of the whole structure while printing, extra support material had to be generated inside the tube by the printer software; in some cases, these additions were manually removable after printing. We found that this problem could be avoided by printing models “standing up”, rather than on the side.

Detachable model

As an extension, we also sought to test the potential for “detachable” models – an effectively “LEGO-like” design where sections can be assembled and re-assembled after printing. In this explorative build, each section was made into a separate .stl file. A significant potential downside to this approach was that, in order to maintain the ability to assemble the build in different orders, the outwardly observable size of the whole model had to be kept constant (to maintain fit with other segments); in our attempts, this was determined by the largest input tube section. In this manner, printed sections are effectively reusable;

and the approach does not suffer from the issue of interference from structural support elements. We aim to further explore the potential for “reusable” tube sections in future iterations.

3D printing: Additional considerations

For 3D printing, we used a Prusa i3 MK3 3D printer. The material used was Polyactic Acid (PLA). The observations reported here for physical models are based on experience with these products only. Because 3D printers may use a range or different materials, we cannot categorically state that any settings are appropriate for printing tube sequences; other available materials may be more or less appropriate. A continuous model normally took 2.5 hours to print, while a detachable model (all four sections) took approximately 4.5 hours. The printer software handles placement and generates the necessary support automatically. If available, we recommend the use of water-dissolvable material for support.

Discussion

The *TubeN* software and GUI may be used as a complement in phonetics classes. The code and GUI .exe file, are publicly available for download. In future work, we intend to investigate and evaluate the potential of the *TubeN* environment for phonetics and speech acoustics teaching (e.g., Arai, 2022). We believe exploring relationships of speech acoustics is a valuable method of instruction and learning. In future work, we intend to investigate and evaluate the potential of the *TubeN* environment for phonetics and speech acoustics teaching. We hope that introducing a codeless and easily accessible environment facilitates phonetics learning for a new generation of students: we encourage teachers of phonetics to explore such an endeavor with us. The code and GUI .exe file, are publicly available for download (github.com/jbeskow/tuben).

Figure 1. The new realization of the computer program by Liljencrants and Fant (1975), with a codeless graphical user interface. The program can be run without any coding experience using an executable .exe file, available in the relevant GitHub repository.

Figure 2. The “Trajectory” window. Graphical vowel space of Canadian vowels from Russell (2024).

Figure 3. Four-tube illustration for the example [i]. The new realization of the computer program by Liljencrants and Fant (1975) includes code for generating illustrations of distance from lips (top), spectral peak determinants (middle), and vocal tract area transfer functions (bottom) for sequences of tubes.

Figure 4. A 3D printed tube section. After the example model presented in Liljencrants and Fant (1975). The configuration is the same as in Figures 1 and 3. Total length is 16 cm. The tube is positioned top-down as corresponding to increasing distance from the lips.

Acknowledgements

The results of this work will be more widely accessible through the national infrastructure Språkbanken Tal under funding from the Swedish Research Council (2017-00626).

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The function of North Germanic word accents

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Abstract

Since 2010, it has become increasingly clear that North Germanic word accents have a strong predictive function in speech processing. Recent findings on the semantic effects of word accents might appear contradictory to this interpretation. However, we show that the predictive perspective is crucial for understanding these semantic effects.

Introduction

North Germanic word accents and Danish stød are distinctive in the traditional phonological sense (Trubetzkoy, 1958) since they can minimally distinguish word pairs such as ¹*moppen* ‘the mop’ and ²*moppen* ‘the moped.’ However, they typically show relatively low functional load. Swedish has around 357 minimal pairs (Elert, 1972). In Norwegian, word accents have gained in functional load with minimal pair estimates ranging between 2432 (Jensen, 1958) and slightly over 3000 (Leira, 1998) due to the loss of segmental contrasts in some environments. It does not seem likely that word accents’ *raison de’etre* and the cause of their survival in the language has been distinguishing around a few hundred word pairs. It has been suggested that the main role of word accents in language is their *predictive* function (Roll, 2022). Recent evidence, however, has shown that they give rise to an electrophysiological N400 effect in semantically incongruent contexts (Kwon, 2023;

Kwon & Roll, in press, submitted). The results indicate an association between word accents and lexical forms since the N400 is typically interpreted as indexing full-form lexical processing (Kutas & Hillyard, 1980). This might seem like a counterargument to the predictive function, which has mainly been argued based on the association between word accents and certain suffixes (Roll, Horne, & Lindgren, 2010; Roll, Söderström, & Horne, 2013; Söderström, Horne, & Roll, 2017). Here, we will argue quite the opposite: The lexical effects of word accents are not found at odds with the predictive function, but rather *because of it*.

Markedness and brain activity

The story of the predictive function of word accents is also a story of a brain wave: the *pre-activation negativity* (PrAN). When word accent perception was first tested using event-related potentials (ERP), a difference was found in the brain activity after the F0 onset of accent 1 and 2 (Roll et al., 2010). ERPs are portions of the electroencephalographic (EEG) signal time-locked to a certain event, in this case word accents that the participants listened to. Depending on the characteristics of the underlying brain sources, potentials can be electrically positive or negative. This gives rise to characteristic components related to auditory perception in the ERP signal, such as the N1, a negative deflection

peaking at around 100 ms after a sound, and the P2, with its positive peak somewhere around 200 ms. These components are typically larger for unexpected events than expected. The N400 is a negative peak at around 400 ms following events that are semantically interpretable, mostly words, but also, for example, images.

The ERP difference between accent 1 and 2 starts at 136 ms after F0 onset. It overlaps with the P2 component, and was, therefore, when first observed, naturally assumed to be caused by accent 2 enhancing the P2 (Roll et al., 2010). This was all the more natural since accent 2 is generally assumed to be *marked* both lexically and phonetically (Riad, 2014). This assumption turned out to be untenable as further evidence emerged.

If the difference in the brain's perception were due to accent 2 being lexically marked, we would expect correct accent 2 words to have faster response times than accent 1 (Felder, Jönsson-Steiner, & Eulitz, 2009). Quite the opposite has repeatedly been observed (Gosselke Berthelsen, Horne, Brännström, Shtyrov, & Roll, 2018; Söderström, Roll, & Horne, 2012). Further, if the word accent ERP effect were due to accent 2 being acoustically marked, the effect should be found for word accents outside of a lexical context. Accent 2, being a high tone, could be thought to draw passive attention allocation to it (Roll, Söderström, & Horne, 2011). However, this hypothesis, too, turned out to be contradicted by evidence. Central Swedish Accent 2 does have a stronger acoustic effect than accent 1, but it occurs before the P2 and consists of an increase of the N1 component. In other words, the acoustic markedness effect of accent 2 is clearly dissociated from the difference found between accent 1 and 2 in lexical contexts (Roll et al., 2013).

Starting to view the results in light of the rising predictive coding

framework (Friston & Kiebel, 2009), a new interpretation began to take shape. What if the observed brain processing difference between the two word accents was rather an effect of accent 1 than of accent 2? What if it reflected the fact that accent 1 is a better *predictor* than accent 2? Since accent 2 is found in all transparent compounds in Central Swedish, listeners can be more certain about which word they are hearing if it starts with accent 1. There are fewer words to choose from beginning with accent 1. The word simply cannot be one of a possibly infinite array of compounds. Added to this, accent 2 is also associated with a larger number of suffixes. In line with this interpretation, in a combined ERP and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) study, accent 1 was shown to produce greater activity around the left auditory cortex, in areas known for phonetic, phonological, and lexical processing. The hemodynamic increase in activity correlated with the ERP effect of accent 1 (Roll et al., 2015). The logical next step was to see if the certainty about which word was heard increased the negative effect of accent 1. The frequencies of the stimulus words in a corpus were assessed based on their pronunciation and the number of words in the corpus that started on each occurring syllable onset and nucleus were extracted. In this way, the number of possible continuations a listener could be expected to choose between when hearing a particular word beginning could be calculated. The results were striking: The negativity of the ERPs increased with the possible certainty of the listener about the word identity. Since the ERP activity had also correlated with increased neural activity in brain areas associated with phonological and lexical activation, the effect was interpreted as showing pre-activation of a word form that had not yet been fully heard. Since this ERP component had not been observed before, it was given a name: the

pre-activation negativity (PrAN) (Söderström, Horne, Frid, & Roll, 2016).

A final piece of evidence pointing towards acoustic prominence not being of major relevance for the perceptual effects was the observation of a PrAN for accent 1 also in South Swedish, where, at F0 onset, accent 1 was a high tone whereas accent 2 was low, that is, the acoustic mirror image as compared to previously studied Central Swedish (Roll, 2015). Even in Danish, the irregular vocal fold vibrations of *stød* gave rise to a similar, albeit later timed, negativity (Hjortdal, Frid, & Roll, 2022). Like accent 1, *stød* constrains the number of possible words more than non-*stød*. Unlike its Swedish counterpart, however, *stød* is usually considered to be phonetically marked (Basbøll, 2005). Finally, with refined lexical statistic measures, PrAN has been found to index predictive certainty rather than surprise, as has been argued for another superficially similar component, the phonological mapping negativity (Hjortdal, Frid, Novén, & Roll, 2024).

What the PrAN discovery showed about word accent perception was thus that phonological or phonetic markedness did not seem to play an important role but lexical characteristics influencing the predictive constraints in speech perception did.

Full form storage and access

Accent 1, then, increases brain activity because it constrains the number of possibilities when hearing a word beginning, allowing for a stronger pre-activation of the expected word form. We say *word form* since this has been the most common case in the literature on word accent processing. It has been shown that word accents *can* be abstractly associated with grammatical suffixes (Söderström, Horne, Mannfolk, Westen, & Roll, 2017; Söderström, Horne, & Roll, 2017). However, brain data points towards relatively frequent Swedish

nouns being stored and mostly accessed as full inflected forms contrary to Finnish, where nouns are decomposed into their morphological subparts during speech processing (Lehtonen, Niska, Wande, Niemi, & Laine, 2006). Word accents are therefore strongly associated with fully inflected words in the case of frequent nouns. This is clearly seen in the fact that the proficiency in native speakers' processing of word accents in real nouns correlates with their cortical structure in brain areas involved in phonological and lexical processing. In contrast, word-accent processing skill in pseudowords is related to the structure of a brain area devoted to morphological processing (Novén, Schremm, Horne, & Roll, 2021; Schremm et al., 2018). This led Schremm et al. (2018) to conclude that word accents are most firmly associated with full word forms in real nouns in the brain. Further, although in the early works on word-accent neurophysiology, the emphasis was on the association between word accents and suffixes (Roll et al., 2010; Roll et al., 2013), since the formulation of the PrAN, the calculation of the predictive characteristics of word accents has been based on fully inflected forms occurring in corpora (Hjortdal et al., 2024; León-Cabrera, Hjortdal, Berthelsen, Rodríguez-Fornells, & Roll, 2024; Roll, Söderström, Hjortdal, & Horne, 2023; Söderström, Horne, Frid, et al., 2016; Söderström, Horne, & Roll, 2016).

Predictive and distinctive function

To return to the initial question, does the finding of an N400 for semantically incongruent word accents show that word accents have a higher functional load in the structuralist sense than previously thought? No, the fact remains that word accents have a low functional load from a structuralist point of view. Easily put, they only distinguish between a handful of minimal pairs and are thus not very useful in the phonological system seen statically as a synchronic stage in

diachronic language development. However, in speech, words are not perceived statically but unfold dynamically. We hear the beginning of words before we hear their end. Since it is becoming increasingly clear that the brain is predictive in its basic functioning (Friston & Kiebel, 2009) and particularly that speech processing is based on prediction (Friston et al., 2021), the predictive function of word accents should be as important as their distinctive function. The predictive function can even be seen as a dynamic form of the distinctive function. At the point where we hear a word accent, we do not have access to the full word form, and it does have a quasi-distinctive function in ruling out all the possibilities that would have had the other word accent (Roll, 2022). Thus, hearing /spe/- with accent 1 our predictive brain can rule out all the 185 possible accent-2 forms, including *spegeln* ‘the mirror,’ and *spetan* ‘the splinter,’ and concentrate on the five possible accent-1 forms, of which the most likely would probably be *spelet* ‘the game.’ In other words, regarding Swedish nouns, the predictive function mainly consists of activating and inhibiting *fully inflected forms*.

There is no difference in the perception process when a semantically incongruent word accent is heard. The word accent is still mainly associated with a fully inflected form. If hearing *Han åkte iväg på ¹mop-* ‘He went away on (the) mop-’ with accent 1, the predictive perception system activates the most likely candidates, involving ¹*moppen* ‘the mop’ and inhibits accent-2 candidates like the semantically congruent ²*moppen* ‘the moped.’ Therefore, semantic integration becomes more difficult, increasing the N400.

Conclusions

Word accents have been shown to have a strong predictive function in speech processing. The predictive function has mainly been argued and

calculated based on fully inflected word forms. There is also previous evidence that word accents have strong associations with full word-form representations in the brain. Therefore, in view of the previous research, in no way does the finding of an N400 effect for semantically incongruent word accents contradict their predictive function. On the contrary, it strengthens the interpretation. From a structuralist functional load perspective, word accents would not be expected to give rise to a robust semantic effect due to their low functional load. Only when seen from a dynamic predictive processing perspective does the brain’s strong semantic reaction to contextually incongruent word accents make sense.

Acknowledgments

The work was supported by the Swedish Research Council (Grant No. 2018.00632), the Marcus and Amalia Wallenberg Foundation (Grant No. 2018.0021), the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation (Grant No. 2018.0454), Lund University, and the Crafoord Foundation (Grant No. 2017.0006).

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Somali pitch accent from a typological perspective

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Abstract

The classification of Somali as a tone or pitch/tonal accent language has long been debated. This paper examines the fundamental frequency (F0) manifestations of Somali accents in isolated word forms and noun phrases (NPs), as well as other features such as the function and predictability of accents. The results reveal both similarities and differences when compared to Japanese and Swedish, which are widely described as pitch-accent languages.

Introduction

Somali is a Cushitic language in the Afro-Asiatic phylum, spoken in Somalia and neighboring Kenya, Ethiopia, and Djibouti. It is the official language of Somalia and the Somali Regional State of Ethiopia. In Sweden, the Somali community represents the largest group of African-born immigrants, and among school children, Somali is the second largest minority language after Arabic (Nilsson 2018).

Somali is a typologically interesting language. Since Armstrong (1934), there has been a long-standing debate about whether it is a tone or pitch/tonal-accent language (see Hyman 1981, Le Gac 2016, and Downing & Nilsson 2019 for an overview). In the present study, we use the term accent.

This paper examines the Somali accent's fundamental frequency (F0) manifestations in isolated word forms and noun phrases (NPs). The results are compared with well-established pitch accent languages like Japanese and Swedish, including other features such as the function and predictability of accents.

Function and predictability of accent

Despite the debate about prosodic typology, there has been broad consensus that pitch accent in Somali and other Cushitic languages serves primarily a grammatical role rather than a lexical one (cf. Mous 2021).

The examples (1) – (4) below show different functions carried by the Somali pitch accent.

(1) case contrast for ‘Mohammad’

- a. *Maxámed*, ‘Absolute’
- b. *Maxamed*, ‘Nominative’
- c. *Maxaméd*, ‘Genitive’
- d. *Máxamed*, ‘Vocative’

(2) gender contrast

- a. *ínan* ‘boy’
- b. *ínán* ‘girl’

(3) word class contrast

- a. *héés* ‘sing!’
- b. *heés* ‘a song’

(4) lexical contrast

- a. *béer* ‘liver’
- b. *beér* ‘garden, field’

Thus, in Somali, the accentual pattern of a given word is predictable mainly based on grammar, with only a small number of exceptions, such as (4) above.

The function and predictability of pitch accents in Somali can be compared with those in Japanese and Swedish (Nagano-Madsen & Bruce 1998). In Japanese, pitch accents are mostly unpredictable as they are lexical, and there is even an accent dictionary for Japanese.

The pitch accents in Swedish are affiliated with the lexicon through the stress category first, as Swedish is a

Germanic language like English. The stress location in Swedish is partly predictable from syllable weight and word-internal structure but otherwise has to be specified in the lexicon. The distinction between accents 1 and 2 is often predictable by knowing both phonological and morphological factors (Nagano-Madsen and Bruce 1998).

Somali accent patterns

Thus far, three basic contrastive pitch patterns have been recognized for common nouns, verbs, and adjectives in Somali: penult and final accents marked by a H tone and an unaccented pattern, which has a realization of L-tone (Hyman 1981). In addition, some words have an accent on the earlier part of the word as a result of diachronic change, e.g., *már-ayaa* < *már-a hayaa* ‘is passing by’ (Saeed 1999: 89), also observed in the vocative case.

Unaccented words

In Somali, unaccented words are typically found among bare nouns as subjects and verbs in the non-progressive aspect. However, these verbs are often in tonal alternation with the preceding sentence type marker (STM) in accent placement (Hyman 1981, Saeed 1999: 45, Orwin 2007: 9). As a result, a long sequence consisting of only unaccented words is unlikely to occur in Somali.

Unaccented words differ entirely in Japanese, which can be considered the default (see Ito & Mester 2016 for discussion). According to Kubozono (2006), 71% of native Japanese words are unaccented, while this proportion drops to 7% for Western loanwords. Therefore, constructing sentences consisting entirely of unaccented words is easy in Japanese.

Dialectal variation

The dialectal variation in word accent patterns has been well-known for a long time, both for Japanese (Hattori 1933) and for Swedish (Meyer 1937, Gårding

1977). The dialectal variation in Japanese and Swedish includes even areas without accent distinction, i.e., accentless dialects. To our knowledge, no such dialectal variations have been reported in Somali. In our recordings of the word-list, a striking agreement was found in accent placement (final, penult, and unaccented) between speakers of the Northern dialect around Hargeisa and those from the Southern dialect around Mogadishu.

Analysis of F0 manifestation

The F0 manifestation of the Somali accent is examined in word isolation form and a NP composed of a noun followed by an adjective.

Speakers

Five native speakers of Somali participated in the recording. Three are from Mogadishu, the capital of Somalia, and one is a female speaker. Two of them are from the Northern area around Halgeisha. The recordings were made either in a soundproof or quiet room. All the recordings were made during 2019 in Sweden as mono, 44100 Hz, 32-bit, float PCM wav-files using Audacity 2.1.2 and a SoundProjects LSM microphone. The recorded material was processed and analyzed using the SUGI Speech Analyzer.

Word in isolation form

A wordlist of 28 words varying in word length from 1 to 7 morae was prepared. The speakers show a remarkable agreement in accent placement despite their regional origin, with only a few exceptions produced by one of the speakers (Speaker 2), whose father turned out not to be a native Somali speaker.

F0 manifestation of Somali accents

Figure 1 shows F0 contours of final, penult, and unaccented (L) patterns. The invariant F0 configuration for the accent is a sharp F0 rise (H) on the accented mora, with the penult followed by a sharp F0 fall (L) on the post-accented

mora. No other invariant F0 shapes were observed.

Consequently, we propose the tonal structure of final and penult accents in Somali as H* and H*+L, respectively. The H*+L type also applies to other non-final accents besides penult, i.e., exceptional cases where the accent is found earlier in a word and the case of a tonal alternation. All five speakers show the same F0 manifestations for the three accent patterns mentioned above, with slight variation in final lowering. More examples are found in Figure 2, which shows the F0 manifestations of Somali accents in NPs.

Figure 1. F0 contours of the three accentual patterns in Somali: *maamúle* ‘manager’ (penult), *minaarád* ‘minaret’ (final), *maalaa* ‘milks’ (unaccented/L), Speaker 1.

Comparison with other languages

The manifestation of F0 in Somali accents shows similarities and differences compared to Japanese and Swedish accents. Somali and Japanese share a similarity in the alignment of F0 and segments. In both Somali and Japanese, the rise and fall of F0 in accents are timed with a mora boundary (cf. Nagano-Madsen 1992:77). As for Swedish, accents 1 and 2 have been analyzed as a difference in the timing of the tonal contour with the stressed syllable.

The main difference between Somali and Japanese is the presence or absence of the phrasal component. In Japanese, there is an invariant F0 rise to mark the onset of a word/phrase, which applies to both unaccented and accented words. In Fujisaki’s intonation model of standard Japanese (Fujisaki & Sudo

1971), accents are superimposed on a phrasal component. Even in the competing AM intonation model of Japanese, both phrasal and accentual components are recognized as basic components (Pierrehumbert & Beckman 1988, Venditti 2005).

Figure 2 illustrates the F0 manifestation of accented vs. unaccented words in Ryukyuan (or Ryukyu dialect of Japanese). The phrasal component is marked by (H-). Another difference is how unaccented words are realized: they are transcribed as a H in Japanese but a L in Somali.

Figure 2. F0 contours illustrating accented vs. unaccented words in the Ryukyuan dialect of Japanese. Adopted from Nagano-Madsen (2018).

The tonal structure of pitch accents

Table 1 summarizes the labeling and tonal structure of accents in Somali, Japanese, and Swedish. The tonal structure of Japanese and Swedish accents is adopted from Venditti (2005) and Nagano-Madsen and Bruce (1998). It is difficult to see any similarities in labeling pitch accents for the three languages. When represented by tonal structure, their similarities in the F0 manifestation of accents become clearer.

Table 1. Pitch accent specifications.

language	Accent labeling	Tonal structure
Somali	Final penult	H* H*+L
Japanese	Unaccented Accented	H- H*+L
Swedish	Accent I, accent II	HL* H*L

Noun Phrases

This section examines the F0 manifestation of Somali accents in NPs (noun + adjective). Recent studies by Le Gac (2018) and Downing & Nilsson (2019) have explored accent realization in Somali NPs. Le Gac challenges the traditional binary analysis of accent reduction in the second H in subject NPs, citing variations observed in his acoustic measurements of F0 peak height.

Meanwhile, Downing & Nilsson analyze non-subject NPs from an extensive sentence corpus produced by three speakers. They report that the second H in an NP is omitted in 50% of the cases (297 out of 599 instances). Their findings contradict the general description, as asserted by Hyman (1981), Saeed (1993:111-117), and Green & Morrison (2016), that the H tone on the modifier is typically resistant to deletion. Since both Le Gac's and Downing and Nilsson's studies analyzed the existing speech corpus, the details of the noun phrase (NP) types were not specified. Therefore, in our test material, we used all possible combinations of accents for nouns and adjectives and short and long words.

Test NPs

Test NPs are composed of a noun followed by an adjective covering all the possible combinations of final (H*) and penult (H*+L) accents as shown in (1) – (4) below. Test phrases are also composed, as much as possible, to include short and long words. Each speaker produced the NP in isolation and repeated it at least three times.

(1) penult + penult
 a. *mallaáy wéyn* 'a big fish'
 b. *wiil róon* 'a healthy boy'

(2) penult + final
 a. *mallaáy yaryár* 'small fish'
 b. *wiil yár* 'a small boy'

(3) final + penult

a. *caaró wéyn* 'a big spider'
 b. *maroodí nóol* 'a living elephant'

(4) final + final
 a. *nál yár* 'a small light bulb'
 b. *meél marán* 'an empty place'
 c. *laamó yaryár* 'small branches'

Results and discussion

Table 2. summarizes the accent combination of the first word (noun) and the second word (adjective) and the resulting F0 manifestations. It identifies three types of F0 manifestation regarding how the second accent is produced and how the speakers use the pattern. Figures 3 - 5 illustrate typical examples of each type.

Table 2. Accent combination and F0 manifestation with speaker specification in the bracket.

First word	Second word	
	Penult (H*+L)	Final (H*)
Penult (H*+L)	Downstep (all)	Downstep (1, 3, 4, 5) Deletion (2); for <i>wiil yár</i> , by all)
Final (H*)	Downstep (1, 4) Deletion (2) Plateau (3, 5)	Deletion (all)

Three types of F0 manifestations are found for the NP in Somali spoken in isolation: they are downstep, where the second accent is produced at a lower pitch register; deletion, where the second accent is deleted; and a plateau, where the second accent merges the first one, forming a level F0 like a plateau. Hyman (1981) describes the case where the H tone is lowered by an intervening L tone, i.e., automatic downstep. Our results show that a downstep can occur without an intervening L tone, i.e., a non-automatic downstep, and can also occur across a pause.

Figure 3. (a) speaker 1, (b) speaker 2: *Malláay wéyn* ‘big fish’ P=penult.

Figure 4. (a) speaker 1, (b) speaker 5. *Caaró wéyn* ‘a big spider’ F=final, P=penult.

Figure 5. (a) speaker 3, *Malláay yaryár* ‘small fish,’ (b) speaker 3. *Laamó yaryár* ‘small branches,’ P=penult, F=final.

The most common type of F0 manifestation of NPs is a downstep, which all five speakers use for combining H*+L and H*+L (penult+penult) and other combinations. All speakers deleted the second accent in a combination for H* + H* (final+final) and for *wíill vár* ‘a small boy’, a combination of H*+L – H*. We consider the deletion in these examples primarily due to the production mechanism of the laryngeal muscles involved in producing a rising (LH) F0, which takes longer than a falling (HL) F0, cf. Hirose (1981).

The combination of final plus penult H*– H*+L allows more variations, including a plateau, typically found in fluent, fast speech.

Interestingly, three F0 patterns found for NPs with a modifier in Somali are reminiscent of those reported for Standard Japanese (Venditti 2005) and Ryukyuan (Nagano-Madsen 2015).

In our results, the deletion of the second accent is more limited than that

reported by Downing & Nilsson (2019). We consider it due to the difference in the material analyzed in the two studies. Downing & Nilsson elicited the NPs from an existing sentence corpus, while the present study analyzed carefully produced NPs in isolation.

Conclusions

Somali is like Japanese in that both manifest accents on a mora basis, whereas Swedish does so on a syllable basis. Japanese marks the word/phrase onset by a well-defined F0 shape, called a phrasal component, while no such component is found in Somali. The unaccented word in Somali has a low F0 (L-tone sequence), while that in Japanese has a high F0 (H-tone sequence). The occurrence of unaccented words is limited in Somali, whereas it is a default in native Japanese words.

Accents in Somali are mostly grammatical and predictable, whereas accents in Japanese exhibit lexical contrast, making their patterns unpredictable. Accents in Swedish fall somewhere between Somali and Japanese in terms of function and predictability.

Acknowledgments

This work received partial financial support from the Swedish Research Council under grant no. 2015-01394 (Somali and prosodic typology).

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Final lowering in contacting African tone languages: A study of variation in postlexical prosody

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Abstract

This paper explores a critically understudied phenomenon, multilingual sociotonic variation involving two contacting African tonal languages, Guinean Mano and Guinean Kpelle. Based on manual annotation and automatic f_0 extraction from semi-spontaneous data, we explore variation in utterance-final H→M lowering rule in Mano. We study tone production in Mano speakers having various degrees of exposure to Mano and Kpelle and compare bilingual Mano tone production with that of baseline Mano and Kpelle L1 speakers. We demonstrate that the presence of final H lowering correlates with the degree of Mano/Kpelle exposure. First, final lowering is not attested in Mano L2 tone production similarly to Kpelle L1 speech. Second, its realization in simultaneous bilingual speakers depends on their socialization background; namely, it is identical to baseline Mano speech in bilinguals who were socialized in Mano-speaking families; and it is less consistent in speakers from bilingual and Kpelle-speaking families.

Introduction

Final lowering is a common prosodic boundary phenomenon attested in different languages, such as English, Danish, Japanese and Kipare (Arvaniti, 2007 and references therein). For example, in English, the final H in a series of downstepping H peaks is significantly lowered (Liberman & Pierrehumbert, 1984, p. 182). The broad typological scope of languages having final lowering suggests that it may be physiologically

conditioned, e.g. due to relaxation of laryngeal muscles, yet it has been phonologized in some tone languages (Gussenhoven, 2004).

There is a growing literature on contact-induced variation in lexical prosody of tonal languages, i.e. languages having contrastive pitch specifications relevant for lexical and/or grammatical meanings (Wee, 2019), and which constitute around a half of world languages (Maddieson, 2013). Sociotonic research on the interaction between tonal languages and linguistic varieties remains scarce and focussed on Southeast Asian languages (Stanford, 2008, 2016; Mok et al., 2013; Jingwei, 2014; Yeh & Lin, 2015; Jingwei et al., 2023). Even less is known about the acquisition of allotonic rules (Qin, 2022) and sociotonic variation in African level tone languages. Furthermore, current sociotonic research has mainly focused on controlled speech data, i.e. word lists, sentence frames, and phrase lists (Stanford, 2008; Jingwei, 2014), which limits the scope of study to lexical tones and leaves variation in intonation almost completely unexplored.

Located at the intersection of sociotonic research and research of multilingualism, this paper explores a critically understudied phenomenon, multilingual variation in prosody involving two contacting African tonal languages, Mano, or Manon [iso 639-3:mev] and Kpelle, or Guerzé [iso 639-3:gkp], based on both manual annotation and automatic f_0 extraction from semi-spontaneous data.

Mano and Kpelle have different tonal systems, with Kpelle featuring a binary tonal contrast (Low/High) and

Mano has three contrastive level tones (Low/Mid/High), as well as a specific utterance-final rule of H lowering.

In this paper, we focus on utterance-final H lowering rule as a sociotonic variable in Mano tone production. We explore variation in Mano speakers having various degrees of exposure to Mano and Kpelle, and compare bilingual Mano tone production with that of baseline Mano and Kpelle L1 speakers.

We demonstrate that the presence of final H lowering correlates with the degree of Mano/Kpelle exposure. It is not attested in Mano L2 tone production; and it varies in simultaneous bilinguals, depending on their socialization background.

Sociolinguistic situation

Kpelle and Mano belong to the different branches of the Mande family: Southwestern Mande (Kpelle) and Southern Mande (Mano). Both languages are spoken in Northern Liberia and in the Southeastern Guinean region named Forest Guinea (Guinée Forestière), which is the locality that we study here. In Forest Guinea, Mano and Kpelle are spoken by 57 000 and 332 000 people, respectively. While Mano and Kpelle have distinct ethnic identities, they have closely intertwined economic activities and similar cultural patterns, with widely practiced intermarriages. The numerical dominance of Kpelle speakers over Mano speakers commonly results in asymmetrical bilingualism, whereby the Mano speak Kpelle more often than the other way around (Khachatryan & Konoshenko, 2021, p. 980).

Tones in Mano and Kpelle

Tones in Kpelle

Guinean Kpelle has a binary Low vs. High contrast with morpheme-level tone melodies, e.g. /H/ *kélé* ‘raffia palm’, /L^H/, *kèlè* ‘small bee’, /HL/ *kélè* ‘shed’, /L/ *kèlèŋ* ‘bird species’, /LHL/ *kèlèŋ* ‘African fox’. Underlying melodies are

subject to several surface tone rules, which are not relevant for the present discussion (Konoshenko, 2014, 2022). Crucially, utterance-final H tone is faithfully realised as H in Guinean Kpelle, as shown in Figure 1. Guinean Kpelle also features a boundary extra-high H% tone, which is not covered in this study.

Tones and final lowering in Mano

Guinean Mano has three contrastive lexical Low/Mid/High tones, e.g. *lè* ‘place’, *lè* copula, *lé* attention drawing marker (Khachatryan et al., 2022).

Crucially, in Mano, High tone surfaces as Mid on the utterance-final tone bearing unit (1); and final H lowering only appears on utterance boundaries. This is further illustrated in Figure 2.

(1) H → M / _##

While final lowering is gradient in intonation-only languages like English, the Mano H lowering results in a change of tone category, as is often the case in African tone languages (Gussenhoven, 2004, pp. 110–113), e.g. in Kukuya (Hyman, 1987).

Phonologically, final H lowering in Mano is, however, rather peculiar. Bisyllabic morphemes like *sónó* ‘near’ are arguably lexically associated with a single underlying /H/ melody in Mano since lexical rules refer to the underlying tones in Mano, e.g. Imperfective lowering: *pélé* ‘wash’ → *pèlè* ‘wash:IPFV’. Yet, final High lowering only affects H associated with the last TBU in Mano: /sónó###/ → [sónó###], [*sónó###]. It thus does not refer to the underlying lexical /H/, but rather to the surface string of H tones, picking the last TBU. Therefore, while its phonological implementation is categorical (H → M), it operates as a late postlexical rule, just like the intonational phenomena.

Figure 1. No final lowering in L1 Kpelle production

Figure 2. Final lowering in L1 Mano production

Data collection and methods

Data and participants

In this study, we analyse a dataset containing semi-spontaneous utterances based on a questionnaire with 20 pictures, originally devised and recorded to study the variation in Mano reflexive marking (Khachaturyan et al. 2024) and not intended for phonetic/phonological analysis. The collected data were recorded using a Zoom Q8 camera with in-built stereo microphone in a natural setting, usually in the speakers' households in their villages of residence. Hence, the average quality of the available recordings was rather poor, so we only selected the recordings where the participant's voice was stronger and having no overlapping noises.

This study is based on a subset of recordings from 22 adult participants (8 females and 12 males; 5 speakers were recorded in Kpelle and 17 in Mano) collected by Pé Mamy, our Guinean collaborator, between February 2022 and July 2023. Prior to elicitation, a sociolinguistic questionnaire was collected for each

speaker. There were 687 utterances in total in our dataset.

We use the term Mano L1 to refer to speakers who were socialized exclusively in monolingual Mano families (biological and adoptive) and reside in Mano-dominant villages. We compare their tone production with that of three bilingual speaker groups (Mano 2L1 speakers socialized in Mano-speaking families, Bi/Kpelle 2L1 speakers socialized in bilingual and Kpelle-speaking families, Mano L2 speakers having Kpelle as their L1), as well as baseline Kpelle L1 speakers. By 2L1 we understand speakers who were exposed to both Mano and Kpelle from early childhood; and Mano L2 speakers in our sample were exposed to Mano primarily from adolescence or adulthood, from 15 years or later.

Transcription and annotations

Both Mano and Kpelle recordings were originally transcribed in Elan software (ELAN, 2023) by Pé Mamy, a native speaker of Mano and Kpelle. The transcriptions were later manually checked for accuracy by the co-authors, based on

their language expertise, and exported to Praat (version 6.03.05, Boersma & Weenink, 2023). The recordings were segmented into several units on separate TextGrid tiers: utterances, morphemes with glosses, and segments, i.e. consonants and vowels.

The vowels were annotated on two additional tiers receiving two labels: the *expected* surface tone, based on our prior expertise and the Mamy’s transcription, and second, the *attested* surface tone, based on the first author’s auditory impression complemented by visual inspection of the f_0 trace in Praat. Utterance-final H was labelled as expected H#.

The segmented and annotated text-grids for each speaker were then fed to a Praat script written by Juraj Šimko. The script (i) collected all the categorical labels in the relevant tiers, (ii) extracted mean f_0 from the vowel segments with manually adjusted speaker-specific floor and ceiling settings. During the post-processing phase, raw f_0 values were transformed to semitones with speaker-specific reference (individual median f_0).

Measurements and statistics

The present study is based on a dataset containing 189 tokens of utterance-final H# tones in Mano and Kpelle recordings, including 109 HH#, 64 LH# and 13 MH# transitions. As we demonstrate in Konoshenko et al. (n.d.), automatic downstep influences the realization of H after both L and M. For this reason and given that the other two transitions are less frequent, we only focus on HH# sequences here.

For each pair of adjacent tones, a *transition* between mean f_0 values was calculated by subtracting f_0 value of the present vowel segment from that of the preceding one. In our previous study (Konoshenko et al. in prep), we found that tone space, operationalised as the difference between median H and median L values, was different across speaker types, being the largest in Mano

L1 and the smallest in Kpelle L1. For this reason, f_0 transition values were normalised for speaker-type specific tone space before statistical modeling.

To explore the variation in HH# transitions, we fitted a linear mixed-effect regression model having the normalized f_0 *transition value* as dependent variable and *speaker type* as a fixed categorical predictor. Individual *speakers* and *lexical items* were modelled as random intercepts.

The statistical analysis was implemented by using `lme4` package (Bates et al., 2024) in RStudio (RStudio Team, 2024), with the `lmerTest` package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017) for estimating p -values (alpha level set at .05).

Results

Table 1 shows how the utterance-final /H#/ realisations were categorically labelled in different speaker types.

Table 1. Expected /H#/ across speaker types

Speaker type	[H]	[H?]	[M]	[M?]
Mano L1	0	1	34	1
Mano 2L1	0	0	11	1
Bi/Kpelle 2L1	9	1	6	0
Mano L2	21	0	1	2
Kpelle L1	20	0	0	0

Table 1 suggests that Mano L1 and Mano 2L1 speakers generally lowered /H#/ to [M], while both non-lowered [H] and [M] were attested in Bi/Kpelle 2L1 speakers. Non-lowered [H] was strictly dominant in Mano L2 production, and there was no lowering in Kpelle L1 speech.

Normalised HH# f_0 transition values plotted in Figure 3 below confirm the results obtained from categorical annotation. Figure 3 shows that Mano L1 and 2L1 speakers generally lowered /H#/.

Figure 3. Final lowering across speaker types

Bi/Kpelle 2L1 type had both lowered and non-lowered realisations. Finally, the HH# transition was most often realised as a minimal rise of a little over 0 st in Mano L2 and Kpelle L1 production, which was typical for HH sequences in our data.

Regression model also returned a significant effect of speaker type on the normalised HH# f_0 transition value. The transition value was significantly higher in both Mano L2 and Kpelle L1 types, as opposed to Mano L1 coded as the reference level ($\beta = .49, t = 3.33, p < .01$ for Mano L2 and $\beta = .74, t = 3.03, p < .01$ for Kpelle L1). Note that recoding Bi/Kpelle 2L1 type as reference returned no significant difference between this type and Mano L2 as well as Kpelle L1.

Discussion

This study contributes to the discussion of sociotonic variation and the acquisition of allotonic rules (Qin, 2022) by showing that, unlike in Mano L1 production, final H lowering rule is generally not attested in Mano L2 speakers, despite their generally high tonal proficiency in Mano and, more specifically, in Mano Mid tone (Konoshenko et al., n.d.). Our tentative explanation is that, despite the clear functional association of final H lowering with utterance

boundaries, since Mano final H lowering is categorical in nature but applies postlexically, it may be more difficult to acquire than lexical rules, which are learned by L2 speakers as our prior evidence suggests.

This study also shows that 2L1 speakers socialized in Mano-speaking families systematically applied final lowering, while it was less consistent in 2L1 speakers socialized in bilingual or Kpelle-speaking families.

Methodologically, this study is based on recordings of semi-naturalistic speech allowing us to capture sociotonic variation in a more ecologically valid way (Stanford, 2016).

Conclusions

This is the first sociotonic study of allotonic variation in African multilingual environment. We have shown that utterance-final H lowering varies depending on the speakers' backgrounds and, crucially, it is not learned by Mano L2 speakers. It remains to be seen whether final lowering operates differently from other tone rules in Mano due to its postlexical nature, or whether tone rules – both lexical and postlexical – generally tend to be less productive in multilingual speech.

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Onomatopoeia in contact languages – similarities and differences between Meänkieli, Swedish, Finnish, Kven and Sami

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Abstract

There has not been much research on change of onomatopoeia in contact languages. The main question is what happens to onomatopoeic phonological structures when two or more languages with different structures meet and influence each other. What sounds onomatopoeic in one language may not do so in another language. A minority language of northern Sweden, Meänkieli, which is closely related to Finnish, spoken in parallel with Swedish since the 14th century, is analysed. Other languages studied are North Sami, spoken in the same area, and Kven, spoken in Norway, and Finnish. The methodology consists of lexicon excerption and phonological analysis.

The results show that Meänkieli uses initial consonant clusters, which are similar to, but not identical with, those of Swedish, in contrast with standard Finnish which uses no initial consonant clusters in onomatopoeic words. However, onomatopoeia in Meänkieli also shows similarities with south-western Finnish dialects in Finland, which use initial consonant clusters.

Introduction and background

Meänkieli is a minority language of Sweden with a long history along the Swedish-Finnish border where the Torne river is separating – or uniting – the two countries. The name Meänkieli (meaning “our language”) was officially established in Sweden in the year 2000.

Finnish, spoken in Finland is a Finno-Ugric language, as well as Meänkieli. Swedish, on the other hand, is a Germanic language. Finnish and Swedish have very different grammars, vocabularies and phonologies. The speakers of Meänkieli in Sweden are now to a large extent bilingual in Swedish and Meänkieli. The contact with Finland was impeded or interrupted when Sweden lost Finland to Russia in 1809. Meänkieli is considered to be a language, not a dialect of Finnish, mainly on linguistic grounds (Valijärvi, Blokland, Kangas, Ackermann-Boström & Kuoppa, 2022), but also on social and political grounds.

Figure 1. Map of the Meänkieli areas in Sweden (left) and Finland (right). The Kven areas in Norway are north and northwest of Sweden.

Onomatopoeia is here defined as speech sounds imitating non-speech sounds, but only conventionalized onomatopoeia is considered, i. e. onomatopoeia which is integrated in the phonology of the language, and not “wild forms” which may occur with an

individual speaker in a specific situation. In this context the question surges of how a language may adapt to phonologies of other languages.

Consonantal structures of Swedish and Standard Finnish

Swedish permits up to three consonants in word beginnings, the first one being an /s/, the second a voiceless stop and the third /l/, /j/, /r/ or /v/. Not all combinations are allowed (Sigurd, 1965). Standard Finnish on the other hand does not have any initial consonant clusters except in some, more recent, loan words (e.g. *kromosomi*), where two consonant clusters can be permitted. In older loan words, often from Swedish, consonants are deleted like in Swedish *strand* (*beach*) which has become *ranta*. In Meänkieli it is more common with initial two-consonant clusters in general, and it is common with two-consonant clusters in onomatopoeic words. However, Meänkieli does not generally have initial three-consonant clusters, except for in some varieties.

Standard Finnish and Finnish dialects

In Finland, Meänkieli is considered a dialect, belonging to the western dialects, more precisely the Norrbothnian dialects. Swedish and Finnish dialects have been spoken in parallel for many hundreds of years in Finland, and the same goes for Swedish and Meänkieli in Sweden.

Standard Finnish, was created in the 19th century and it is mainly a written language (and spoken as “general spoken language” in news casts etc.). Koponen (2014) writes that a thousand years ago, both Finnish and Swedish were different from what they are now and both languages existed mainly as spoken dialects. Unlike Swedish, Finnish originally could not have two (or three) consonants at the beginning of a word. When a word was borrowed into Finnish, all initial consonants other than

the last were generally dropped. Through the influence of Swedish, initial consonant groups (*klasi* (glass), *trappu* (stairs) etc.) gradually gained entry into the Western Finnish dialects and also into the written language. During the 19th century, however, a large part of them were thinned out again, in an effort to make the written language more like Eastern Finnish. In short, there has been influences between Finnish and Swedish in Finland for many years. And there has been influences from Swedish to Meänkieli in Sweden for many years. Still today, spoken Finnish consists of many different dialects.

Kven and Sami

Kven, closely related to Meänkieli, has initial consonant structures similar to Meänkieli. In North Sami up to three initial consonant clusters are possible, often an /s/ being the initial consonant (Svonni, 1993).

Research on onomatopoeia in language contact and language change

To our knowledge there has been very little, or none, research on onomatopoeia in language contact induced language change. Heikkonen (2014) studied onomatopoeia and sound symbolism in North Uralic languages focusing on terminology and etymologies.

Research questions

1. To what extent does Meänkieli have initial consonant clusters in onomatopoeic words?
2. What are the similarities between Meänkieli and Standard Finnish, Finnish dialects, Kven and North Sami for initial consonant clusters in onomatopoeic words?
3. How has Swedish in Finland and Swedish in Sweden influenced initial consonant clusters in Meänkieli?

Method and materials

Lexica of Swedish, Standard Finnish, Finnish dialects, Meänkieli, Kven and North Sami were manually searched for onomatopoeic words with initial consonant clusters. The search was quite unproblematic since beginnings of words are easy to search for in electronic dictionaries. The model used is that of Abelin (1999). The dictionaries are of different sizes so both absolute and relative frequencies will be presented. The study is thus on initial consonant clusters and the onomatopoeias connected with these. Of course, there are many alternative forms in the languages, and there are slight differences in meaning between the languages, but the focus has been on initial consonant clusters for onomatopoeic words, which is a rather uncomplicated category.

The following four online dictionaries were searched: *Meänkieli-ruotti sanakirja* (33 000 lexical entries), *Stora Finsk-svenska ordboken* (109 000 lexical entries), *Kven-norsk ordbok* (7 500 lexical entries), and *Nordsamisk-Norsk ordbok* (33 000 lexical entries). The dictionaries were searched for onomatopoeic words beginning with consonant clusters. Onomatopoeia in Swedish consonant clusters was studied in Abelin (1999), based on *Svenska Akademiens Ordlista* (135 000 lexical entries). Furthermore, a small dictionary of a variety of Meänkieli – Jellivaaransuomi (Winsa, 1992) – was excerpted.

Orthography in Finnish, Meänkieli, Kven and North Sami is quite phonemic, so only a few explanations of the pronunciations of the consonant letters are given here: The voiceless stops, represented by <p>, <t>, <k> in writing are non-aspirated in Finnish, Meänkieli and Kven. The <r> is often a dental trill.

Results

Meänkieli is similar to Swedish in using initial consonant clusters for onomatopoeia, and this differs much from standard Finnish. However, onomatopoeic meanings connected with consonant clusters are not identical to the use in Swedish but points to an independent development in Meänkieli. There are similar onomatopoeias in Meänkieli and Kven which we don't see in standard Finnish.

In tables 1, 2 and 3 examples of differences in initial consonant clusters and vocabularies are presented.

Figure 2 shows the percentages of onomatopoeic words with initial consonant clusters in the dictionaries of Swedish, Meänkieli, Kven and standard Finnish.

Table 1 exemplifies that where Swedish uses two- or three consonant clusters, Meänkieli uses two-consonant clusters, while standard Finnish uses single initial consonants.

In Table 2 we can see that Meänkieli and Kven are quite similar in terms of initial consonant clusters. This can be compared with Finnish in Table 1. None of the initial consonant clusters in Table 2 were found to be onomatopoeic in the North Sami dictionary.

For the entire dictionaries of Swedish, Meänkieli, Standard Finnish and Kven the percent onomatopoeic words with initial consonant clusters are: Meänkieli 4,4% (80 words), Swedish 3,8% (106 words), Kven 3,07% (18 words), and standard Finnish 0,3% (8 words), see Figure 2.

As stated above, the dictionaries are of different sizes, and the criteria for including different types of word may differ.

Table 1. Examples of onomatopoeic words in Swedish, Meänkieli, Standard Finnish, and English.

Swedish	Meänkieli	Standard Finnish	English
spruta	pruiskuta	ruiskuttaa	spray
klappa	klaputtaa	taputtaa	clap
knastra	prätistä	rätinä	crackle
skrapa	kravata	raaputa	scratch
kraxa	kraakua	kurjuu	croak
prassla	krapista	rapista	rustle
pladdra	klipistä	lörpötellä	babble
plaska	klutsuta	loiskia	splash
knacka	knakata	koputtaa	knock
knaka	kripsahtaa	narista	crack
knäppa	kräpsyttää	napsahtaa	snap
smattra	kropista	räätistä	clatter
smälla	plittoa	paukkua	bang
knattra	prätistä	päristä	rattle
blaska	frääkätä	roiskua	splash
skvätta	pläiskiä	räiskiä	splash
plumsa	klopsuttaa	roiskua	splash

Table 2. Examples of onomatopoeic words in Meänkieli and Kven.

Meänkieli	Kven
pruiskuta	truiskuta
klaputtaa	klaputa
kripsahtaa	naskuut
kraapasta	kraapasta
kraakua	kraakkuut
kravata	kravata
klopsuttaa	klopsuttaa
pläiskiä	truiskuta

Figure 2. Number of onomatopoeic words in relation to total number of words with initial consonant clusters, in the four dictionaries.

Finnish dialects

In *Suomen Murteiden Sanakirja* (The dictionary of Finnish dialects) many of

the Meänkieli onomatopoeic words were found, all of them in the south-western, southern or north-western parts of Finland. There are also many other non-onomatopoeic western dialectal Finnish words which begin with initial two-consonant clusters.

In *Suomen Murteiden Sanakirja* places in Sweden are specified as places for Finnish dialects. However, we have ignored those examples as examples of Finnish dialects, since they refer to Meänkieli, and in that dictionary we have only looked at examples from Finland. A large part of the dialectal onomatopoeic words with initial consonant clusters are from the south-western part, where Swedish has long been spoken. There are also many other two- or three-consonant cluster words, quite a few of them are loan words from Swedish. There is one three consonant clusters which does not exist in Swedish, namely *skl-*.

All the Finnish dialectal words presented in Table 3 come from the south-western, southern or sometimes north-western areas of Finland, areas where Swedish is spoken. Of course, there is a lot of variation.

Some characteristics of Jellivaaran-suomi

Even though we did not find great differences in onomatopoeia between the Meänkieli of Torne valley variety and the Jellivaaransuomi variety, spoken around the town of Gällivare in Sweden, some characteristics must be mentioned. Jellivaaransuomi can sometimes have up to three initial consonants with the first one being an /s/. This is similar to the consonant structure of Swedish, but the

/s/ is added in a unique manner, which is shown by the following examples, e.g. *spricka* from Swedish *bricka* (tray), *strappu* from Swedish *trappa* (stairs) and *trallari* from Swedish *rallare* (railway worker). Could this be an influence from Swedish or North Sami (which also can have up to three initial consonant clusters (Svonni, 1993) or could it be cases of hypercorrection? However, a similar phenomenon is also found in Helsinki slang “Stadin slangi” where we find additions of initial consonants.

Table 3. Examples of onomatopoeic words in Meänkieli, with the addition from different Finnish dialects. Cf. Table 1.

Finnish dialects	Meänkieli	Standard Finnish	English
	pruiskuta	ruiskuttaa	spray
klaputtaa	klaputtaa	taputtaa	clap
	prätistä	rätinä	crackle
krapata, skrapata	Kravata	raaputa	scratch
kraakua	kraakua	kurjuu	croak
krapista	krapista	rapista	rustle
klipistä	klipistä	lörpötellä	babble
klutsuttaa	klutsuta	loiskia	splash
knakata	knakata	koputtaa	knock
kripsahtaa	kripsahtaa	narista	crack
kräpsyttää	kräpsyttää	napsahtaa	snap
kropista	kropista	räätitä	clatter
plittuuna	plittoa	paukkua	bang
	prätistä	päristä	rattle
fräkätä	frääkätä	roiskua	splash
	pläiskiä	räiskiä	splash
klopsuttaa	klopsuttaa	roiskua	splash

Discussion

Could it be that Meänkieli has retained clusters from earlier stages, which have since disappeared in Standard Finnish? And has Meänkieli been influenced by Swedish several times? Many of the word forms of Meänkieli are almost identical to those in some of the Finnish dialects. The results suggest that the onomatopoeic words are quite robust in Meänkieli and have not changed much from their dialectal, mostly south-western, origins, areas where also Swedish has been spoken for a long time. However, it is very possible that Meänkieli in Sweden has continued to be influenced

by Swedish, and North Sami. This could also be the explanation of the initial consonant structures of Jellivaaransuomi.

Jellivaaransuomi shows that Meänkieli could continue to be influenced by surrounding languages. Another factor could be that Jellivaaransuomi is spoken further away from the Finnish border.

Conclusions

First, Meänkieli has a large number of onomatopoeic initial consonant clusters, which are similar to Swedish. Secondly, Meänkieli differs from standard Finnish in this respect, but it is quite similar to some Finnish dialects and to Kven. At

this stage it is too early to answer the third research question and say whether onomatopoeic initial consonant clusters in Meänkieli are remnants from older Swedish influences on older Finnish dialects, or influences from Swedish in Sweden, or possibly from North Sami. Our original idea was that Meänkieli has been influenced only by Swedish in Sweden, but everything seems to point to Meänkieli having preserved onomatopoeic words and clusters from western Finnish dialects, where the dialects were influenced by Swedish very long ago. Meänkieli has also been influenced by Swedish in Sweden, where Meänkieli has been spoken since the 14th century. However, due to the political situation of isolation in Sweden, Meänkieli has also developed along its own path.

Meänkieli is classified as a northern Finnish dialect in Finland, but in the case of onomatopoeia it is clear that Meänkieli has many similarities with south-western Finnish dialects.

It is well known that onomatopoeia differs from language to language, to a large extent depending on the phonology and phonotactics of each language. The general question which remains to be solved is: can onomatopoeia in one language be influenced by onomatopoeia in another language? That is, can the speakers of one language adapt to onomatopoeia of another language? We would like to answer yes to this question, but it is clear that more research is needed on onomatopoeia in languages in contact.

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Cross-linguistic competition across three languages in L3 Swedish spoken sentences

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Abstract

Efficient word recognition is crucial for speech comprehension. In multilinguals, it can be affected by parallel language activation creating cross-linguistic competition triggered by word form similarity to the input. However, findings for bilinguals' sentence processing diverge, and little is yet known about trilinguals, whose both non-target languages can compete (Bartolotti & Marian, 2018; Lijewska, 2022). This study investigated whether third language (L3) speech comprehension could be affected by lexical competition across three languages, and whether sentential context could modulate single and double cross-linguistic competition. Forty-four Russian-English late L3-Swedish learners aged 22 – 60 did a lexical selection task while listening to Swedish sentences that were low or highly constraining towards a target noun and seeing two pictures (the target and its competitor). Participants' reaction times (RTs) and accuracy were collected. The competitor's Russian phonological onset could overlap with the target's Swedish onset (e.g., /'moʎn'ijə/, 'lightning' and /mo:l/ 'goal'); the competitor could be a Swedish-English cognate (e.g., *bok* – *book*) or be a cognate and overlap (e.g., *hammare* – *hammer* – /møʎe'tok/). The results revealed shorter RTs and higher accuracy in high- than low-constraint sentences. However, phonological competition made the overall accuracy significantly lower and RTs in the high-constraint sentences longer. In contrast, single English and double Russian-English competition effects were not significant. Longer Russian-speaking country residence (or delayed L3-immersion) made the participants slower. The results suggest that top-down information from sentential context could not significantly modulate bottom-up driven first-language phonological competition. The pattern is inconsistent with the BIA+ model (Dijkstra & van Heuven, 2002) but aligns with BLINCS (Shook & Marian, 2013), which requires further investigation and suggests the need for *multilingual* mental lexicon models. The study informs on trilinguals, whose numbers are increasing but who remain unrepresented in research, and sets further questions, e.g., how language status and learning history affect cross-linguistic interactions.

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Markers of decision points in three classical collaborative ranking tasks

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Abstract

In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a major shift from offline to online activities in the meeting realm, we collected the MEET corpus to systematically examine the effects of collocated (physical), remote (digital), and hybrid work meetings on collaborative decision-making (Esfandiari-Baiat & Edlund, 2024). The corpus contains purposeful meetings following Goffman (1961), with focused interaction maintaining a single focus of cognitive and visual attention through collaborative tasks. We recorded ten sessions of three meetings where participants completed a different classical ranking task in each meeting: the Camping game survival task (Hare, 1952), the NASA moon survival task (Hall & Watson, 1970), and the Desert survival task (Lafferty & Pond, 1974). Each session contains one collocated, one remote and one hybrid meeting with the same three participants.

Here, we describe the first steps towards annotation that will allow us to describe the ranking tasks as an incremental decision process and compare participant behaviours at similar steps along the process. We present the current state of the annotation alongside examples of speech and communicative behaviours occurring when participants *question*, *propose*, and *decide*.

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Swedish Embodied Pronunciation Training: a project presentation

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Abstract

Research has shown that gestures can have beneficial effects on second language (L2) pronunciation learning. However, we still do not have a coherent picture of these effects, because different studies have investigated different gestures and usually either considered segmental (Hoetjes & van Maastricht, 2020; Iizuka et al., 2020; Li & Somlak, 2019; Xi et al., 2020) or prosodic (Morett & Chang, 2015; Yuan et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2018) features, but not both, and mostly either tested learners' production or perception. Importantly, most of these studies have been conducted in a lab setting rather than in an authentic classroom setting.

This project aims to study the effects of embodied training, using gestures, on pronunciation learning in Swedish, in two lab studies and two classroom studies. Two studies (one in each setting) will focus on a segmental feature, namely the Swedish vowel contrast /i/≠/y/, while the other two will focus on a prosodic one, more specifically the Swedish length contrast (*vila* ≠ *villa*).

The studies will assess both learners' perception and production of these phonological features before and after a training phase, through a pre-/post-/delayed post-test design. The instruction phase will consist of a video training learners on the given contrast in three different conditions (between subjects), plus a control group (no training): one group without gestures (audiovisual speech only condition), and the other two groups will receive training with two different gestures. The gesture conditions are currently being defined based on interviews conducted with teachers of Swedish as a second language.

Learners' production in the pre- and post-tests will be assessed through native speaker ratings and acoustic analysis. Perception will be measured through identification or discrimination tasks, but also using eye-tracking, providing a continuous measure of learners' processing abilities.

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Towards a sustainable approach regarding speech and language technology! What standards/guidelines are needed?

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Abstract

Introduction: Big data is essential regarding use of speech and language technology. Our focus in this study is on internet of things and how it can clean and structure annotation of raw speech data. We further focus on data reusability value and creation of standards available through open source databases. Our goal is to combine user epigenetic/genetic with best possible speech and language technology to design therapies for people suffering from stuttering.

Background: About 1% of Swedish population suffers from stuttering. More men than women are affected. Stuttering is more frequent among children than adults. World-wide about 70 millions people are affected by stuttering and 3 millions of them live in USA.

Method: There is currently a Smith and Weber-Fox's neurodevelopmental, epigenetic model available for stuttering. We aim to correlate this model with internet of things and how it can clean and structure annotation of raw speech data in order to stimulate the stuttering individual towards self-awareness of its speech and how we can help the individual towards stutter free speech.

Results: A simulation demo will be available on the presenter's laptop at the conference in order to show how individuals suffering from stuttering can be stimulated into a stuttering free life.

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Request For Comments: A functionally motivated Swedish phoneme inventory for speech technology

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Abstract

The design of existing phoneme inventories for speech technology has been governed by a wide and varying range of criteria, from computational limitations on character encoding to theory-laden decision and occasionally by coincidence and laziness. One of the most prolific systems is the Swedish SAMPA and more recently subsets of IPA. In practice, at least for Swedish, there are subtle differences in the phoneme inventories for many, if not most applications. These inventories are rarely well-documented, nor are the design choices explicitly motivated.

The national research infrastructure Språkbanken Tal (the speech branch of Språkbanken) is in the process of releasing a range of tools and models for Swedish speech technology. As part of this, we are specifying a common Swedish phoneme inventory for speech technology. The phoneme inventory is functionally and pragmatically motivated rather than theoretically, with key requirements including ease of use, avoiding conflicts with for example source code, and platform independence.

The current draft specification is largely based on a phoneme inventory that the Swedish Agency for Accessible Media has adapted from earlier phoneme sets. We will present the draft and the underlying design criteria, and we hope for feedback and comments which we will incorporate into the next version, which we aim to present at the Swedish Speech Technology Conference later this year (SLTC 2024).

